

**The Role of Twitter in Shaping Political
Communication: A Case Study of Pakistan**

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Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the
University of the West of Scotland for the award of Doctor of
Philosophy.

October 2025

Abstract

This thesis examines the role of Twitter in shaping political communication in Pakistan, with a focus on how political actors construct, frame, and disseminate strategic narratives in a hybrid media environment. Using an interpretivist research philosophy, the study draws on qualitative data from elite interviews with political leaders, party media teams, and senior journalists, complemented by data collected via the Twitter API. Three key recent political events in Pakistan provide a focus to understand how digital media intersect with historically embedded political structures, provincial demographics, and partisan divides. Applying framing theory and public sphere theory as dual lenses, the study reveals the evolving role of Twitter as the primary platform for initiating political messages in Pakistan. The findings suggest that Twitter functions as an elite digital sphere where political parties construct narratives which are then amplified by journalists and media outlets. Unlike previous eras where legacy media held exclusive control over political discourse, the findings show that traditional media now often follow Twitter's lead, sourcing content and cues from politicians' tweets. Individual journalists further amplify these messages, and their personal biases, professional affiliations, and financial incentives contribute to an increasingly fragmented and politicised information environment. The study highlights how digital media platforms have not only shifted the locus of narrative control but also exacerbated issues of misinformation, unethical journalism, and political bias. This study contributes to the literature on political communication in non-Western contexts by illustrating how Pakistan's digital political sphere is shaped by the convergence of technological affordances, entrenched political cultures, and media fragmentation. It argues that while Twitter empowers political actors to set agendas and mobilise publics, the hybrid media environment continues to reshape democratic engagement and journalistic practices in complex and often problematic ways.

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DECLARATION

This research project serves as a partial submission for the Doctor of Philosophy degree at the University of the West of Scotland. I affirm that the work presented herein is my original contribution. Any information obtained from external sources has been appropriately cited in the thesis.

Throughout the duration of my registered studies while preparing this thesis, I have not pursued any other academic awards or qualifications. The content included in this thesis has not been submitted, in whole or in part, for any academic award or qualification other than that for which it is currently being submitted.

Naheed Akhtar

Acknowledgments

First and foremost, I would like to express my deepest gratitude to my lead supervisor, Professor David McGillivray, for his unwavering support, encouragement, and expert guidance throughout this PhD journey. His consistent moral and professional support helped me stay grounded during some of the most challenging moments of my life. I am equally grateful to my other supervisory team members, Dr Ross Campbell and Dr Margaret Hughes, along with my assessor, Professor Graham Jeffery, whose insights, constructive feedback, and ongoing encouragement have been invaluable in shaping this research. I could not have completed this work without their collective belief in my potential and the consistent academic guidance they provided.

Pursuing a PhD in the UK was a dream that my mother and I shared. This dream became a reality, but one that came with immense personal sacrifice. The past three and a half years have been the most testing period of my life. Coming to a new country, adapting to a different culture, raising two young children, facing financial challenges, and navigating a global pandemic, all while coping with the immense grief of losing both of my parents, has been a journey beyond words.

The woman who first dreamed of this PhD and the woman writing this acknowledgement are not the same person. This process has reshaped me entirely. While the hardships were immense, they were accompanied by growth, learning, and transformation. This PhD has not only been an academic journey but also a profoundly personal one. I have learned more than I ever

imagined, not only about my subject area, but about perseverance, time management, and self-discipline.

As someone who spent 15 years working as a journalist, I have always had a deep interest in transitioning into academia. This PhD allowed me to explore that passion fully. I have grown intellectually, professionally, and personally. I learned to navigate research ethics, refined my writing and analytical skills, and developed a deep appreciation for research methodologies. I also learned how to manage multiple roles: as a full-time mother, a wife, a PhD researcher, and a working professional, taking on responsibilities as a research assistant and associate lecturer. Balancing these roles has taught me the value of resilience, discipline, and self-compassion.

I dedicate this work to my late parents, whose unwavering love, prayers, and belief in me brought me this far. It remains one of my deepest regrets that they could not see me complete this milestone, and I could not say a final goodbye. Their absence has been a profound loss, but their memory continues to guide me.

To my children, who have grown up watching me work late nights and long weekends, I hope this journey teaches them that dreams are achievable, no matter the odds. You celebrated every small milestone with me, and your joy became my motivation. I am especially grateful to my husband, who stood by me throughout this journey. His support, both emotional and practical, enabled me to keep going through moments of exhaustion, grief, and doubt. He took on responsibilities at home, cared for our children when I needed time, and reminded me constantly that I could do this.

Finally, I would like to thank all my PhD colleagues who have been an inspiration to me since I joined UWS. The rich academic discussions with them have truly expanded my knowledge and have helped me to meet my goals. I will always be grateful for their encouragement and

kindness. This PhD is not just a personal achievement, but a collective one shaped by the support and generosity of so many.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Personal and Professional Motivations

Having spent fifteen years in journalism as a field reporter, sub-editor, and news producer in Pakistan, witnessing the evolution of news media, I decided to embark on a PhD that focused on contemporary academic debates about news media and politics. I worked as a field journalist in the news media, which experienced a dramatic change over a relatively brief period of time. It was a time when the media in Pakistan experienced a degree of freedom awarded by a dictator, President Pervaiz Musharraf. In 2002, private media channels were licensed to operate in Pakistan by the then-President Gen. Pervaiz Musharraf through the Pakistan Electronic Media Regulatory Authority (PEMRA) ordinance. At that time, the Pakistani media entered a new phase, moving from state-owned to private, from print to electronic. This was the time when Pakistan, as a US strategic partner, occupied the main stage of the global war on terror, with terrorism-related stories being the main content for 24/7 news media coverage. Large media groups, including Jang (Geo), Nawa-e-Waqt, Dawn, Express, and ARY, were the first to launch their news channels. News and entertainment electronic media became a lucrative market within a few years, and I was one of the reporters who had the opportunity to join this expanding profession. These private news channels were broadcasting live terrorist attacks and state operations against terrorists. The Pakistan Institute of Peace Studies published a report in 2010 outlining how electronic media outlets in Pakistan invited militant leaders onto their live programmes to generate higher ratings (Hassan, 2014). As the state and its allies began to exercise control of terrorism, the media industries needed different content for their screens. Political talk shows took over prime screen time and TV anchors became celebrities. As Hussain (2012, p. 54) argues, they were making “villains and heroes, terrorists and leaders”. Political leaders and representatives of public offices were dependent on the mainstream news media to defend their policies. Following trends associated with the evolution of technologies

around the world, Pakistani media channels began to use social media content for their news stories. We have now become used to journalists using these platforms to break stories and as a source of their reporting because the public now debates social issues on social media. Alongside the presence of journalists, mainstream media, and the public on social media platforms like Twitter (now X), political parties and politicians also began to use these spaces to post their messages, criticise opponents and government policies, and run their political campaigns.

Along with working in journalism full-time and witnessing the rapid changes in media, public attitudes and politicians, I continued studying on a part-time basis. In 2012, after completing a master's degree in political science, I started researching political systems and comparing activities in my own country with those in other parts of the world. At that point, I started to investigate more seriously the relationship between news media and politics. My first research enquiry focused on the discourses on Pakistani electronic media and their impact on state policy against the 'Global War on Terrorism'. I worked on news coverage patterns of terrorism-related incidents by leading news channels, including Geo, Express, ARY, and Dunya news, to investigate their alignment with the state's antiterrorism policy. I also began to explore the agenda setting role of electronic media. However, I always had a desire to further explore the role of new media (social media) in political communication, especially in response to the growth of social media platforms. I embarked on this thesis to quench that academic thirst. Based on my understanding of the changing role of mainstream media due to social media, where there is two-way communication, no editorial checks, and more voices included, I wanted to explore the academic debates about the phenomenon and how those compare to the situation in Pakistan. Reporting in the field of political communication for more than a decade in Pakistan, I had a clear understanding of the political culture and media landscape and well-established connections with senior journalists and political party media managers. I wanted to

utilise these strengths to undertake doctoral studies in the field of political communication in Pakistan with a particular focus on the strategic use of Twitter for political communication.

As the focus of this research is to investigate the role of social media in shaping political communication, it is essential to understand the overall political culture, the nature of political campaigns, voter behaviours, and other complexities that are linked to and affect political communication in Pakistan. The next section of this introductory chapter outlines the country's historical and contemporary political culture to set the scene for how social media is transforming the practice of political communication.

1.2 Political culture in Pakistan: A brief historical overview

Political culture is one of the most central concepts of political science. It was first introduced by two American authors, Almond and Verba (1963) in their book *The Civic Culture: The Political Attitudes and Democracy in Five Nations*. They introduced the idea that a stable democracy depends not only on institutions but also on citizens' political attitudes and behaviours. Their typology, parochial, subject, and participant political cultures, offers a valuable lens for understanding Pakistan's hybrid political environment¹. In Pakistan, where democratic institutions remain fragile and elite dominance persists, political culture is shaped by both limited public trust and increasing digital participation. This context helps explain how strategic political communication on platforms like Twitter interacts with and reflects the broader political culture. Siddiqi (2020) suggests that the culture of political parties in Pakistan influences public views about politics in the country. He also suggests that every political party has its subculture and operates as an ideational agent that shapes narratives, beliefs, and values in the public sphere. Siddiqi goes on to argue that the connection between political parties and

¹ Political culture is referenced in this thesis solely as contextual background to situate the Pakistani political environment and is not employed as a conceptual or analytical framework for the analysis

individuals in Pakistan is based on parties presenting their agendas in the form of beliefs to the public. Individuals choose to vote for parties that they associate as being closer to their own beliefs and values. Siddiqi (2020) highlights six characteristics of Pakistani politics in terms of its political culture. First, he suggests that it is dynastic politics. For example, the third generation of the Pakistan People's Party (PPP) is fighting for power in 2025. Former Prime Minister Zulfikar Bhutto's daughter Benazir Bhutto became Prime Minister (from 1988 to 1990, and again from 1993 to 1996), and in 2025, Bilawal Bhutto, Benazir Bhutto's son, is the party's chairman. He has also served as the Federal Minister for Foreign Affairs in Pakistan. PPP is one of the largest political parties in Pakistan but Pakistan Muslim League Nawaz (PMLN), the second most influential political party, also has first and second generations in power. However, while the main parties have dynastic power, Pakistan Tehreek-e-Insaf (PTI), which has emerged as a powerful political party, is newer and does not have the legacy of the other two.

Siddiqi (2020) states that the second element of political culture is the dominant aspect of the personality cult within the political parties of Pakistan. He suggests that it is not the agenda or manifesto of these parties that is presented to the people, but rather the personas of their leaders. In this cult, leaders are depicted as flawless heroes, whether military or civilian. Siddiqi traces the history of personality-centred politics, beginning with Jinnah, the first governor-general of Pakistan in 1947; followed by Ayub Khan, president from 1958 to 1969; Zulfikar Ali Bhutto, Prime Minister from 1973 to 1977; Zia-ul-Haq (1978-1988); Pervez Musharraf, President from 2001 to 2008; Nawaz Sharif, Prime Minister for three non-consecutive terms (first from 1990 to 1993, second from 1997 to 1999, and third from 2013 to 2017); Benazir Bhutto, Prime Minister from 1988 to 1990 and again from 1993 to 1996; and currently Imran Khan, Prime Minister from 2018 to 2022. Each of these figures has been portrayed as a saviour of the country and nation by their followers. As Siddiqi (2020) indicated:

This leadership is idealised by the public as a form of deliverance from social ills such as corruption or positively related to the dynamic of economic growth and development, including provisions for employment, education and health (p., 544).

The third feature of Pakistan's political culture, according to Siddiqi (2020), is the practice of producing slogans that challenge corruption and support calls for greater accountability in politics. Hussain, Sajid and Jullandhry (2018) highlighted this feature in their research on political party advertisements for the 2013 General Elections. They suggest that "The Pakistan Tehreek-e-Insaaf (PTI) published 41% of their campaign advertisements for the youth; while it stood at only 13% for PML-N and 33% for the PPP with the PTI messaging highlighting corruption as a cause of youth brain-drain from the country" (p.8). Saleem (2017) also expresses the view that PTI took full advantage of their anti-corruption narrative when a Supreme Court decision for a Panama corruption case scandal ousted former Prime Minister Nawaz Sharif. It was the same narrative, 'corruption-free Naya (new) Pakistan', that brought victory to PTI in the 2018 General Election (Shah, 2019).

Fourth, there is a tendency of a clear divide between civil and military leadership as political parties claim to be the democratic forces and providers of economic stability, and military regimes blame politicians for being self-serving, corrupt elites. The same division is evident in the narratives and beliefs of the public in Pakistan. The divide is evident in the political power history of the country as well as in the form of periodic rules by the military dictatorship and the political parties in Pakistan. Siddiqi further suggests that this divide extends into the different priorities of government structures in Pakistan at different times. For instance, the federalised unitary government structure is supported by military regimes and the sharing of federal power with provinces is supported by political regimes.

The fifth characteristic of the political culture of Pakistan highlighted by Siddiqi suggests that religiously oriented political parties are not supported by the dominating majority of the country. Islam is a central feature of political discourse overall in the country, and all dominating political parties tend to project their leaders as Muslim heroes, but religious parties like Jamat-e-Islami, Jamiat-e-Ullemas Islam, and Tehreek-e-Labaik have never been elected into government. Instead, they have only been part of the government with other dominating political parties (Islam, 2013; Siddiqi, 2018). Sixth, ethnic minorities, which were part of Pakistan at the time of partition, are considered at the receiving end of the political culture. However, current political powers are sensitive about the issue after the 18th amendment made in the constitution of Pakistan in 2010 to decentralise the power and make provincial governments more autonomous, and there is a representation of minorities in both the provincial and federal houses.

Chak (2014) suggests the presence of three schools of thought in Pakistan's political culture. The first school is traditionalists who resist change and development, believing that the welfare of the state and society can be ensured by following the tenets of Islam. Secularists, the second school of thought, are inspired by the British colonialist Western idea of the state, which emphasises a separation from religion and the indigenous societal values of Pakistan. This applies only to the privileged class. The revivalists, the third school of thought, are inclined to take an intermediary approach and believe in progressing forward with contemporary economic and societal needs, holding the basis of the ideology of Pakistan laid by the founder of Pakistan, Muhammad Ali Jinnah and his fellows. Chak (2014), however, argues that all three schools are in tension with each other, and this is the cause of many conflicts in Pakistan. In addition to the elements of political culture and schools of thought in Pakistan, there are provincial dynamics as well. Prominent political parties have different levels of influence in different provinces in Pakistan. Every province has a different level of education, poverty,

cultural values, media and internet penetration. The next section further highlights these complexities in detail which will help to understand the campaigning strategies of political parties in different parts of the country.

1.3 Political elites and provincial politics in Pakistan

Ashfaq and Roofi (2023) argue that political culture in Pakistan is dominated by multiple elites, who also influence voter behaviours and choices (Ashfaq and Roofi, 2023; Rizvi, 2013). There are the military, bureaucrats, industrial elites, religious and political elites. In addition, every province has a distinct political culture because of its historical background. Shabbir and Haider (2023) have suggested that every province has its own ways of contributing to the overall political system of Pakistan. For example:

Punjab's history is marked by its prominent role in the pre-Partition era, while Sindh has a rich historical heritage that influences its politics. Balochistan, with its history of insurgency and ethnic diversity, presents a different historical backdrop. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa has its unique historical factors, shaped by tribal traditions and religious affiliations (p., 672).

However, they highlight that Punjab is the powerhouse of Pakistani politics. It is the most populous province of Pakistan and is dominated by business, religious and feudal elites. Different political parties have different levels of strength based on their ideological bases in each province. For instance, PPP has its stronger roots in Sindh, while Awami National Party (ANP) has its stronger roots in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK). The Pakistan Muslim League has historically dominated in Punjab. Pakistan Tehreek-e-Insaaf took the lead in KPK and Punjab in the 2018 elections and formed a government at the federal level. Sindh remained dominated by PPP.

This section has provided insight about the dynamics of political culture in Pakistan, highlighting that the impact of each political party depends on several factors, including the history of each province on the political map of the country. Before outlining the prevailing forms of political communication and campaigning in Pakistan, it is essential to describe the types and behaviours of voters in Pakistan to understand the importance of communication priorities for political parties during their campaigns.

1.4 Political culture and voter behaviour in Pakistan

Yousaf (2016) has highlighted six categories of voters in Pakistan targeted by political parties during marketing campaigns. First, the religious group is claimed by religious political parties like Jamiat-e-Ul-lema Islam, Jamat-e-Islami, and Tehreek-e-Labbaik Pakistan. These voters are scattered throughout the country in all provinces, but none of the religious political parties of the country has a stronghold on any one province. Yousaf also quotes the Election Commission of Pakistan, according to which it is illegal to ask for votes in the name of religion. However, apart from religious political parties, all other parties tend to garner votes by presenting themselves as more closely aligned with religion during their political campaigns. Shabbir and Haider (2023) noted this trend in their research about political voter behaviour in Punjab during the 2018 elections:

During the 2018 general elections in Pakistan, political parties were observed manipulating religion to achieve their political objectives in various ways. Some parties strategically aligned themselves with religious groups or leaders to garner support, emphasising their commitment to Islamic values (p., 677).

Yousaf notes that the religious and political parties have ardent support from certain parts of Pakistani society and that strong support helps them get some seats at the provincial and

national levels. These parties exploit this power by offering support to the main political parties to participate in government through seat adjustments.

The second type of vote bank is ideological voters. These are the people who affiliate with certain political parties for ideological reasons. For instance, the Pakistan Muslim League was founded by Quaid-e-Azam Muhammad Ali Jinnah and represents the freedom movement. It had historically enjoyed a huge sentimental support from the people of Pakistan. It has now been divided into different party groups. Third, the victim vote bank, which is historically aligned with the Pakistan People's Party (PPP). Originating with a socialist ideology, the party was founded by Zulfikar Ali Bhutto, former Prime Minister of Pakistan, who was hanged during dictator Zia-ul-Haq's regime. The people of Pakistan supported his daughter, Benazir Bhutto, to become the Prime Minister of Pakistan twice. "Bhutto was alive and is alive" was the most famous slogan in the rallies of PPP. Similarly, the assassination of former Prime Minister Benazir Bhutto at a public rally in December 2007 helped the PPP earn the sympathy vote from all over Pakistan and gain government (Yousaf, 2016). The government structure in Pakistan is divided into federal and provincial. The party that wins most seats at the provincial level forms the government at the federal level. Fourth, according to Yousaf, is a big vote bank of those political leaders positioning themselves as custodians and advocates of a specific tribe, cast, ethnic or social group. Politics in Pakistan has long been fixated with the ideological considerations of these social solidarity groups. The political choices individuals make are often subject to the influence of these large groups.

The fifth category according to Yousaf is the vote bank, rooted in the traditional power of feudal lords in interior Sindh and Punjab, where landowners exert significant influence over dependent communities. Unlike vote banks based on ideology, religion, or ethnicity, this type relies on hierarchical patron-client relationships in which political parties approach landlords, who in turn mobilise their tenants and followers to secure collective blocs of votes.

The hereditary ministers or descendants of Sufi tombs, who often lead the traditional Sufi rituals, also enjoy significant influence and respect among the followers, and thus are highly electable and in great demand as electoral candidates by the political parties (Yousaf, 2016, p., 142).

Yousaf also notes that the five vote banks still exist, but gradual changes are taking place, and a new type of vote bank is also emerging in Pakistan. The new vote bank comprises of those who have tested the afore-mentioned political representatives of political parties multiple times and are not happy with their performance. It also includes young people studying in universities and colleges that have access to digital devices, the internet and social media:

More than ever before, youngsters participated actively in the 2013 elections. The percentage of young voters climbed to 11% in the 2013 elections. It needs to be regarded as the first step towards political equality (Ahmad, Alvi and Ittefaq, 2019, p., 3)

According to the Election Commission of Pakistan, young people accounted for 34% of the overall vote bank because all these voters were under 31 years of age (ECP, 2013). This vote bank is mostly attracted by the comparatively new political party, Pakistan Tehreek-e-Insaf (PTI). This party has raised a slogan for change, for “New Pakistan.” The party has demonstrated its strength by securing the provincial government in 2013 and the federal government in the 2018 elections. Table 1.1 presents the latest number of voters by province and age as of July 2025.

Population by Age Group and Province (Number and Percentage)

Province	18-25	26-35	36-45	46-55	56-65	65+
Punjab	10,817,651 (18.48%)	16,100,424 (27.50%)	12,196,281 (20.83%)	8,768,570 (14.98%)	5,801,931 (9.91%)	4,860,134 (8.30%)
Sindh	4,348,019 (20.61%)	6,014,691 (28.51%)	4,310,344 (20.43%)	2,994,791 (14.20%)	1,921,621 (9.11%)	1,506,010 (7.14%)
Khyber Pakhtunkhwa	3,037,852 (19.33%)	4,244,073 (27.00%)	3,216,396 (20.47%)	2,294,872 (14.60%)	1,593,614 (10.14%)	1,329,563 (8.46%)
Balochistan	1,039,132 (19.10%)	1,420,787 (26.11%)	1,107,202 (20.35%)	798,005 (14.67%)	569,874 (10.47%)	505,767 (9.30%)

Table 1.1 Age-wise number of registered voters in Pakistan (ECP, 2025)

Graph 1.1 presents the number and percentages of registered voters by age group and province based on the latest data from the Election Commission of Pakistan.

Graph 1.1 Number of registered voters by age group and province (self-contribution)

Understanding the age-wise distribution of voters across provinces is crucial, as it aligns with the strategic focus observed in political parties' digital campaigns. The data reveal that a significant portion of Pakistan's electorate comprises young voters, particularly in provinces such as Punjab and Sindh. This demographic trend helps explain why political parties

increasingly prioritise youth-focused messaging and digital engagement, especially on platforms like Twitter, Facebook, and TikTok. According to data from the International Foundation for Electoral Systems (IFES, 2025), Pakistan was projected to have over 128 million registered voters for the 2024 General Elections. This demographic breakdown reveals that 54 per cent of the electorate comprises women, while 46 per cent are men. Notably, a significant proportion, 44 per cent of the total registered voters, fall within the age range of 18 to 35 years. Furthermore, it is noteworthy that approximately 22 million new voters have been registered between the 2018 and 2024 General Elections, according to IFES (2025). This data highlights the growing engagement of younger voters in Pakistan, which is a crucial factor for analysing the findings in the later chapters of the dissertation.

Shah and Majeed (2022) highlight that election trends and political culture differ across Pakistan based on other factors such as socioeconomic and educational status. Their research reveals that the Punjab province holds a vital role in shaping electoral trends in Pakistan's political system. Table 1.2, extracted from the National Assembly of Pakistan, explains the division of electoral seats allocated by province.

Province/Area	General Seats	Women seats	Non-Muslim Seats	Total seats
Balochistan	16	4		20
Khyber Pakhtunkhwa	45	10		55
Punjab	141	32	—	173
Sindh	61	14		75
Capital Territory/Islamabad	3			3
			10	
Total	266	60	10	336

Table 1.2 Province-wise National Assembly of Pakistan Seat Allocation

Punjab is the largest province in terms of population and holds the highest number of seats in the National Assembly of Pakistan, which contributes to forming the government for any political party that wins Punjab. “For decades, the electoral demography of Punjab is symbolic that the one who rules Punjab dominates in the centre as well.” (Shah, Majeed, 2022, p. 146).

Having outlined the political culture, provincial dynamics, and voter behaviour in Pakistan, the following section examines the traditional campaigning strategies of major political parties. Understanding these established approaches to electoral mobilisation provides an essential foundation for analysing how parties have adapted and extended these strategies into the digital sphere, particularly through the strategic use of social media for political communication.

1.5 Political campaigning in Pakistan

Provincial and national-level General Elections are held under the Election Commission of Pakistan, an autonomous institution. Pakistan is a multiparty democracy, but three parties dominate in terms of public popularity and show strength in the General Elections to form the government in the centre. The parties include traditional parties PMLN, PPP, and a comparatively new party, PTI. Research conducted on the determinants of successful political campaigns in Pakistan, in which recruits of the research were members of the aforementioned political parties, revealed that political parties in Pakistan do not consider the party manifesto as an essential component to run their political campaigns. The popularity of the contesting candidate and the political party in the constituency were viewed as more important, according to the study's respondents (Usman, Munawar and Amjad, 2013). The popularity of the leadership was another factor considered important by respondents for a successful election turnout. One of the respondents is quoted as saying that:

In general elections, the main role is of leadership. If a candidate is 50% voted for his personality, then 50%-60% of votes for him will be due to party leadership (p., 112).

The research findings also suggest that political parties consider voter choices and frame their party campaign slogans according to public sentiments. Social factors also play a significant role in shaping political campaigns, particularly through the influence of political caste affiliations, the *biradari* (kinship-based) system, and ethnic loyalties. Media propaganda also

plays a vital role, and in some cases, it is considered more important than political factors. The majority of respondents of the research conducted by Usman, Munawar and Amjad (2013) considered money an important factor for running political campaigns, highlighting the need for funds to conduct rallies and hire party workers. Research also suggests that respondents agreed that the malpractices of maligning individuals from other political parties through the media are an important part of political campaigns in Pakistan.

Yousaf (2016) has noted that PPP secured sympathy votes in the 2008 elections after the assassination of former Prime Minister Benazir Bhutto in December 2007 and gained control of the government. He also suggests that political parties spend a large amount of money on banners and stickers displayed in the streets with huge images of their leaders and slogans inscribed. Also, it is common among all political parties to name public utility infrastructures built from taxpayers' money after party chairpersons. This serves as a reminder of their services to the people of Pakistan in the next election campaign. Yousaf also notes that political parties give a significant amount of advertisement money to media channels when they are in government to run their media campaigns and set a narrative in their favour.

However, in addition to the traditional campaigning strategies, political parties in Pakistan are also adopting new trends. A growing body of scholarship now focuses on the utilisation of social media by political parties in Pakistan. This introductory chapter now turns to the relationship between media and politics in Pakistan.

1.6 The media and politics nexus in Pakistan

The relationship between media and politics in Pakistan has evolved through distinct phases shaped by political regimes, technological advancements, and institutional constraints. While Article 19A of the Constitution guarantees freedom of speech and access to information, for decades after independence in 1947 the media landscape was dominated by state-owned

outlets, including print newspapers and a single radio station. Television, introduced in 1964, operated under tight state control, with Pakistan Television Corporation (PTV) primarily broadcasting the activities of ruling party politicians.

A significant shift occurred in 2002 when the Pakistan Electronic Media Regulatory Authority (PEMRA), under President Pervez Musharraf, liberalised the broadcast sector, triggering an unprecedented growth in private television channels (Hussain, 2012). By 2008, over 70 channels were operating, focusing heavily on terrorism, political scandals, and social crises such as honour killings (Paracha *et al.*, 2013). As war and terrorism reporting declined, political talk shows filled the gap, creating what Pintak, Bowe and Nazir (2018) describe as a savage freedom, marked by intense political debate and polarisation. These developments entrenched the integration of political parties and media, where commercially driven news outlets increasingly served elite political interests (Pintak, Bowe and Nazir, 2018), echoing Herman and Chomsky (2010) analysis of how traditional media protects the agendas of powerful groups.

However, the rise of the internet and social media introduced new spaces for political communication, challenging the agenda-setting monopoly of traditional media (Kathurwar, 2017). Globally, social media has reshaped campaigning strategies, from former US president Barack Obama's 2008 Twitter-driven mobilisation and former President of United States Donald Trump's Twitter strategy as highlighted by Akram, Imran and ul Hassan (2025) to microtargeting in the UK's 2015 General Election highlighted by Wring and Ward (2015), illustrating how digital platforms alter the power dynamics of communication by enabling unmediated outreach and precise audience targeting.

In Pakistan, social media adoption has accelerated despite structural inequalities and digital divides (Keniston and Kumar, 2004). Internet penetration rose from just 6.3 per cent of the

population in 2005 to 36.5 per cent by 2022 (Kemp, 2021), aided by widespread mobile data access. Social media users increased by nine million in a single year, reaching 31.5 per cent of the population in early 2022 (Kemp, 2021). This growing digital presence has prompted successive governments and political parties to institutionalise social media operations through digital media wings and strategic communication cells within the Ministry of Information and Broadcasting (Gishkori, 2021; Paracha, 2017), which function to project party narratives, counter opponents' messaging, and maintain online influence.

Research shows that Twitter is an elite-driven, agenda-setting platform, where political leaders and journalists strategically shape narratives that are later amplified by mainstream media (Jungherr 2016; Parmelee and Bichard 2011). Bruns and Highfield (2015) describe Twitter as a form of networked gatekeeping where influential users, rather than traditional newsrooms, determine which issues gain salience. Chadwick (2017) similarly argues that in hybrid media systems, Twitter serves as a bridge between digital and traditional spheres, enabling political actors to bypass conventional gatekeepers while still influencing news agendas.

There is evidence that this elite-centric dynamic is evident in Pakistan. Political leaders regularly engage audiences through Twitter Spaces, such as Imran Khan's record-breaking April 2022 broadcast, which drew 165,000 live listeners (Tribune, 2022). The growing followership of key politicians illustrates the platform's unique influence: as of October 2025, former Prime Minister Imran Khan currently has over 20.5 million followers, PMLN leader Maryam Nawaz Sharif approximately 8.1 million, and PPP leader Bilawal Bhutto Zardari around 4.4 million (author's compilation from publicly available X profiles, October 2025). These large and active follower networks demonstrate the potential of Twitter for rapid message dissemination, direct outreach, and agenda control. Beyond political leaders, journalists, influencers, and mainstream media organisations actively participate on Twitter, further entangling digital and traditional spheres in shaping political discourse.

Although Twitter has a smaller user base than Facebook or WhatsApp in Pakistan, it holds disproportionate influence because it is the platform of choice for opinion leaders, journalists, and political elites who shape public debate and influence mainstream news agendas (Jungherr, 2016). Its affordances like hashtags, trending topics, and live interactions facilitate the rapid amplification of frames, many of which are embedded in Pakistan's historical patterns of elite dominance, political polarisation, and populist rhetoric (Pintak, Bowe and Nazir, 2018).

For these reasons, this study focuses on Twitter as a strategic arena where political parties construct frames, and where mainstream journalists amplify and adapt those frames. By analysing these interactions, the research explores how digital platforms are reshaping political communication in Pakistan's hybrid media environment, addressing a gap in understanding framing practices within fragile democracies. Having established the historical evolution of the media and politics nexus in Pakistan and the unique role Twitter plays within this hybrid media system; the next section outlines the research aims and objectives that guide this study.

1.7 Study Aim and Objectives

This research aims to explore the way Twitter as a strategic tool is shaping political communication in Pakistan. The following objectives are designed to achieve the aim of the study:

- To critically analyse Twitter usage by prominent political parties in Pakistan as a strategic campaigning tool.
- To critically analyse the role of mainstream news media on Twitter in spreading messages of political parties to target potential voters.
- To examine how Twitter restructures political discourse and contributes to the formation of a digitally mediated public sphere in Pakistan.

To achieve these objectives, this study adopts an integrated theoretical framework that combines framing theory with the concept of the public sphere. Framing theory provides a lens to analyse how political parties construct frames to legitimise their positions, while the public sphere perspective helps to understand how these frames circulate and gain salience within the digital sphere, where journalists, elites, and citizens interact. For this study, the public sphere is understood as a communicative space in which issues of collective concern are articulated, circulated, and contested through media, rather than as an idealised arena of rational deliberation. Drawing from Habermas's original formulation (1962), the public sphere refers to arenas where participation is, in principle, open and public discussion enables the formation of political opinion; however, this study adopts an analytical rather than normative understanding of the concept. However, in Pakistan's fragile democracy marked by elite-dominated politics, media polarisation, and historical constraints on free expression these processes are more complex than in established democracies. By examining the interplay between framing and the digital public sphere in this context, the study fosters a nuanced understanding of how political communication is shaped and disseminated within Pakistan's hybrid media system. The study investigates how online political communication intersects with offline political culture in a fragile democracy characterised by elite dominance, media polarisation, and historical constraints on deliberation. In this thesis, Twitter² (now X) is understood as a microblogging social media platform that enables users to create public profiles, publish short textual messages, and engage in real-time information exchange through features such as reposting, replying, and hashtagging. These affordances the action possibilities that a communication technology or platform enables or constrains for its users (Gibson and Ward, 2009) facilitate rapid dissemination of information, visibility of political actors, and

² Term "Twitter" is used throughout this study for the consistency because of its use in literary sources consulted for study and the participants of the study.

networked public interaction. In this thesis, the concept of strategic communication refers to the deliberate, goal-oriented use of communication to influence public opinion, frame narratives, and mobilise support, particularly during electoral campaigns (Hallahan et al., 2007; Cornelissen, 2017; Entman, 2004). It differs from everyday communication in its intentionality, structured planning, and alignment with political objectives (Hallahan *et al.*, 2007). In the context of this study, strategic communication by political parties is identified through evidence of coordinated messaging, targeted framing, and efforts to gain media amplification or public traction. This definition sets the boundaries of the research: the study does not analyse all forms of political talk on social media but focuses specifically on patterns of communication initiated or amplified by political actors as part of their broader political strategy. The concept of “hybridity” is used in a precise and limited sense in this work to refer to a hybrid media environment in which political communication is produced and circulated through interaction between social media platforms and mainstream news media, rather than through either sphere operating independently. The thesis therefore uses “hybrid media system” to describe cross-media flows, where platforms such as Twitter shape visibility and agenda cues, while mainstream media remains central in amplification and reach.

1.8 Contribution of the Study

This thesis advances knowledge in three key ways. First, it contributes to scholarship on the Global South by examining how the digital public sphere operates within a fragile democratic context, demonstrating how political communication is shaped by elite-driven dynamics and cross-media interaction rather than inclusive deliberation. Second, it extends framing theory by embedding it within the Pakistani context, showing how frames are not only constructed by political actors but are amplified and reshaped through contextual factors such as platform visibility, media practices, and political polarisation. Third, the thesis contributes to understanding platform journalism by drawing on insights from both senior political decision-

makers and social media managers, as well as journalists, to explain how political narratives are strategically disseminated and amplified within a hybrid media environment.. This research makes both theoretical and empirical contributions to the field of media and political communication. Theoretically, it extends debates on the digital public sphere and framing theory by showing how these frameworks operate together in a fragile democracy, where elite dominance, media polarisation, and platform logics intersect. By analysing how frames are constructed and propagated on Twitter, the study highlights how political communication in Pakistan reflects, but also differs from, patterns observed in established democracies.

Empirically, this study offers an in-depth examination of Twitter's role in shaping political discourse within Pakistan's hybrid media system, with a focus on the interactions among political parties, journalists, and social media teams. Through interviews with political elites and senior journalists, it reveals how Twitter has become a strategic tool not only for direct voter outreach but also for influencing mainstream news agendas. This research, therefore, advances understanding of how social media transforms political campaigning and political journalism in contexts marked by historical constraints on the public sphere.

In doing so, the study offers a nuanced perspective on how digital platforms mediate political communication in fragile democracies, providing insights that transcend Western-centric analyses and highlighting the complex interplay between online framing, media logics, and offline political culture.

1.9 Structure of thesis

The thesis is divided into two parts, comprising a total of nine chapters. In the first part, the **first chapter** introduces the work, its aims and objectives, contribution and structure. **Chapter 2** explores the relevant literature about the evolution of political communication in modern democracies. It traces the changes in dependencies of politicians on broadcast media to social

media, how social media has played a role and how it is being used as a strategic tool by the political parties in the developed democracies, weaker democracies and autocratic regimes (western and non-western) like US, UK, Italy, Australia and Germany, India, Nigeria and Iran. It considers what role social media has played during election campaigns. It also includes the role of social media in autocratic regimes. It also brings forward the concept of bots and how they work. The chapter also highlights the link between social media and democracy in different countries. The chapter establishes the role of social media, particularly Twitter, in contemporary politics and political communication. It also highlights the opportunities and challenges brought forward by social media for journalism and mainstream media. **Chapter 3** highlights the evolution of media and political communication in Pakistan and the phases of this evolution. It reviews previous research on the social media platform Twitter as an increasingly prominent form of political communication and identifies the gap from which the main research questions are drawn. **Chapter 4** provides a detailed elaboration of the theoretical framework underlying the study. To address the research questions, this study adopts the lens of framing theory and its application to social media. It outlines the theoretical framework that provides a foundation for framing and disseminating political messages in the broader public sphere through the strategic use of mainstream media and the digital sphere. The concept of the digital and public sphere is also elaborated to address the dissemination of political messages as part of the strategy for political campaigns. Guided by the theoretical framework **Chapter 5** outlines the research methodology adopted to address the research questions. The chapter highlights how previous research on Twitter has employed various research methodologies and provides details of the research design used in this study.

In the second part of the thesis, the findings chapters are structured to reflect this analytical focus. The first findings chapter (**Chapter 6**) begins by identifying the actors who dominate the digital political sphere in Pakistan, establishing the elite nature of participation. It then

explores the organisational structures and internal coordination of political parties' social media teams, revealing the mechanisms through which strategic content is constructed. It presents the first two themes identified after thematic coding analysis of the collected data. It establishes the elite digital sphere and its strategic use by the political parties in Pakistan, including how they frame their messages for political campaigns, focusing on language use, propaganda, disinformation, and engagement with public and national issues. This chapter draws on data generated from interviews with the prominent politicians of selected political parties, media managers of the selected political parties and the prominent senior journalists in Pakistan working for national and international media. Twitter data for selected events is also utilised to complement the research findings. The second findings chapter (**Chapter 7**) shifts focus to the role of mainstream journalists and media in amplifying political content. It first establishes that Twitter is widely used as a primary source of political news and then explores how media actors amplify specific political narratives, often reflecting partisan biases. This structure supports the study's investigation of how political messages are strategically framed and how salience is achieved through interactions between political actors, media professionals, and platform dynamics. It provides findings focused on journalists and the mainstream media's role in the salience of political party messages, exploring how they generate their frames. It also explores the role of mainstream media and journalists in shaping political communication within an environment defined by challenges and threats from the strategic use of social media. This chapter draws primarily on interviews with senior journalists who have worked as political journalists in all developmental phases of the media in Pakistan, alongside data drawn from interviews with media managers and politicians of the selected political parties. **Chapter 8** is a discussion chapter of how this whole activity of political parties, mainstream media and journalists is shaping political communication in Pakistan. **Chapter 9** concludes the study and presents recommendations for future research.

1.10 Conclusion

In summary, this chapter has introduced the political and media landscape of Pakistan, explained the rationale for focusing on Twitter as an elite-driven platform, identified the research gap, and outlined the aims, objectives, and theoretical framework guiding the study. This foundation highlights the need to examine how Twitter shapes political communication in Pakistan's hybrid media environment. The next chapter builds on this groundwork by reviewing the relevant literature on political communication, framing, and the evolution of journalism practices in the digital age.

Chapter 2: Political Communication from Old to New Media

2.1 Introduction

Throughout history, politics has continuously adopted channels of communication to reach and influence potential voters. Experts like Larrondo-Ureta and Meso-Ayerdi (2022) and Shah et al. (2015) believe that through the course of its adaptation, politics has been influenced by channels of communication, whether print, electronic or digital media. Politics and political communication are two different fields, but politics always needs a mediating channel (Larrondo-Ureta and Meso-Ayerdi, 2022). This chapter focuses on the evolution of political communication and discusses the changing role of key actors in the shift from old to new media. It reviews the international literature on political communication, with particular emphasis on how the field has been reshaped by technological and social change. The chapter begins by outlining foundational definitions and the central actors in political communication, including political parties, media institutions, journalists, and citizens. The chapter then traces how shifts from traditional mass media to digital and platform-based systems have altered the structure, reach, and rhythm of political discourse. Special attention is given to the growing significance of Twitter in political campaigns and media reporting, and how politicians and journalists have used the platform to shape narratives, gain visibility, and influence agenda-setting processes.

In doing so, this chapter highlights recurring themes in the global literature, such as the erosion of gatekeeping roles, the emergence of strategic communication practices tailored to platform logics, and the challenges posed by disinformation, polarisation, and weakened editorial oversight. These dynamics form the broader conceptual and empirical backdrop against which political communication must now be analysed.

2.2 Defining political communication

Historically, political communication can be traced back to the works of Aristotle and Plato (Kaid, 2004) but the contemporary field has its roots in other domains like journalism, psychology, politics, communication, history, technology and rhetoric in the 20th century. Chafee (1975) defines political communication as the “role of communication in politics” (p. 15). Nimmo (1981) suggests that political communication is a process in which political institutions and the public interact with each other. The influential political communication scholar, McNair, defines political communication as all forms of communication by politicians and political actors used to achieve specific objectives. Communication directed at these individuals by the audience, as well as reporting on political figures in news and editorials, collectively constitutes political communication (McNair, 2017). In his definition, McNair includes political actors, the media and the public as the main actors. For him, political actors include political parties, public organisations, pressure groups and the individuals who work as influencers to help achieve political objectives. McNair believes that all political communication is intended to influence audiences. Audiences can range from government officials and political parties to the public. Media, the third element of McNair’s political communication definition, includes print, electronic and social media. While the focus of this study is social media, it is important to first highlight the inseparability of the historical relationship between political communication and older, or legacy, forms of media broadcast and print.

2.3 Evolution of political communication: legacy media

Discussion about the importance of media for politics is not new, as it has been a focus of media and politics students for decades. For example, Scupham (1967) argued that radio and television transformed the concept of political controversy into political argument. Later

studies, such as Blumler and McQuail (1969)'s analysis of political television during election campaigns, showed that broadcast media became a central source of political information for the electorate, contributing to issue salience and voter decision-making. These foundational studies established the groundwork for understanding how mediated communication plays a central role in shaping political knowledge and attitudes. Kaid (2004) has also highlighted that the evolution of media has always had an impact on the political campaign strategies of political parties. She also highlights that television had a greater ability to dramatise campaigns and television journalists had a more powerful impact on political campaigns because of their on-screen appearances. Kaid argues that politicians' soundbites were used in the news discussions in which journalists would talk about the backstage political manoeuvrings of the political candidates. Schill (2012), considering the importance of visual image in the electronic media, suggests that visual symbols have long been a central component of political communication, and their importance increased as the visual medium of television became the dominant source of political information. He argues that politicians understand the significance of visuals and work equally hard to construct effective image bites as they do powerful sound bites. The significance of visuals in shaping political perceptions was famously illustrated in the Kennedy- Nixon presidential debates of 1960, where radio listeners considered Nixon to have performed better, while television viewers favoured Kennedy, largely due to his confident appearance and composure on screen (Kraus, 1988). This case marked a turning point in demonstrating how visual presence could outweigh verbal arguments in political campaigns. Schill (2012) therefore contends that what the American people 'see' is often more influential than what presidents 'say' in their speeches. If a sixty-second clip can convey the crux of the argument, then the audience will be more interested in that. It suggests that the evolution of media from print to electronic and from radio to television has had a powerful impact on political campaigning. However, Schill argues that while the 'legacy' media still plays an

essential role in political communication, technological developments have opened new tools and tactics. In the next section, I discuss the role of social media in political communication across different political systems, internationally.

2.4 Political communication and social media

Social media has significantly reshaped the traditional relationship between media, politics, and the public by enabling political actors to bypass journalistic gatekeepers and speak directly to their audiences. Unlike in the broadcast era where political communication was filtered through institutional journalism; platforms like Twitter facilitate real-time, unmediated messaging by politicians and parties (Enli, 2017; Kreiss, 2018). Larrondo-Ureta and Meso-Ayerdi (2022) describe this as a “regime change” in political communication, reflecting broader transformations in how authority and influence are distributed across the media ecosystem. This shift not only empowers political actors but also reconfigures the role of mainstream media. As Chadwick (2017) and Hermida (2012) argue, news organisations increasingly rely on social media for breaking news, quotes, and framing cues, often repackaging tweets and trends as news content. In this way, media organisations act both as curators and amplifiers of digital discourse, often blurring the line between journalism and networked communication. Rather than enhancing media power in the traditional sense, social media has dispersed it, placing journalists, politicians, influencers, and platforms in a competitive and entangled communicative space (Poell, 2013). Since its emergence, social media has facilitated a bidirectional model of political communication, transforming both political leaders and citizens into active communicative agents. Rather than depending on traditional media to mediate their messages, political parties now use social media platforms to engage audiences directly through text, visuals, audio, and livestreams (Stromer-Galley, 2019). These platforms not only serve as tools for political messaging but also connect online and offline mobilisation, linking digital campaigns with street-level activism (Harfoush, 2009).

Political communication in the digital era is increasingly data-driven and strategic, with campaign teams carefully mapping the architecture of online networks, identifying key influencers, and orchestrating the spread of political messages (Forelle *et al.*, 2015). In this context, language and symbolism are not incidental but deliberately constructed to maximise resonance and virality. Scholars such as Zappavigna (2012) and Burton, Miller and Shea (2015) have demonstrated that political language on social media is often strategically framed to elicit emotional responses, signal group identity, and stimulate user engagement. These evolving practices underscore a shift in the logic of political communication from top-down message delivery to an interactive and algorithmically shaped contest over visibility and influence

Macnamara and Kenning (2014) have explored how social media is used for political communication in the US, UK, Australia, Sweden, and Taiwan. Their research highlights that even though voting is compulsory in Australia and there is no need to mobilise voters through the media, political parties are now following international trends related to social media campaigns. Gurevitch, Coleman and Blumler (2009) have studied the relationship between old and new media with political communication and suggest that the new media ecology has brought consequences for governments, mainstream media, political parties, and political journalists because of emerging citizen journalism on social media. They suggest that,

Producers of political coverage on television, from news broadcasts to election campaign reports and issue analyses, are under intense pressure to compete for the attention of the fragmented audience (p. 172).

Political use of the internet and social media has attracted the attention of academics keen to study its use by political parties for intraparty communication, to compete with other political parties and to exploit it as a tool to reach potential voters, according to Gibson and Ward (2009).

Their research investigated whether social media has had any effect on the dependency of political communication on mainstream media. They also analysed if there were any new dependencies arising due to the emergence and growth of social media. A study conducted by D’heer and Verdegem (2014) identified five ways in which social media can shape or be shaped by politicians. Firstly, D’heer and Verdegem (2014), like Parmelee and Bichard (2011), argue that politicians use the social media platform, Twitter, for political campaigns due to the presence of political journalists there. By doing so, they intend to increase their public reach through mainstream journalists. Secondly, mainstream media journalists use Twitter information for awareness. Topics and messages that go viral on Twitter or become trends, catching the attention of journalists, are then used by various media outlets from different angles. For instance, Graham, Jackson and Broersma (2016) found that British newspapers are more likely to feature negative tweets (tweets that attack other politicians) by politicians more often in their news headlines. Additionally, tweets from prominent politicians tend to attract journalists more. The third aspect of social media and political communication interaction outlined in the research is that every Tweet or message contains an economic value for the network companies. Social media companies, therefore, give more importance to tweets from individuals with more followers or topics having the potential to get more “likes”. In this sense, politicians’ expertise should be complemented with knowledge of how social media platforms, as economic entities, prioritise content (Verdegem and D’heer, 2018). Fourthly, unlike mainstream media, message content is not only produced and shaped by politicians and the media. Instead, non-elite citizens also get involved in it. Politicians post their messages on social media but are seldom involved in dialogue with citizens. Lastly, it is also highlighted that, unlike mainstream media, social media has a smaller audience. The study suggests that politicians target social media platforms to convey their messages to the masses through political journalists who are part of mainstream media.

Studies from the United States have documented that politicians' use of social media is correlated with their competitive position: challengers were more likely to be early adopters of social media, while incumbents adopted more slowly but steadily (Enli, 2017). Zhuravskaya, Petrova and Enikolopov (2020) argue that social media affects politics for two essential reasons. Firstly, social media provides low barriers to entry for politicians and political workers. Secondly, the information provided by politicians is less effective because of the presence of other actors, including the public to add information. However, social media has certainly provided access to content generation to those who the mainstream political establishment previously sidelined. Social media has helped to amplify protests against economic, political and social crises the world over. There are prominent examples of protests from autocratic countries, including Arab Spring, Iran, and Russia (Zhuravskaya, Petrova and Enikolopov, 2020). Zhuravskaya et al explore how autocratic regimes utilise social media for propaganda. (Diamond, 2015) also terms social media as a 'liberation technology' based on its use in political campaigns against autocratic regimes. This can create a challenge for existing political actors and make them vulnerable too (Edmond, 2013). Social media also gives a platform to previously marginalised groups, not only to the legitimate opposition. As WL Bennett (2012, p. 739) suggests:

From the Arab Spring and Los indignados in Spain to Occupy Wall Street (and beyond), large-scale, sustained protests are utilising digital media in ways that extend beyond sending and receiving messages.

Social media use by politicians and the emergence of Twitter, Facebook and other social media platforms as part of the public sphere for political discourse has raised new questions for how political communication can be studied (Pal, 2017). There are many interpretations of what makes a politician's message appealing. Politicians benefit from having direct access to communication channels without mediation by the mainstream media, and when such

messages find wider purchase, they offer a powerful form of endorsement. Pal (2017) is of the view that the growing reliance on social media for political outreach has led to the increasing personalisation of politics. The online behaviour of politicians like Donald Trump shows that it is not just the reverberation of individual messages through an online space, but the very composition of political communication, that needs careful study. These messages say something about both the politician communicating and the citizenry reacting to it. Through examples from Donald Trump's tweets, Pal (2017) explains how political messages are intentionally and strategically crafted to target specific audiences. The shift from public speeches or televised appearances to social media does not alter the fundamental nature of political outreach (Graham, Jackson and Broersma, 2016). Messages on social media serve as a means of telling a story as well as a means of reinforcing a candidate's credibility (Page and Duffy, 2018). White (2014) has discussed the same dimension of social media's impact on politics. He is of the view that social media platforms have provided a source of information, but that information is also filtered and crafted to inform and influence others. As Habermas (2006) also argued, the internet and social media platforms focus the attention of the anonymous public on some specific information, which is crafted and filtered for the public as it is provided to journalists, suggesting that the information reaching the general public is still narrow and framed to fit a message.

This section has highlighted the increasing dependence of political actors on social media platforms for strategic political communication. Politicians are not only using these platforms to bypass traditional gatekeepers and reach audiences directly, but are also carefully crafting their messages to maximise resonance, visibility, and emotional impact. These practices reflect the growing importance of *framing* in digital political communication. As Entman (1993) explains, framing involves the selection and emphasis of particular aspects of a perceived reality to promote a specific interpretation or agenda. Social media, while often celebrated for

enhancing access to political discourse, raises critical questions about whether it genuinely fosters democratic deliberation or simply reinforces pre-framed and polarised narratives. The next section explores how these dynamics intersect with debates around democratisation and political participation.

2.5 Social media and democratisation

Social media has transformed political communication from a one-way broadcast monologue into a more participatory dialogue (Patrut and Patrut, 2014). One of its most widely debated contributions is its potential to support democratisation by enabling users to act not only as consumers but also as producers of political content. However, this democratic potential is uneven and context-dependent. Calderaro (2014), in a cross-national study of 190 countries, found that the presence of political parties on social media varies significantly, with liberal democracies showing stronger online engagement. He argues that structural and contextual factors such as the strength of democratic institutions and media freedom largely determine the capacity of social media to act as a democratising force. These findings challenge universal claims about the empowering nature of digital platforms, particularly in fragile democracies. While organisations such as UNESCO affirm that a healthy and pluralistic media environment is vital to sustaining democracy (UNESCO, 2005), scholars have increasingly questioned whether contemporary media systems, especially in the digital age, are equipped to uphold this responsibility. In this context, it becomes crucial to assess not only access to platforms but also the quality and function of political discourse they enable.

Jha and Kodila-Tedika (2020) conducted a study on the relationship between democracy and social media across 125 countries. Their findings suggest that the relationship is stronger in lower-income countries compared to higher-income ones. However, they also argue that the internet and technology-based platforms like social media cannot independently determine the

democratic nature of a country, as other structural and contextual factors play a more defining role. In a similar vein, Poell (2013) contends that social media platforms such as Facebook, YouTube, and Twitter have become deeply embedded in the mechanics of everyday life, influencing informal interactions, institutional structures, and professional routines. While acknowledging a level of neutrality in how these platforms operate, his analysis of social media logic draws attention to how algorithmic design, virality, and engagement metrics shape communication patterns and restructure power relationships in digital public discourse. Poell highlights that these platforms have significantly influenced processes of mobilisation by enabling fast-paced message amplification and reshaping the norms of conventional media logic.

Supporting this, Tufekci (2017) argues that social media enables a new form of participatory politics by allowing individuals to bypass traditional gatekeepers and directly shape public narratives. While it has created opportunities for political participation, mobilisation, and feedback, there remains ongoing debate about whether it genuinely fosters democratic deliberation. Social media's affordances such as speed, reach, and two-way communication enable politicians and policymakers to interact more directly with the public, making it possible to receive feedback and, in some cases, adjust decisions accordingly. This transformation raises the question of whether such interactions promote meaningful democratic dialogue or merely performative engagement. At the same time, the rise of increasingly autocratic regimes around the world demonstrates that these affordances are not always liberating; in many cases, social media is restricted, manipulated, or used as a tool of surveillance and control, limiting its potential to foster open political debate (Fuchs, 2014; Tufekci, 2017). For instance, Wyatt, Katz and Kim (2000) studied political conversation in informal offline spaces such as homes, workplaces, and civic organisations, finding that such discussions play a vital role in strengthening democratic systems. They argue that individuals felt free to engage in political

and personal discussions, and these everyday conversations helped sustain a functioning democracy. Their work becomes even more relevant in the digital era, where social media platforms have expanded and redefined these informal public spheres. Online platforms have become new sites for political talk, activism, and mobilisation, but they are also marked by unequal access, manipulation, and polarisation. Taken together, these studies suggest that social media holds the potential to contribute positively to democratic processes by increasing interaction, participation, and access to information. However, its role is shaped by pre-existing political structures, platform logics, and the ways in which political actors choose to use these tools. While platforms may provide new spaces for discourse, they also replicate existing power dynamics, often privileging dominant voices and failing to guarantee inclusive deliberation.

However, many still question social media's efficacy as a democratising process. Research by Zhuravskaya, Petrova, and Nikolopov (2020) about the impact of social media on politics reveals that politicians from the extreme left and extreme right have benefited more from social media than the general public. This raises concerns about the type of content that thrives in algorithm-driven environments and whether this enhances or undermines deliberative engagement. A study by Chan, Chen and Lee (2017) examining university students in Taiwan, Hong Kong, and China, revealed that social media has become the primary source of political news among young people, with a significant correlation between media use and political discussion. Their findings suggest that frequent exposure to political content online encourages increased participation in political conversations and online civic engagement.

These findings align with broader trends identified by the Reuters Institute Digital News Report 2022, which indicates that individuals under 30 are increasingly reliant on social media platforms for news consumption (Reuters Institute, 2022). The report, covering forty-six countries across the America, Africa, Europe, and the Asia-Pacific, highlights a generational shift in news habits that challenges traditional journalism. Notably, the 2025 edition of the

Reuters report finds that Twitter usage has remained stable or increased in many countries, reinforcing its continued relevance as a political communication platform (Reuters Institute, 2025).

Extending this analysis, Vissers and Stolle (2014) identify a spillover effect between online and offline political engagement, particularly among younger users. Their study argues that online discussions not only increase political awareness but also build the confidence and motivation necessary for offline participation. Taken together, these studies suggest that while social media may not universally democratise political participation, it does offer affordances that encourage youth engagement, particularly in hybrid media systems where mainstream media may not fully represent younger or marginalised voices.

Effing, van Hillegersberg and Huibers (2011) argue that participation is the key distinction between the early internet and modern social media platforms. In their study of social media's impact on elections in the Netherlands, they found that politicians who effectively managed their social media presence and deployed tailored messaging strategies secured more votes. However, many political actors were still learning to use these platforms strategically. This underlines the importance of not just digital presence, but message framing and engagement tactics in political campaigning.

A compelling example of this shift is the Momentum movement within the UK Labour Party under Jeremy Corbyn's leadership. Rather than relying solely on traditional top-down messaging, the campaign empowered activists to interact with voters and frame campaign narratives organically. These supporters played a central role in shaping the Labour Party's discourse on platforms like Facebook and Twitter, fostering a participatory digital environment that aligned closely with Corbyn's political brand (Rhodes, 2019). Walsh (2017) described the 2017 British General Election as the "Facebook election," noting that Corbyn's personal page

attracted significantly more engagement than the official Labour Party account, reflecting the affordances of social media for personalised, resonant political framing.

This strategic use of social media illustrates what Entman (1993) calls framing: the selection and salience of specific aspects of a message to promote a particular interpretation. Activists and political communicators on digital platforms engage in constant frame-building to mobilise support, set agendas, and influence voter perceptions. Moreover, as these interactions occur in a networked digital space, they resemble what Papacharissi (2020) term the networked or digital public sphere a space where dialogue between citizens, political elites, and institutions unfolds in real time. Verdegem and D'heer (2018) argue that these socio-technological shifts have reshaped the logic of political campaigning, as politicians integrate social media to align online political activity with offline mobilisation, reinforcing both reach and resonance.

Social media can also be viewed as a space to influence. An exploratory study on the impact of social media influencers on political communication reveals that although they are considered apolitical (non-political actors), their posts related to political issues influence followers (Suuronen *et al.*, 2021). This study reveals that social media posts from influencers play an important role during elections, projecting and marketing brands. Similarly, they also have a role in projecting political parties and political figures. The study was conducted by surveying one hundred Finnish social media influencers to investigate the degree of their involvement in political issues. It suggests that political issues discussed by social media influencers get more attention and gain more popularity. The findings of the study also suggest that social media influencers can shape opinions by giving supporting statements in digital spaces where political topics can have more impact.

The literature discussed so far highlights the use of social media in the developed world. However, as the political systems of developing and underdeveloped countries are different,

the level of education and freedom of information is often restricted, and social media's impact in shaping political communication also varies under fragile political systems. The next section reviews literature regarding social media use for political communication in non-Western states.

2.6 Social media and political communication in non-Western states

To date, this chapter has explored how social media is reshaping political communication, primarily through literature drawn from Western liberal democracies. However, the empirical focus of this thesis is Pakistan a non-Western context characterised by a fragile political system, a distinct media environment, and a rapidly evolving digital sphere in which social media platforms and mainstream news media interact to shape political communication. In such contexts, the dynamics of social media communication diverge significantly from those in consolidated democracies. This section shifts the focus to non-Western countries to explore how cultural, technological, and political variations influence the use of social media in political communication. It also considers how platform-based interaction in these contexts raises questions about participation, influence, and framing in digitally mediated public discourse.

In Sri Lanka, a qualitative study on first-time voters at the University of Colombo revealed that social media peer interactions played a significant role in shaping political attitudes (Chandrasekara and Dharmadasa, 2014). Based on 21 in-depth interviews, the study found that new voters were often directed toward political interests through peer influence on social platforms. Respondents did not always consider the broader implications of their voting choices, suggesting that first-time voters may be susceptible to persuasive digital content. Importantly, high-status peers with direct political affiliations served as opinion leaders, illustrating the growing influence of informal networks in shaping political framing.

Similarly, a cross-national study examining Twitter's predictive utility for elections in Malaysia, India, and Pakistan found that the platform's predictive performance was significantly higher in India and Pakistan than in Malaysia (Jaidka *et al.*, 2019). The researchers used volumetric, sentiment, and social network analysis and found that recency of tweets improved predictive outcomes, while the overall structure of social networks remained relatively stable even during intense political discourse. These findings suggest that in countries like India and Pakistan, Twitter not only serves as a tool for communication but also offers insights into public sentiment and the framing of political events.

A detailed study about the changing face of political communication in Africa by Ndlela and Mano (2020) reveals that political campaigning in much of the continent, which used to be conducted through traditional approaches like rallies, posters, door-to-door canvassing of potential voters and by some paid political advertisements on mass media, has changed with the emergence of social media. Ndlela and Mano highlight that social media was used in disseminating information about the toppling of Sudan president Omar Al Bashir, protests against the Algerian president, Zimbabwe election clashes in 2018, and clashes between civilians and the military in Zimbabwe and Sudan. The research argues that in African countries, efforts to control social media are due to these reasons. It highlights how social media was shut down in Chad, Gabon, Gambia, Congo, Ethiopia, Burundi, Mali and Uganda during elections. However, their research also emphasises the emerging power of social media as an alternative platform, “As governments push back via mass media, which they can easily control, directly or indirectly, social media becomes alternative communication channels or even potential game changers in election campaigning” (Ndlela and Mano, 2020, p., 4).

A comprehensive study by Rodrigues (2020) on India's General Elections of 2018–2019 highlights the extensive use of digital platforms such as WhatsApp (a Meta-owned service), Facebook Live, Twitter, and YouTube by politicians to reach voters. Rodrigues argues that the

strategic use of social media for public mobilisation in India can be traced back to the influence of the Arab Spring and the 2011 anti-corruption movement led by Anna Hazare and Arvind Kejriwal. Their campaign, which called for the inclusion of civil society in formulating a national ombudsman, effectively used social media to mobilise the Indian middle class also the main audience of mainstream media outlets. As a result, the campaign received prominent television coverage, establishing a precedent for future electoral strategies.

During the 2012–2013 elections, the Aam Aadmi Party, emerging from Hazare’s movement, relied heavily on Twitter and YouTube for outreach and succeeded in forming a provincial government. By 2018–2019, these practices had become embedded in mainstream campaign strategy. Although only half of India’s 200 million internet users were active on social media, Rodrigues (2020) notes that the mainstream media’s coverage of social media content itself amplified the role of these platforms in the public discourse. This suggests not a replacement of traditional media, but a hybrid model in which social and mainstream media co-construct political narratives.

Narendra Modi’s 2014 election campaign, which capitalised on social media’s mobilisation potential, inspired other parties to follow suit in 2019. BJP’s IT cell head Amit Malviya is cited stating that the party had a clear understanding of the efficacy of social media as a political tool (Rodrigues, 2020). These developments in India demonstrate how digital platforms like Twitter are deeply embedded in broader communicative ecologies, reflecting an evolving public sphere where digital and broadcast logics converge to frame political discourse and shape voter perception.

Similarly, research on political discussion and protests in Iran highlights the mediating role of social media platforms in facilitating political expression under authoritarian constraints. Rahbarqazi and Baghban (2019) found that during the 2018 protests in Iran, social media

served as a crucial alternative space for information exchange, especially given the longstanding restrictions on mainstream media following the 1990 sanctions. The study notes that the early adoption of platforms like Orkut with Iran becoming its third-largest user base after Brazil and the United States reflects the public's longstanding engagement with online networks to circumvent media censorship.

At the same time, social media is not solely a vehicle for dissent. Kermani and Adham (2021) examined how Iranian conservative elites have actively used digital platforms to promote and reinforce autocratic ideologies. Their research illustrates how social media, far from being inherently democratising, can also be instrumentalised by dominant political actors to sustain hegemonic narratives and resist liberal reform. This dual usage is echoed in other weak democracies and authoritarian regimes across the Global South, including Sri Lanka, Iran, and several African states such as Chad, Gabon, Gambia, Congo, Ethiopia, Burundi, Mali, and Uganda. In these contexts, social media platforms are often simultaneously subject to state restrictions and used as political tools both by opposition movements and by ruling elites. As such, these examples illustrate that while social media can function as liberation technology (Diamond, 2015), its effects are shaped by specific political and institutional contexts. This underscores the need for careful contextual analysis when evaluating the political role of social media outside Western liberal democracies.

2.7 Crafting political messages in the age of social media

While the previous section examined the broader role of social media in non-Western political systems, this section narrows the focus to how political actors strategically craft messages for digital campaigning. Understanding the design and dissemination of these messages is essential for analysing how political communication is framed and circulated within digital spheres. As Schäwel, Frener and Trepte (2021) argue, political parties increasingly engage in behavioural

targeting tailoring messages based on users' demographics, gender, and interests to persuade and mobilise potential voters. Their research also highlights growing concerns about user privacy and the scale of political investment in microtargeted advertising. For example, in the 2016 U.S. Presidential Election, Donald Trump spent \$44 million and Hillary Clinton \$28 million on digital advertising. In Germany, political parties also invested in digital advertising during the 2017 federal election, with spending varying across parties such as Die Linke, the Greens, and the Free Democratic Party (Schäwel, Frener and Trepte, 2021). In the 2019 European election campaign, available data report party-level expenditures on digital advertising, with individual parties spending up to €550,000 on platforms such as Facebook and Google (Hegelich and Serrano, 2019). These examples illustrate the rising centrality of data-driven messaging strategies in contemporary political communication a development this chapter explores in more detail. In addition to microtargeting, research shows that authoritarian regimes such as those in China, Iran, and Russia have also adopted advanced digital strategies employing social media experts and automated accounts, or "bots," to disseminate pro-government narratives (Forelle *et al.*, 2015). The A study conducted by Forelle about Venezuela illustrates how political bots are deployed to manipulate public discourse: fake Twitter accounts, often referred to as "Twitter eggs," were programmed to generate scripted tweets, boost follower counts, create artificial trends, and direct attention toward particular agendas. These bots played a crucial role in amplifying the messages of prominent political figures, thereby shaping online opinion and framing public perception. Moreover, the study revealed that user data is systematically mined and traded across borders for political advantage. Data-mining firms in the U.S., for example, were found maintaining detailed profiles of citizens in Argentina (Forelle *et al.*, 2015). Such findings underscore the growing sophistication of digital campaign tactics globally and raise important questions about authenticity, manipulation, and the ethical implications of algorithmically framed political

communication. As political communication has evolved in the digital age, parties and candidates increasingly rely on computerised strategies to automate and amplify their messages. Larrondo-Ureta and Meso-Ayerdi (2022) describe this phenomenon as “robotic political communication,” wherein big data and algorithmic tools are used to generate and disseminate opinion-based content across platforms (p. 53). One of the earliest and most influential platforms in this shift is Twitter. Research by Fraia and Missaglia (2014) traced the initial diffusion of Twitter among parliamentarians in the UK, US, Denmark, and the Netherlands, showing comparable adoption rates: between 7% and 12% in 2009, rising to 25–30% by 2010. As early as 2011, Twitter saw 140 million tweets daily, a number that skyrocketed to 867 million by 2022 (Teufl and Kraxberger, 2011). Larrondo-Ureta and Meso-Ayerdi (2022) further argue that among social media platforms, Twitter holds a distinct position in political campaigning due to its immediacy, interactivity, and public visibility. This is corroborated by the Reuters Digital News Report (2022), which confirms that Twitter remains the preferred platform for both journalists and politicians in shaping public narratives.

The use of Twitter as a strategic tool for political communication has been the focus of many studies in established democracies, with researchers highlighting its affordances for bypassing traditional media filters, shaping public discourse, and amplifying strategic narratives. Boynton (2014) contends that Twitter has significantly reconfigured the communicative landscape by introducing a new, participatory form of political engagement. Unlike traditional broadcast media, which adheres to a one-way communication model, Twitter fosters what Boynton(2014) terms "co-motion" a dynamic public space where users actively interact with, remix, and recirculate political content. His study of 800 curated Twitter streams reveals how politicians have embraced the platform’s immediacy, authenticity, and openness to communicate directly with constituents, shaping political frames and responses in real-time. Boynton (2014) also

emphasises that Twitter's public-by-default nature allows for greater visibility and traceability of political discourse compared to closed social networks.

However, other empirical work suggests that despite Twitter's dialogic potential, many politicians continue to adopt traditional top-down communication strategies. For instance, Sæbø (2011), analysing 4,000 tweets by 102 Norwegian parliamentarians, categorised their Twitter behaviour into eight communication patterns. The study found that the majority of tweets served informational purposes sharing links, updates, or statements and only a minuscule number involved genuine dialogue with constituents. Most tweets either promoted the politicians' own activities or echoed messages from political allies, while only two tweets in the sample demonstrated interaction with non-elite users. This indicates that while Twitter offers affordances for two-way engagement and deliberative dialogue, political actors often use it in ways that reinforce existing hierarchies and gatekeeping structures, raising critical questions about the realisation of the digital public sphere. From a framing perspective, these studies suggest that Twitter enables political actors to curate their image and control the narrative more tightly than in traditional media contexts. The apparent preference for one-way communication aligns with an instrumental approach to social media, where platforms are used to push messages rather than foster participatory deliberation.

Comparative research conducted on the impact of social media on election outcomes in India, Pakistan, and Malaysia found that most existing literature had focused on liberal democracies, and its applicability to weaker democracies remains questionable (Jaidka *et al.*, 2019). This is an important consideration in contexts like Pakistan, where democratic institutions are fragile, and media systems are entangled with state and political interests. Political communication scholarship increasingly shows that politicians across the globe are investing heavily in online campaigning, with digital strategies becoming central to electoral politics (Pal, 2017). One notable example is the former U.S. President Donald Trump, who employed Twitter to craft

provocative and populist frames using expressive, informal, and emotionally charged language. Pal (2017) argues that such innuendo and metaphoric messaging is a hallmark of political speech online, which makes semantic analysis of social media content complex and nuanced. In this context, qualitative, human-led framing analysis remains a preferred method for interpreting the discursive strategies of political actors.

The strategic use of social media for election campaigning gained momentum during the 2004 U.S. Presidential Election and reached a turning point with Barack Obama's 2008 campaign, widely acknowledged for its pioneering use of digital platforms to mobilise support (Macnamara and Kenning, 2014). In the UK context, Bright *et al.* (2020) studied the 2015 and 2017 General Elections and concluded that Twitter, while effective for message broadcasting and agenda-setting, did not directly translate into votes. However, they noted that when used effectively at the constituency level, Twitter could amplify local campaign visibility and contribute to the party's popularity. Their research underscores the platform's affordance for micro-level political framing, arguing that "Twitter provides a platform for essentially any constituency campaign to become local" (p., 1001). This suggests that Twitter's role may be less about direct vote conversion and more about shaping visibility, public engagement, and frame propagation³ across both national and local levels.

A study of Swiss politicians' Twitter use underscores the importance of contextualising political communication within specific political systems (Rauchfleisch and Metag, 2016). Using innovation diffusion theory, the researchers found that younger, male politicians in urbanised, high-tech environments were the early adopters and more active users of Twitter. Older politicians followed suit only after observing the growing popularity and reach of their

³ Frame propagation refers to the process through which interpretive frames are disseminated, reinforced, and amplified across media platforms and actors Entman, R. M. (1993) 'Framing: Toward clarification of a fractured paradigm', *Journal of communication*, 43(4), pp. 51-58.

younger counterparts. Notably, the study revealed a paradox in party representation: while the Swiss People's Party (SVP) the dominant right-wing party with the largest electoral campaign budget was underrepresented on Twitter, the Social Democratic Party (SP), with the smallest budget among the four major parties, had the strongest Twitter presence. This suggests that social media may serve as a levelling tool for financially weaker parties, allowing them to amplify their visibility through younger, digitally fluent members. However, this finding contrasts with broader literature from other national contexts where parties and governments with greater financial resources dominate digital platforms by hiring influencers, social media consultants, and deploying targeted advertising strategies. The Swiss case thus offers a nuanced perspective on how generational, institutional, and financial factors intersect in shaping political communication on Twitter.

According to Romero, Meeder and Kleinberg (2011), the spread of information on Twitter suggests that the probability of adoption of an idea greatly depends on the quantity of its exposure on the platform. The research indicates that different categories used on Twitter for stickiness⁴ include celebrities, music, and technology. Importantly, the study conceptualises “persistence” as the extent to which repeated exposure to a hashtag continues to generate meaningful additional effects, rather than diminishing rapidly after initial encounters. The study found that hashtags on politically controversial topics are particularly persistent. Having explored the evolution of political communication in digital contexts, particularly how political actors use social media for strategic campaigning, it is now imperative to examine how this transformation intersects with journalistic practice. The following section reviews the literature

⁴ Stickiness refers to the capacity of online content to sustain attention, encourage repeated exposure, and remain visible through user interaction and platform amplification Romero, D. M., Meeder, B. and Kleinberg, J. 'Differences in the mechanics of information diffusion across topics: idioms, political hashtags, and complex contagion on twitter'. *Proceedings of the 20th international conference on World wide web*, 695-704.

on the ethical challenges faced by journalism in the age of social media and its implications for political communication.

2.8 Social media and the challenge to ethical journalism

The preceding discussion has established how political parties, politicians, governments, and elites in different societies and political systems utilise social media platforms for their political campaigns and how this has transformed political communication patterns. While examining the key actors in political communication, many focus on the role of journalists and mainstream media on its contemporary evolution. In this section, I discuss three main challenges that the growth in social media use generates for media organisations and journalists, particularly those operating in political journalism. First, information is shared on social media platforms not only by journalists or media organisations. For instance, the 2005 London Bridge bombing and photos of an aeroplane in the Hudson River posted on Twitter illustrate that the most impactful images and videos have been shared on social media platforms by citizens (Hermida, 2012). However, Hermida emphasises that mainstream media organisations worldwide have eagerly adopted social media, changing how citizens and journalists approach news in the current landscape. The research further underscores that mainstream media use social media for news gathering in situations where journalists arrive late. For instance, Sharma and Sivakumar (2023) argue that social media has become a source for journalists to return to for story ideas, and the race to get more likes and attract public attention on social media platforms has become a discussion point in mainstream media newsrooms. Their research findings, focused on the 2019 General Election in India, reveal that social media was spreading hate speech and misinformation during the election campaign, indicating that fact-checking in the wake of the spread of disinformation on social media has become more relevant for journalists, the second challenge that social media poses for the mainstream media. Existing literature reveals that in traditional mainstream media, existing myths among news users contribute to the acceptance

and belief of disinformation, which is damaging to the media as a democratic institution. For instance, Henkel (2021) noted that disinformative stories about Europe informed British perception for decades; she called those disinformative stories “Euromyths” and has argued that “Euromyths news stories obviously undermined the democratic function of news” (p., 63). Martens *et al.* (2018) noted that disinformation and fake news spreads quickly on digital platforms and Frau-Meigs (2022) found that current beliefs and financial reliance on digital platforms are significant barriers to combating disinformation online. Drawing on international case studies, Culloty and Suiter (2021) concluded that disinformation strengthens the existing bias and prejudice among users. In a situation where disinformation is considered a major challenge, Saldaña and Vu (2022) argue that in the era of fast spreading disinformation due to the availability of digital platforms, journalists have considered social media platforms as an essential component of journalism. Ekström and Westlund (2019) argue for a ‘dislocation of journalism’ due to the advent of social media which has blurred the lines between personal opinions and professional news commentaries by journalists because of the absence of editorial control. The third challenge is the compromising of journalistic ethics on social media. Canter (2015), for instance, highlights the phenomenon of personal branding of journalists on Twitter. Sabedini (2016) considers the language used by some social media journalists unethical and terms it inappropriate and considers it denigrating for ethical journalism. Rogstad (2014) indicates that political journalists are one of the most enthusiastic social media users and highlights the probability of blurring of political news and political commentary by the political journalists on social media platforms like Twitter and Facebook. Rogstad’s research noted that there were five types of political journalists based on their social media interaction and use. The first type is the sparks. These are the journalists who have adapted social media for their personal and professional lives, having an impressive number of followers and connections, and they comment on all political developments. Rogstad found that this commentary is

influenced by popular opinion, and they use dramatic visuals to attract attention, “Some get the role of referees or judges” to give their “verdicts about any political development” (p., 691). The second type is the “self-branding or networkers” who use social media for getting likes and comments, self-branding and connecting with other people. The third type is the ones who prefer to use one digital platform to share all information and gain likes, and refrain from using the other platforms; they are closer to sceptics (the fourth type). Sceptics are low social media users and refrain from giving personal opinions on social media. The fifth category is the opinioners who are not keen on networking but like to give their opinions, and they are popular as well. Apart from the above-discussed types of political journalists, there is discussion in Rostag's work about political commentators. With the advent of political information directly available to the audience due to the presence of political actors on social media, news media and journalists have taken on the added responsibility of commenting on and interpreting this information. However, journalistic interactions and utilisation of digital platforms like Twitter differ across political systems, according to Bruns and Nuernbergk (2019). Their research on a cross-country comparison of Twitter usage by political reporters in Germany and Australia reveals that journalists are now directly exposed to politicians and other audiences more than they were through mainstream media. The research also reveals that the audience engagement in both countries was different, “Australian press corps journalists are substantially more active, and also receive far more engagement from ordinary users in return, their German counterparts have proven considerably more reluctant to incorporate Twitter fully into their professional workflows” (p. 206). Crilley and Gillespie (2019) argue that unregulated social media platforms significantly influence journalism in various detrimental ways. They note that political actors utilise these platforms to disseminate propaganda and misinformation. Furthermore, these environments often perpetuate issues such as sexism, racism, and xenophobia. Most importantly, this landscape contributes to a decline in public trust and

obstructs the media's pursuit of truth. Thus, the unregulated nature of social media poses substantial challenges to the integrity of journalism and the quality of public discourse.

Journalism has historically been defined by professional norms and ethical commitments such as truth-telling, impartiality, verification, and editorial independence, which positioned journalists as trusted gatekeepers of information (Rosenstiel, 2014; Ward, 2011). These principles were reinforced through codes of ethics and newsroom practices that emphasised accuracy, balance, and responsibility to the public. Within this framework, journalists were distinguished from other communicators by their professional training, institutional affiliations, and accountability to established standards. However, the rise of digital media has blurred these boundaries, complicating what it means to be a journalist and raising questions about how traditional ethical commitments can be upheld in an environment where speed, visibility, and audience engagement often drive the news production process. Alongside ethical concerns, evolving news values present another key challenge for journalism in the digital age. Traditionally, news selection has been guided by established criteria such as relevance, timeliness, conflict, and prominence (Galtung and Ruge, 1965; Harcup and O'Neill, 2001; Harcup and O'Neill, 2017). However, these news values have evolved in response to the digital media environment. Harcup and O'Neill (2017) revised and expanded earlier frameworks to include values such as *shareability*, reflecting the growing influence of audience engagement and platform dynamics in contemporary news production. With the rise of social media, newsworthiness is increasingly shaped by platform-specific dynamics, including algorithmic visibility, engagement metrics, and virality (Tandoc Jr, 2014; Van Dalen, 2012). This shift can incentivise the prioritisation of sensational or polarising content, often at the expense of accuracy or public interest journalism. As Carlson (2020) notes, the influence of metrics challenges traditional journalistic norms by blurring the line between editorial judgement and audience preferences. In politically polarised environments, this recalibration of news values

can undermine journalistic independence and gatekeeping, making journalists more vulnerable to framing by political actors and eroding public trust in media (McManus, 1994; Carlson, 2020; Tandoc Jr and Vos, 2016).

2.9 Conclusion

In this chapter, I have reviewed the global literature on social media and political communication, with particular attention to the strategic use of platforms by political actors. The review shows that political parties employ social media to mobilise supporters, defend their positions, and connect online and offline campaigns. Social media has become integral to modern political strategies, often used for propaganda and the careful framing of messages to appeal to fragmented audiences. In many contexts, parties also rely on influencers to amplify their campaigns and extend their reach.

The literature further highlights the dual role of social media: in some cases, such as the Arab Spring⁵, it has enabled collective action and challenged authoritarian regimes, while in others, particularly in Europe, it has contributed to the rise of populism⁶. In South Asia, the case of Narendra Modi demonstrates how populist leaders can strategically harness social media within political cultures that share historical and institutional similarities with Pakistan. A recurring theme across studies is that younger generations rely heavily on social media for political information, reshaping how political communication is produced and consumed.

The review also underscores how the rise of social media has transformed journalism. Scholars highlight the spread of disinformation, the adoption of unethical practices by journalists, and

⁵ The Arab Spring refers to a series of mass protests and political uprisings that emerged across parts of the Middle East and North Africa from 2010 onwards, often associated with the use of social media for mobilisation and information sharing Howard, P. N. and Hussain, M. M. (2013) *Democracy's fourth wave?: digital media and the Arab Spring*. Oxford University Press.

⁶ Populism is understood as a political approach that constructs politics as a struggle between a virtuous "people" and a corrupt "elite", often articulated through emotive and polarising communication Mudde, C. and Kaltwasser, C. R. (2017) *Populism: A very short introduction*. Oxford University Press.

the ways in which journalists increasingly adopt roles as commentators, advocates, or referees rather than neutral reporters. These developments reveal that journalists and media organisations are no longer just mediators of political communication but active participants in shaping political narratives. This perspective is especially important for analysing Pakistan, where mainstream media and journalists remain central actors in political discourse but are simultaneously negotiating the pressures and opportunities of a networked communication environment.

Taken together, these insights provide a foundation for understanding how political actors in Pakistan employ social media and how this intersects with the country's political culture, media system, and journalistic practices. The next chapter builds on this discussion by tracing the evolution of the Pakistani media landscape and examining the role of social media in domestic political communication, setting the stage for the empirical analysis of this study.

Chapter 3: Evolution of Media and Political Communication in Pakistan

3.1 Introduction

This chapter explores the evolution of news media and political communication in Pakistan as Kaid (2004) believes that political attitudes learnt through socialisation during the course of time affect the voting choice and behaviour of individuals. The focus of discussion in this chapter is on the emergence and direction of social media political communication using Twitter in Pakistan. As discussed in the introductory chapter of this thesis, Pakistan, since its inception, has frequently experienced unstable democratic circumstances interrupted by military rule. The news media in Pakistan has similarly experienced change influenced by the political atmosphere in the country. I start by setting out a clear picture of the historical relationship between media and political communication in Pakistan, outlining three main phases from independence (1947) through to the current day, with the influence and importance of social media growing. The chapter reviews literature about the use of social media, particularly Twitter, for political communication in Pakistan. The literature gap is identified towards the conclusion of the chapter, leading to the production of clear guiding research questions for the empirical study.

3.2 The first phase: from independence

The main characteristic of the first phase of media and political communication activity in Pakistan was accompanied by military interventions, martial laws and dictatorial regimes at different intervals. Dictators controlled the media and so did the civilian rulers. For instance, a study conducted about the history of media and politics in Pakistan notes that, “Military rule has lasted for more than around 35 years (Ayub Khan 1958-1969, Yahya Khan 1969-1971, Zia ul Haq 1977-1988, and Pervaiz Musharraf 1999-2008)” (Parveen and Bhatti, 2018, p. 6). Similarly, another study on the liberalisation of media in Pakistan revealed that civilian

governments that followed dictatorial regimes did not change their media policies (Gul, Obaid and Ali, 2017).

Pakistan Television and Radio Pakistan, being state entities, were unable to give coverage to the opposition. For instance, Javed Jabbar, former Senator and Minister for Information, in his address at the Asian Media Summit 2004, revealed that Benazir Bhutto despite being a strong representative of Pakistan People's Party was never covered by state owned media when General Zia Ul Haq was Head of State after imposing martial law in the country 1977 to 1988. After his death in a plane crash, Bhutto became Prime Minister of Pakistan and her government's activities were then fully covered by radio and TV (Parveen and Bhatti, 2018). There was no reporting about social and public issues like health, education, food, climate, and energy. There was no representation of the public on the screens and as noted by Yusuf and Shoemaker (2013), "The story of the Pakistani media was one of intimidation and control. From the start, the state – particularly the military governments used print and subsequently broadcast media to disseminate a unified national position on domestic and foreign policy issues" (p., 6). According to Perveen and Bhatti, "The only gain for electronic media during 1997-1999 was the decision to telecast recorded versions of Question Hours in Parliament on radio and TV" (p., 4). So, until 1999, there was limited media choice for the electronic media audience and newspaper readers, with one-way communication and narrative control by the state. However, this phase was followed by the emergence of a more pluralistic mainstream media which started to represent the voices of those who had previously been kept silent. Private media channels became the eyes and ears of the public. The next section brings forward the evolution and expansion of mainstream media in Pakistan.

3.3 The second phase: media freedom in Pakistan

The second phase is unique because Pakistani media outlets secured more freedom, flourished, and developed under the dictatorial regime of President Pervez Musharraf, starting from 2002. The annual report published by Intermedia 2006-2007 indicated that during the 1999 Kargil War, Pakistanis could only access updates about the conflict from Indian satellite channels because Pakistan's only national TV channel was not providing much coverage. To counter Indian narratives about the Kargil War, Pervez Musharraf gave freedom to the media in the country under PEMRA ordinance 2001. According to Khan and Joseph (2008) "Less than a year after the Kargil conflict, Minister for Information Javed Jabbar explained Pakistan's intentions in liberalising the electronic-media sector as an attempt... counter...Indian propaganda" (p., 33). According to the Pakistan Institute of Developing Economy (PIDE), Pakistan in 2021:

Since 2002, deregulation of the media has resulted in a proliferation of private cable and satellite TV outlets. Today, Pakistan boasts 112 Satellite TV Channels, 4,060 cable operators, and 43 landing TV Channels from abroad, like BBC, CNN, etc. Total TV viewership was 144 million, 70 per cent of which is viewership for entertainment channels (Maqbool, 2022, p., 1).

As the focus of this research is political communication, Table 3.1 lists the ratings of STV news Channels according to PEMRA 2025. However, PEMRA does not publish the actual number of viewers in the list.

Sr. No	Channel Ratings
1	Dunya News
2	Samaa News
3	Geo News
4	ARY News
5	Express News
6	Dawn News
7	Neo News
8	GNN
9	Hum News
10	Aaj News
11	Bol News
12	24 News
13	92 News
14	News One
15	Public News
16	Suno News
17	Aik News
18	Abb Takk
19	Roze News
20	Such News

Table 3.1 Viewership rating of Satellite TV News channels (PEMRA 2025)

Research conducted by Khan and Joseph (2008) explores two crucial aspects of the freedom era in Pakistani media and politics. One is the live coverage of the Lal Masjid incident in Islamabad, which lasted from 3 to 11 July 2007 and dominated news broadcasts for a whole month.

The operation was conducted by security agencies in the capital city of Islamabad against a religious group in a mosque famously called Lal Masjid (meaning Red Mosque). Television channels covered the siege extensively, broadcasting live images of clashes between security forces and armed students, the movement of troops and armoured vehicles, and even interviews with individuals inside the mosque. In some cases, unverified claims about casualties and hostages were aired in real time, raising serious concerns about sensationalism, the security risks of revealing operational details, and the lack of editorial gatekeeping.

This rapid reporting put the state in a difficult position, highlighting the challenges faced by a newly independent media that lacked the training necessary for conflict coverage. Initially, the media's focus was on the unfolding events, but after a week, the narrative began to shift towards

legitimising the military operation. As noted by Khan and Joseph, the situation escalated dramatically when "Musharraf ordered security forces to storm the Lal Masjid on July 3, 2007, and cameras captured it all live" (Khan and Joseph, 2008, p.34).

The Lal Masjid episode was significant because it exposed both the opportunities and risks of liberalised private media in Pakistan. It revealed how competition for live coverage could undermine ethical standards, but also how swiftly media narratives could align with state perspectives in moments of crisis. In the aftermath, the government sought tighter control over news coverage during sensitive events, while media regulators began to call for professional training and clearer codes of conduct. In this sense, Lal Masjid marked an early test of Pakistan's liberalised media environment, illustrating the tensions between freedom, responsibility, and state authority

A second important highlight of the research conducted by Khan and Joseph is the shift in political activity towards media channels. They suggest that the government banned the traditional ways of conducting rallies and processions after the killing of former Prime Minister Bhutto in a suicide attack in Rawalpindi. As a result, political parties turned towards the utilisation of private media channels to promote their political campaigns. Paid advertisements became an important part of campaign policy. This was the time when the link between media and politics developed to a new level. All political parties who were unable to gather people to build their narrative and run political campaigns needed television screens and newspapers to do this for them. Political communication which had previously taken place in corner meetings, rallies and door to door campaigns was now accessible through television screens (Khan and Joseph, 2008).

In the second phase, when media freedom was enabled, the country was experiencing instability in law and order. A qualitative and quantitative content analysis of prime-time media

content of main news channels including Geo News, ARY News, Express News and Dawn News conducted by (Yousaf, Yasmeen and Ali, 2019) concluded that Pakistani news channels used sensationalism to secure higher ratings and to increase viewership. The study also revealed that the news channels were telecasting news related to terrorism and politics. Paracha *et al.* (2013) have also demonstrated that the focus of the media in Pakistan was on the stories linked with politics, terrorism and honour killing, which was creating panic among the public. Michaelsen (2011) highlighted the dilemma of free media in Pakistan and suggested that the political class in Pakistan is mainly composed of wealthy elites and powerful landowners. They have a very significant influence on the media landscape. While television channels are not necessarily owned outright by political parties, proprietors' affiliations with political and economic elites mean that media outlets often reflect elite interests, blurring the boundaries between journalism, business, and politics. Secondly, religious groups that are less representative in Parliament compared to other powerful elites have undue influence in sections of the media. Michaelsen (2011) notes that after the assassination of Punjab governor Salman Taseer in January 2011, some Urdu-language media outlets portrayed his killer, Mumtaz Qadri, as a hero. While these were mainstream commercial television channels rather than explicitly religious broadcasters, their coverage often reflected conservative religious sentiment. This alignment stemmed less from formal ownership by religious groups than from a combination of audience demand, sensationalist programming, and the ideological leanings of journalists and proprietors.

Pintak, Bowe and Nazir (2018) found that in Pakistan, the media became political party integrated and that Pakistani politics was highly polarised and because of its commercial interests, was also serving political elites:

Pakistan's political parties are highly polarised and, in some cases, militarised. Individual media organisations are closely allied with one of the respective camps, a structure known as parallelism (p., 935).

The same research noted that politicians and anchors became heroes and started narrative building. In a survey conducted by media and policy academics, they found that leading media channels working in the country were polarised and often viewed as being supportive of particular political parties. For instance, a study conducted by Sarwar, Umber and Bajwa (2020) about polarised media content and its influence on audiences in Pakistan revealed that Geo News, which was a trend setter after the advent of freedom of media in Pakistan for more than a decade, was boycotted by the ruling Pakistan People's Party in 2010. Geo News reportedly supported the Dunya and Express media groups, whereas some media groups like Dawn owned were neutral. Resultantly, the media was polarised, having three clear positions. The study suggested that there were three visible poles among media organisations including those against PPP (the then ruling party), those in support of PPP and the neutral ones. The research also finds that political parties utilised journalists and media groups to promote their agendas and target potential voters.

Gul, Obaid and Ali (2017) argue that cross-ownership and liberal media policies in Pakistan have undermined democratic values by concentrating news outlets within a few large groups. This concentration reduces diversity in information flow, as channels and newspapers under the same proprietors often reproduce similar content. Moreover, they contend that news content has increasingly been shaped by commercial and political pressures: in some cases, political actors are able to purchase favourable coverage, while in other cases, proprietors' own political and economic interests influence editorial agendas. Hussain (2012) argues that after 2001, although electronic and print news media had moved out of direct government control, they remained shaped by the interests of financiers, senior journalists, and proprietors of media

houses. While explicit ownership by political organisations is less visible, the alignment of media outlets with the political or economic interests of their owners suggests that control over content shifted from state regulation to private influence. He noted that the media had become a force to affect political decision making by generating debate focused on a particular agenda, “it is the financiers, the media houses and the media anchors that make heroes and villains, leaders and terrorists” (p., 54). For that reason, according to Hussain, even government representatives and organisations were dependent on the media to defend their decisions or policies along with the opposition on the other side. However, he also accepts that due to the emergence of a freer media, many social and economic problems were highlighted which would not have happened before media freedom in Pakistan (Hussain, 2012). Bilal *et al.* (2012) highlight in their critical analysis of prime-time political talk shows in Pakistan that the talk shows “unravel critical agendas, incentives, motives and manipulations” (p., 218) when viewed critically. Saeed *et al.* (2021) conducted a survey study among media and communication students in Pakistan to compare the credibility of social media and mainstream media in Pakistan. The research revealed that mainstream media journalists and channels were considered biased by young people, and they preferred social media as more reliable sources of news.

The available literature depicts the national media of Pakistan being used as a vehicle by those in power, with little access to or representation for the opposition (Çakır and Batool, 2019). Political campaigns were often conducted through large processions or door-to-door visits. However, increasing freedom for the media industries from 2001 opened a window of opportunity for the public to receive more information and have their views represented more effectively. Due to the war on terror and ban on outdoor political gatherings, politicians turned towards the private media to convey messages via their screens. Here, the scenario was similar

to Habermas' (1991) model of transforming the public sphere, as journalists and those on good terms with media owners had time on TV screens, but communication was still unidirectional.

The polarisation of mainstream media in Pakistan continued to hinder information flows. Yet, the emerging popularity of new media platforms offered a different pattern of communication, unlike the largely unidirectional mainstream media communication channels. The technological shift and trust deficit in traditional media opened up an opportunity for a new media phase in Pakistan. The next section examines the use of social media for political communication in Pakistan, marking the third phase of media freedom and information explosion. This was accompanied by a decade and a half of democratic governments for the first time in Pakistan's history. The section highlights how scholars and critics understand social media as crucial in shaping contemporary political communication practices.

3.4 The third phase: an age of social media

According to Kugelman (2012), in Pakistan, social media is utilised for five primary purposes: giving more attention to news ignored by mainstream media, coordinating humanitarian causes, disseminating news about protests or other social movements, and stimulating communication between politicians and the public. The fifth main reason for using social media in Pakistan, as noted by Kugelman, is to promote online community building and foster social interactions among people. This involves utilising social media platforms to connect with others, share experiences, and engage in discussions about various topics beyond just news or activism. However, he is of the view that social media is not necessarily an effective platform for bringing change in the context of Pakistan, arguing that one reason is that Pakistan's conventional media outlets function as catalysts for change and incorporate the potential of social media to fulfil this role (Kugelman, 2012). He held this view in 2012, and in 2023, he continues to post detailed analyses of Pakistan's political updates on his Twitter handle.

Research published in the years that followed has shown that social media has the potential to facilitate political change in Pakistan. For instance, Afzal (2014) opines that before the explosion of social media and internet activity, Pakistani politicians used traditional methods to communicate their messages to potential voters. Electronic media provided the mechanics to facilitate these messages to the masses at large, but social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube have become popular in Pakistani politics. “Social media in Pakistan has also been gaining vast popularity among the masses” (p., 40).

Arif (2014) explored the role of YouTube as an alternate platform in political activism in Pakistan, Tunisia and Egypt. Drawing on case studies of the Lawyer movement in 2007 in Pakistan, the Jasmine Revolution in Tunisia, and the Arab Spring in Egypt, a total of 60 most-watched YouTube videos were selected for content analysis. The research findings suggest that YouTube played a vital role in disseminating information to the public when mainstream media was blocked by authoritarian regimes in all three countries. Another study conducted about the use of social media for political awareness in a comparatively remote province (Sindh) in Pakistan revealed that Facebook and YouTube are more popular social media platforms among young people for political information (Diou *et al.*, 2018).

The next section reviews existing literature about social media political communication among Pakistani youth, considering the country's demographics, where young people make up 60 per cent of the total population. According to the Gallup survey (2021), 45 percent of registered voters in Pakistan are between the ages of 18 and 35.

3.4.1 Social media and political communication for Pakistani young people

A study conducted by Eijaz (2013) on the popularity of social media for political communication with Pakistani young people showed that political parties in Pakistan use social media platforms for posting messages. It also indicates that young people studying in

universities, either from urban or rural areas, prefer Facebook for networking and gaining political information. However, it also suggests that the limitations of internet access, load shedding, socio-economic problems, and a low literacy rate in Pakistan act as a hindrance to the dissemination of information (Eijaz, 2013). Another study conducted on the popularity and acceptance of social media use among rural youth supported the argument presented by Eijaz. Ahmad, Alvi and Ittefaq (2019) found that young people in rural Pakistan use social media to access political information. The results reveal that most of the students use social media to enhance their political awareness and access information. Political efficacy is significantly based on online political participation. Study findings indicate that the online information which young university students receive from social media is enhancing their political awareness and is correlated with their offline political active participation. As Bode (2016) suggests, “In rural areas of Pakistan, the younger generations are very active on social media to participate in online and offline political happenings” (p., 7). Bode (2016) conducted research on the role of media in creating political awareness in Pakistan and his findings suggest that young people in Pakistan prefer social media platforms over traditional media to access political news. The findings also revealed that young people were aware of the manifestos of political parties and were clear about their voting rights as well. Another survey conducted on young people at universities living in hostels found that 70 percent received political information and updates from social media and the internet (Eijaz, 2013). It also revealed that young people also receive messages from political parties for membership and registration of their votes on their mobile phones.

Social media is facilitating the process of accountability. The corruption of National Insurance Corporation Limited (NICL), Steel Mill corruption case, rental power project corruption, malfeasance of funds by the Ministry of Religious Affairs (Hajj scandal) in

2011 are a few examples that show people's vigilant participation through social media (Eijaz, 2013, p., 125).

Zaheer (2018) argues that Pakistan is one of the countries where young people comprise 62 percent of the population and consume social media platforms for political discourse and information. In a world where young people are in the majority, he is of the view that greater political awareness from social media can be taken as a positive democratic development. However, he also expresses concern that young people are participating in acts of violence when there is a call for action from political parties they support. Zaheer (2018) suggests that political parties incite violent activities on social media platforms while mobilising them for the protests and offline political activities, "In the name of political participation through social media, they turn out to be intolerant and violent" (p., 107). Muzaffar, Chohdhry and Afzal (2019) also undertook research to investigate social media use among young people for political awareness. The research revealed that social media contribute to political awareness of university students in Pakistan. It also revealed that the awareness level of the selected sample of young university students was not as good as can be expected, but social media did play a role: "Although social media is making the youth socialise, they are not as knowledgeable as expected" (p., 11).

Ali and Chaudhary (2024) conducted a survey about the voting choices of young voters in Pakistan before the 2023 General Elections to investigate modes of communication channels influencing their decision making. The survey was conducted among 277 young voters including male and female both revealed that frequently use social media platforms like Twitter, YouTube, TikTok and WhatsApp to monitor campaigns from their favourite political parties and they prefer using platforms where they can interact with their party leaders directly by commenting on their posts and giving reactions. They contend that:

The social media handles of the political parties are a major source of information on the General Elections in Pakistan. The political gratifications that young voters require from their political leadership is reflected on the posts and hashtags used on the digital platforms. The trend of tweeting by the major political leaders has made a unique first-person communication with the users of the digital platforms (p., 275).

On the other hand, Shahzad and Omar (2021) conducted research on the importance and impact of social networks in the political process in Pakistan and suggest that online participation of young people in weaker democracies like Pakistan does not bring a political change unlike in Western democracies. A survey which was conducted with 864 respondents suggested that “extensive online networks result in less participation in online political activities, whereas no effect was found on youth political behaviour in the real setting” (Shahzad and Omar, 2021 p., 430). As these findings express some elements of further inquiry into the role of social media to mobilising young people, Khan *et al.* (2022) suggest that social media has added to democratic culture by providing platforms to young voters to create their profiles, follow politicians and participate in political communication. Khan et al conducted a survey in a public university by selecting 300 male and female graduate students to investigate the impact of social media on heightened awareness and political mobilisation. The study revealed that young voters in the age group from 18-28 use Facebook and Twitter for accessing political information and to communicate their views. 72.7% of the respondents considered social media for their primary source of political news, 51.7 % consume mainstream media headlines, 40.7% said they consume talk shows and 27.3% they consume public comments in the peer groups. The mechanism of narrative flow from political parties can be understood if a link between all these platforms could be developed in the research.

The literature reviewed depicts the use of YouTube and Facebook as tools utilised for political mobilisation and awareness in Pakistan along with Twitter. However, it is pertinent to mention

that YouTube does not provide two-way communication, and neither do politicians utilise this platform to interact with potential voters directly as few have their own YouTube channels. On the contrary, prominent political leaders and party figures in Pakistan maintain highly active and official Twitter accounts, particularly during election cycles (Qayyoom *et al.*, 2022; Batool *et al.*, 2022; Yousaf, 2016; Salam-Salmaoui and Salam, 2023). Given the norm of platform verification for high-profile public figures, it is likely that many such accounts carry verified badges (Varol *et al.*, 2017). The Facebook pages of political parties are also not verified and there are multiple pages with no clear distinction of actual representation of political parties. Twitter is the focus of this study for reasons previously discussed, and its significance has already been established in the introductory chapter. The next section reviews the existing literature research on Twitter and political communication in Pakistan.

3.5 Influence of Twitter on Pakistani society and politics

The literature included in this section highlights that Twitter has penetrated in Pakistani society and politics to such a level that all mainstream media outlets are using it as a source for their broadcasts. All domestic and foreign political responses are immediately available. Every post from political figures, journalists, and public can trigger communication at large. Political leaders have millions of followers on Twitter. Every politician, either from the treasury benches or from the opposition, keeps her or his team alert to retweets, replies, counters, or joins trends around the clock. As Ausserhofer and Maireder (2013) argue, the increasing popularity of Twitter among “politicians, journalists, political strategists and citizens” is demonstrated by the expanding body of research on this subject (p., 291). Twitter is also unique in its characteristics due to the speed of communication on it and characters like @ and #, which give it a special edge to create a sphericule by any individual. By using @ and adding an account with it, this function directly links with the addressee and helps generate a conversation. Similarly, # also provides a facility to create trends. Bruns (2023) terms Twitter

to be the second most important platform for creating network spheres for political deliberations. Anduiza et al (2009) likes it because of its low barriers as there is direct communication available.

A survey conducted on Twitter users for political communication in Pakistan revealed that people shape their opinion from the information they receive on Twitter (Afzal, 2014). Research by Masroor *et al.* (2019) on social media use in Pakistan suggests that political leaders in Pakistan use Twitter to project a self-positive image and a negative image for others to achieve different goals. Masroor et al analysed the tweets of two eminent Pakistani political figures chosen for unmasking a variety of discourse strategies at work from the perspective of critical discourse analysis (CDA) through the socio-cognitive model of ideological square, “The cognitive binary of positive self-presentation and negative other-presentation help achieve political domination and legitimisation of political actions by controlling the public opinion” (Masroor *et al.*, 2019).

Another study examining the predictive power of Twitter found that it can provide insights into the likely campaigning outcomes of political parties. Research was conducted by collecting pre-2018 General Election Twitter data from the API and analysing the data. It predicted the victory of PTI which was obvious after the announcement of the results (Bilal *et al.*, 2018). The study aimed to investigate whether Twitter accurately reflects public sentiment about political party affiliations and the potential of the platform as a predictor of election outcomes. The research suggested that Twitter has the potential to predict election results as it provides an opportunity for people to express their political opinions. Similar research conducted about the impact of Twitter in predicting the winner of the 2013 election held in Pakistan found that PTI would emerge as the election winner, which PMLN won. However, considering that PTI obtained a landslide victory in one province and secured several important seats across the country, researchers concluded that Twitter could have some influence on the election result,

although it cannot be considered representative of the overall voting population. Twitter users, however, do not represent the entire population, but if famous public figures who have millions of followers on Twitter use it for political communication, then it may contribute to political gains. However, another study conducted in 2016 revealed that the number of Twitter users in Pakistan are too few to be a significant factor for political change. Secondly, the research also found that the Twitter community in Pakistan is also different in a way that they follow religious leaders, politicians, and share their lives and religious beliefs on that platform. In other countries, people follow celebrities, politicians, and actors for the same reason (Khan *et al.*, 2016). Khan *et al.*, in their Twitter user analysis in all four provinces and the capital city Islamabad of Pakistan, found that 41% of the total Twitter users were from Punjab province, 36% belonged to Sindh, 21% from Islamabad and a lower proportion were from another two provinces, Balochistan and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. This indicates that the presence of politicians and political parties on Twitter might have different impacts in different parts of the country, and the parties might utilise Twitter strategically based on the percentage of presence of people from each province. This factor will be further developed in my research.

Azeema, Abbasi and Ansari (2020) argue that prominent journalists and mainstream media also utilise Twitter posts for their news content to enhance their credibility. Research conducted on the use of Twitter for diplomacy between Pakistan and the US during the visit of the then PM Imran Khan to the US revealed that hashtags #PMIKInUSA and #PMIKJalsaInUSA were generated from the PTI official account of Imran Khan and were retweeted and promoted by media influencers and PTI supporters. The research explored the role of Twitter in building positive ties between Pakistan and the US in September 2019, when Donald Trump was the President of the US. QAI SAR (2021) found in his research that Twitter played a vital role in sentiment building about the Turkish President's visit to Pakistan. It also revealed a similarity between the taglines of newspaper websites and Twitter news content related to the topic. He

termed it “intermedia agenda setting”, in which both mainstream media and social media were setting an atmosphere of “Ottoman Empire” nostalgia (p., 187). The study collected data from the Twitter API and cross-matched it with a daytime lag difference with the news publications of the main Pakistani English newspapers, including The Nation, The News International, and the Express Tribune. The study found that social media and mainstream media in Pakistan are interconnected and integrated, and there is an expression of the same agenda setting between social media platforms and newspaper websites as well (QAISAR, 2021).

The 2013 General Election was the first time Twitter use came to the forefront in Pakistan. A study conducted about the usage of Twitter by Members of the National Assembly of Pakistan between 2013 and 2018 revealed that politicians in Pakistan used Twitter to post messages to defame and criticise other politicians. The research, which was conducted to explore what type of language and content politicians are posting on Twitter, found that it is strategic for politicians to construct posts on Twitter by using such rhetoric that they get the response they want from the public. This gives the impression of agenda setting again. Because of the absence of mainstream media as moderator, politicians themselves were able to use Twitter to directly communicate their messages to the electorate. That is the reason political parties are hiring social media teams (Shami, Khan and Ashfaq, 2019). Primarily, the study focused on what members of the National Assembly were using Twitter for. Data collected through questionnaires indicated that majority of the MNAs (59.5%) consider using Twitter to convey their political ideology and to inform people about their political engagements. 13.5% considered they use Twitter to inform people about certain issues. Thus, the findings indicate that politicians utilise Twitter for their political communication, preferring it over Facebook, Instagram, and other social media platforms to reach their potential voters (Shami, 2019).

Another study conducted on the first-ever Twitter campaign by Pakistani political parties to mobilise, inform and engage voters during the elections revealed that Twitter played a major

role in motivating young people to exercise their voting rights(Ahmed and Skoric, 2014). The research findings suggest a strong relationship between online Twitter activity and the offline political campaign during the 2013 elections. The overall timeline distribution of Twitter activity by political parties in Pakistan signals a strong relationship between Twitter and offline party activities, as the spikes in tweeting about the 2013 Pakistan General Election can be linked to major political events and offline campaigning. For instance, Ahmed and Skoric (2014) presented in their research they conducted on first ever Twitter campaign in Pakistani politics that PTI's success (at a provincial level) was largely driven by a unique combination of Twitter communication and face-to-face campaigning aimed at increasing voter turnout, especially among the youth population. Noor Hayat, Zahra and Ali (2022) Also conducted research about the role of Twitter in creating awareness among young people in Pakistan. The research, which was conducted using a survey method with closed-ended questions among a sample size of 300 male and female university students, revealed that youth in Pakistan utilise political information they receive from Twitter and that they communicate on Twitter. The survey was intended to find answers about the impact of Twitter activity on offline political activity, the impact of Twitter political activity on government decisions, and the role of Twitter as a source or a facilitator for the mainstream media organizations and as an influencer of political narrative during General Elections 2013, revealed that majority of the young people believe Twitter does play a role. The findings of the survey revealed that 36% of respondents agreed that political participation on Twitter can affect offline participation in politics, 55% believe that Twitter has facilitated political communication by involving news organisations and 50% suggested Twitter for being the most influential medium for political communication (Noor Hayat, Zahra and Ali, 2022). In Pakistan, this is an emerging phenomenon as Twitter users reached 4.25 million (Statista, 2024) which makes it an interesting area of research not only for communication analysts but also for political campaign strategy managers.

Another research study conducted on the use of hashtags and bots for trend manipulation by political parties in Pakistan revealed that hashtags are used for negative campaigning about other political parties and personalities on Twitter (Kausar, Tahir and Mehmood, 2021). The research also reveals that party factions generate positive hashtags on Twitter to make pro-party trends as well (Kausar, Tahir and Mehmood, 2021), “Hashtags related to factions and personalities are used by political rivals to create political polarisation on online social media” (p., 10). Recent research conducted about information sharing patterns of Pakistani politicians during the 2018 elections on Twitter reveals that the winning party (PTI) leader, Imran Khan, had more followers on Twitter, and he was active during the last month's political campaign on Twitter. Most of the tweets analysed were about calling for votes, promises for developments and political party promotions. The study conducted by using mixed method and analysed six data sets of Twitter posts including three main political party accounts (PTI, PMLN, PPP) their leaders (Imran Khan for PTI, Shehbaz Sharif for PMLN and Bilawal Bhutto for PPP) revealed that in terms of number of tweets and number of hashtags, the PTI official account was at the top, PPP's official account made least Twitter posts and PMLN's official account used the least party hashtags. In addition to that, PTI was the political party that mentioned other accounts in their tweets by using the @ function of Twitter (763 mentions for three weeks), PMLN used this function the least (44 mentions). Findings about the subsets of tweets from party leaders indicated that tweets from Bilawal Bhutto, leader of the PPP, covered a wider range of issues, including terrorism, politics, promotion, calls for votes, and personal life. There were no tweets about any religious issue. The data revealed that young people were only mentioned and addressed by PTI leader Imran Khan; PPP and PMLN did not tweet anything regarding 62 per cent of the population who use social media around the clock. Even the call for votes was less from the PMLN leader as compared to the PPP and the PTI. What

was most apparent from the research findings was PTI's focus on young people, indicating that the party is aware of the type of users active on the Twitter platform.

3.6 Twitter trolling and hate

One of the most troubling consequences of digital political communication is the rise of online trolling and hate campaigns. Globally, research has shown how social media affordances such as anonymity, virality, and algorithmic amplification create conditions in which abuse and harassment can thrive, often targeting journalists, women, and political opponents (Posetti *et al.*, 2022). Recent academic research has also illuminated a concerning phenomenon: female journalists are increasingly subjected to targeted trolling campaigns by political accounts associated with the PTI party. These findings indicate that the PTI government has deployed social media teams specifically to harass journalists who dare to criticise government actions (Hussain, Bostan and Qaisarani (2022). The research conducted on trolling of particularly women journalists on Twitter also revealed that many female journalists abandoned online activities on Twitter due to the level of trolling they were facing, "Hashtags and trends were run against female journalists to discourage them from the critical coverage of the government policies" (p., 2). Content analysis of the trolling tweets and hashtags shows that the language used against female journalists was unethical, abusive and harassing. The research provides insight into the directness of exposure of political party supporters towards journalists or opposition politicians. Another study conducted on the postcolonial men dominating behaviour of Pakistani Twitter users towards women journalists revealed that nine out of ten women faced aggression from political party supporters while expressing their opinions on Twitter (Siddiqua, Gong and Aksar, 2023). The research showed that 24 female journalists presented a combined application/report before a parliamentary committee on Human Rights in which they alleged that there was a coordinated, well-planned harassment campaign against them to

snub their voice on Twitter by PTI. The report was presented before committee on the 9th of August 2020 (Siddiqua, Gong and Aksar, 2023).

Shafiq (2021) investigated the use of hate speech on Twitter by the official information secretaries of three prominent political parties, PMLN (Maryam Aurangzeb), PPP (Maulla Bakhsh Chandio) and PTI (Fawad Chaudhry) of Pakistan, before the General Election of 2018. Discourse analysis of the tweets taken from the timelines of the information secretaries of political parties revealed that the language contained hatred and was offensive. Shafiq highlights that political leaders use abusive language towards opponents in public gatherings and the narrative is picked up by the followers and party supporters. She provided an example from PTI leader Imran Khan, who used the word “donkeys” for PMLN supporters, and the word was taken up by its supporters (p., 231). Violent incidents of beating donkeys were witnessed after that by PTI supporters to tease and incite other political party supporters. The research reveals that politicians also use dehumanising language for each other, as Maryam Aurangzeb addressed in one of her tweets to Imran Khan for being a donkey, commenting that he can never be a horse. Politicians often mobilise ethnic identities as a political strategy, such as appealing to Pashtun identity in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa or Sindhi identity in Sindh. By invoking cultural heritage, language, and regional belonging, they portray themselves as the most authentic defenders of their community’s rights, positioning outsiders as less capable of safeguarding those interests. They accuse opponents, they curse each other as well, “Twitter allows them to think through their hate speech and get more strategic with their words” (Shafiq, 2021 p., 241). Recent research conducted by Zaman and Abbas (2023) about the Twitter activities at the ousting of former Prime Minister Imran Khan also revealed similar findings that the platform plays a vital role in shaping public opinion, providing an alternative media platform in the restricted mainstream media environment in Pakistan. The research focused on public narrative building after the vote of no confidence for the former Prime Minister of

Pakistan, Imran Khan. Zaman and Abbas argued that the public followed the narrative about political unrest in Pakistan on Twitter. “Twitter announced #ImportedGovernmentNaManzoor as a record trending hashtag in history” (Zaman and Abbas, 2022, p. 1612). The research highlighted the connection of various sections of society on Twitter in political discussions. The visualisation of the communication connection between different sections of society was displayed in graphs. In the graph provided, clusters represent various groups of people in society who are connected on Twitter. It is also explained how these clusters relate to the other clusters on Twitter to describe the flow of information from one group to another. The graph shows how the narrative of “RegimechangeinPakistan” reached different groups of society.

3.7 Research Gap

Most of the research conducted on Twitter usage in Pakistan by political parties is carried out through discourse analysis of Twitter data or sentiment analysis. In addition, much of the research is focused on what political parties are doing on Twitter. There is less focus on “how” they are doing it, what strategy they are adopting, and if they are using online Twitter campaigning to mobilise people for offline political activities. The priorities of the political parties in utilising Twitter are established and analysed by directly using Twitter content. There is less evidence of research which has involved interviews with journalists, social media team heads and politicians - what I term the elite circle - to enquire about the strategies and dependencies of their political communication on Twitter, which is the focus of this study. This research explores the mechanism of framing of the messages by political parties on Twitter, followed by the dissemination of those messages through careful strategic planning. It also explores what role mainstream media and journalists are playing when utilising Twitter as a platform for political news. Based on the research gap, the following questions guide the empirical part of the study.

1. How do political parties in Pakistan strategically use Twitter for campaigning and narrative construction?
2. What role do journalists play on Twitter in circulating and amplifying political party messages?
3. How is Twitter shaping the structure and dynamics of political communication within Pakistan's hybrid and elite-dominated public sphere?

3.8 Conclusion

Reviewing literature on Twitter use in political communication in Pakistan, it is considered an important strategic tool by politicians and political parties. Politicians use Twitter for strengthening diplomatic relations, calling for votes, asking for voter registrations, maligning each other and using different tactics like ethnic and religious cards to secure empathy from potential voters. Social media, particularly Twitter, is also used by the urban and rural youth of Pakistan. Some common themes highlighted from the literature review of Twitter political communication in other Western and non-Western countries also appeared in the literature review conducted about Twitter use in Pakistan. For instance, the academic sources reviewed focused on links between Twitter and election activities, political trending and the Twitter use by political parties in Pakistan. Some of the utilisations which could be identified from the existing literature of social media in general and Twitter in specific in Pakistan included, party promotion, political party leader promotion, self-promotion, giving opinion, news sharing, attacking opponents, insulting other politicians, un-ethical language use, threatening, criticism, abuse, narrative building, raising awareness, to impact decision making, propaganda, self-appreciation and trolling. By reaching out to the journalists, politicians, and media managers of political parties, my research investigates how Twitter as a platform shapes traditional ways of political communication in Pakistan. However, it is important to consider the reach of

Twitter narratives among people with lower education levels, living in remote areas, or with limited internet access. As briefly outlined in Chapter 1, this study adopts the Framing theory as the main approach aligned with public sphere as its overarching theoretical framework, building on its classical formulation and subsequent adaptations to digital and hybrid media contexts. The following chapter develops this framework in detail, outlining how concepts from the public sphere tradition, and its contemporary reconceptualisation, will inform the study's exploration of political communication in Pakistan.

Chapter 4: Theoretical Framework

4.1 Introduction

This chapter outlines the theoretical foundations that guide this study's examination of the strategic use of Twitter by political parties, mainstream media, and journalists in Pakistan. Specifically, it outlines a framework to analyse how political and media actors in Pakistan construct political messages on Twitter and how they disseminate them across broader digital and offline spaces. Two key theoretical approaches underpin the framework: framing theory and the transformation of the public sphere.

First, understanding how political actors and media practitioners frame political messages is essential for examining their communication strategies on Twitter. Framing theory provides a valuable critical lens through which to explore the construction of political narratives, issue salience, and meaning making on social media. It can be utilised to offer insight into the selection, emphasis, and exclusion processes involved when political parties and journalists craft their messages to shape public perception and discourse.

Second, alongside the framing of messages, drawing on the gaps identified in the literature review, it is also important in the Pakistani context to investigate how Twitter communications are disseminated and have material effects beyond the platform itself. To analyse this phenomenon, I draw on the transformation of the public sphere, which provides a framework to understand how digital platforms like Twitter interact with traditional media and offline spaces in shaping political debate. As political communication increasingly circulates across online and offline environments, it is important to examine how Twitter posts are recontextualised through mainstream media coverage and other digital forums, contributing to a reconfigured public sphere shaped by cross-media interaction rather than a single, unified communicative space.

Together, these theoretical perspectives enable a comprehensive analysis of the strategic construction, dissemination and effects of political messages. Framing theory focuses attention on the ‘how’ of message construction on Twitter, while the transformation of the public sphere addresses how these messages move, are adapted, and amplified across multiple arenas of political communication. By integrating these concepts, it is possible to deepen understandings of the evolving practices and impacts of political communication in a digitally networked society.

4.2 Framing theory and social media messaging

The literature reviewed in Chapter’s 2 and 3 suggests that, in Pakistan, politicians post messages on social media to defame other parties, to establish their manifesto, to highlight specific issues and hide others. It is the framing of messages involved, along with other strategies, that is important to understand. Even if political parties are spending money on their media teams to strengthen the salience of their messages and target potential voters, media teams also work on projecting certain issues by framing messages accordingly. When the content of political communication is triggered from the political party representatives or official political party accounts, it often includes a clear agenda. For example, political parties use social media platforms for their political campaigns to attract voter attention, run propaganda against other political parties or to express their party manifesto. Framing theory is an extension of agenda-setting theory, which was developed by McCombs and Shaw (1972). The basis of framing theory is that the media focuses attention on specific events and then places them within a field of meaning. Goffman (1974) systematised the concept of framing into a constructionist theory in his book ‘Framing Theory’, defining frames as a set of textual, image or visual messages which enable the brain to interpret information based on previous

experience. He termed it as “schemata of interpretation” (Güran and Özarıslan, 2022 p. 446). After reviewing the literature on frame analysis in social media, virtual digital communities and social media movements, Güran and Özarıslan found that this approach is suitable for social media research. They suggest that, “frame analysis presents an even broader potential for the research of dynamic communication processes in the fast lives of virtual communities and the vast effects of online interaction of social, political, commercial institutions” (p. 446). Entman (1993) conceptualised frames as existing packets of ideas which inform individuals to process new information, and these informed ideas are used as a reference in future to make decisions about any relevant issue that they frame. Entman argues that framing serves as the central mechanism through which government officials and journalists exercise political power over each other as well as over the public. He is also of the view that, despite efforts from journalists to stay unbiased, their framing of news helps political parties. Humphreys and Latour (2013) explain that frames function by drawing attention to specific aspects of a practice while simultaneously diverting attention from others. Stroud and Muddiman (2019) conducted research on the social media engagement of political news on a social media platform and concluded that news with political strategy framing attracts more attention, while news with political issues framing receives more comments and responses: “The public, it seems, prefers news that has normatively undesirable democratic consequences” (p. 443). They introduced different versions of the posts, adding various frames to the headlines of the same political news article, and conducted a meta-analysis of the responses. The findings revealed that different frames receive different reactions on social media. It was noted that the news with undemocratic consequences received more attention. Regardless of the type of responses received for the different frames, they underscored the importance and ongoing influence of framing theory in the digital sphere and for political communication. Furthermore, Hemphill, Culotta and Heston (2013) conducted research on the framing of messages by US politicians

to investigate which issues need more framing effort and who is working more on framing for posting on a social media platform. The findings revealed that politicians actively use social media to frame certain issues by creating hashtags or initiating discussions on specific topics. The findings also indicate that social media has provided an opportunity to politicians to influence potential voters through framing. Researchers “applied statistical feature selection algorithms to identify hashtags used for framing and were able to classify politicians by party with over 95% accuracy by considering only 100 hashtags” (p. 3). The findings clearly revealed that different political parties were using specific frames to select and promote hashtags. Banks *et al.* (2021) conducted research to investigate whether social media just provides a platform for like-minded people to cluster or if there was any role of frames presented to them. The research, focused on the impact of negative frames, revealed that they change the perception of social media users about that event or person, even if their position remains the same during the exposure of those frames to the users.

Manor and Crilley (2018) highlights how the Ministry of Information of Israel crafted frames in visual messages on Twitter to influence audiences and build their image during the 2014 Gaza riots. Accepting the traditional concept of framing theory, Manor argues that the expansion of the idea of framing is necessary to explain how governments frame their messages during war times for maintaining their image and build trust. Stier (2016) argues that political communication on Twitter is highly mediated and needs a very careful use of semantics to attract voters, convince others and compete with their opponents. As the traditional aspect of framing is concerned, certain angles of the main topic are highlighted in a way that it becomes influential to the audience. For example, if a political party introduces health reforms, it will frame messages by showing the number of beneficiaries. On the other hand, the opposition might find several people who did not receive benefits from the reform, and they would frame a message post by mentioning the failure of the government to meet public health needs.

Framing, as a theory of mass communication, refers to how the media packages and presents information to the public (Entman, 2007). According to the theory, the media highlights certain events and then places them within a particular context to encourage or discourage certain interpretations. As the research explores the strategic use of Twitter by political parties, mainstream media and journalists in Pakistan, it is also an attempt to explore whether and how political parties use framing to influence potential voters and engage in narrative building. Framing theory is particularly well suited to this study because it addresses the interpretive processes through which political actors and media shape public understanding of issues. On platforms such as Twitter, the brevity of posts, the strategic use of hashtags, and the incorporation of visual elements all create conditions in which the selection, emphasis, and omission of information become central to meaning-making (Meraz and Papacharissi, 2013; Bruns and Highfield, 2015). In the Pakistani context, where political parties and journalists frequently interact within a hybrid media environment, framing theory provides a valuable analytical lens to examine how competing narratives are constructed and contested. This is especially relevant given Entman (1993)'s assertion that framing performs four key functions, defining problems, diagnosing causes, making moral judgements, and suggesting remedies, all of which can be observed in the political discourse surrounding elections, governance, and policy debates in Pakistan's Twitter sphere. As Devreese (2005) notes, framing is both a product of intentional strategic communication by political actors and the result of journalistic routines, making it particularly apt for studying the dynamic interplay between parties, media, and audiences in a networked public sphere.

While framing theory offers valuable tools for examining how political actors and journalists construct and contest meaning on Twitter, it does not in itself account for the broader communicative environment in which these interactions occur. To understand how these framing processes operate within the structural, normative, and participatory dimensions of

political discourse, this study situates them within the concept of the public sphere, adapted for the realities of digital and hybrid media systems.

4.3 The digital public sphere in Pakistan

The dynamics of political communication on Twitter in Pakistan cannot be fully understood through framing theory alone. While framing illuminates the processes by which political actors and journalists construct and contest meaning, it does not, by itself, explain the broader socio-technical environment in which these frames are produced, circulated, and amplified. For this reason, this study also adopts the concept of the digital public sphere, which extends Habermas's (1962/1989) original model into the context of networked communication. Habermas conceptualised the public sphere as a space of mediated public communication through which political opinions are formed, premised on principles of openness, accessibility, and rational-critical debate. While this formulation provides a foundational framework for understanding the relationship between communication and democracy, it was developed in relation to mass media systems and does not fully account for the dynamics of contemporary digital platforms. Scholars have therefore argued that the public sphere must be understood as reconfigured under digital conditions, where communication is shaped by platform architectures, visibility logics, and affective engagement rather than solely deliberative exchange (Papacharissi, 2010; 2015). In this section, I elaborate on how subsequent scholars have further developed and established the concept of the digital or networked public sphere, particularly through the work of Papacharissi (2010), Benkler (2006), Bruns and Highfield (2015), Raman(2011)and Latif (2021) and many others, and how these perspectives are drawn upon to conceptualise the public sphere for the purposes of this research.. Digital platforms expand access and participation while simultaneously reshaping visibility, discourse dynamics, and the formation of public opinion, complicating the deliberative conditions assumed in Habermas's original framework. In this study, the public sphere is approached as a digitally

mediated and hybrid communicative space, in which political messages circulate across Twitter and mainstream news media, and where agenda formation and amplification are driven by strategic actors and institutional media rather than inclusive public deliberation. In digital environments, the public sphere is reconfigured through affordances such as immediacy, interactivity, algorithmic curation, and the collapse of traditional gatekeeping (Benkler, 2006; Papacharissi, 2015). These conditions not only shape the visibility and reach of political frames but also influence who participates in discourse, how issues gain traction, and how counter-frames emerge (Chadwick, 2017; Freelon and Wells, 2020). In Pakistan's hybrid media system, where mainstream journalism and social media are deeply intertwined, the digital public sphere provides a conceptual scaffold for examining how framing practices unfold within a participatory yet highly mediated communicative arena. Combining the two perspectives enables a more comprehensive analysis framing theory captures the micro-level construction of political meaning, while the digital public sphere situates these processes within the macro-level structures, norms, and affordances of contemporary political communication.

The traditional concept of the public sphere is regarded as a fundamental element for understanding two main components: public communication and deliberation (Bruns and Highfield, 2015). Fraser (2017) further elucidates the concept of the public sphere by emphasising that it “designates a discursive arena in modern societies where private persons discuss matters of common interest” (deliberation) (p. 247). Moreover, Fraser also argues that the classical idea of the public sphere does not align with the actual pattern and structure of public communication; however, it provides a benchmark to criticise and evaluate the effectiveness and legitimacy of what is deemed public opinion.

Scholars like Farooq and Rashid (2021), Fraser (1992) and Calhoun (1993), term the idea of a national public sphere to be state-centred, in which only state narratives were in the centre, and public opinion was aligned with that narrative. Fraser (1992) suspects the concept of the public

sphere to be male-biased as well. She coined the idea of the presence of counter/local publics or public spaces, which were more representative of the public instead of the state. Fraser also argues that these local, marginalised publics can contribute towards the mainstream state or national public sphere. The argument Fraser brought forward is that the national public sphere neglects the contributions of small, marginalised spheres, such as business groups, local charities, community groups that help one another, and even smaller professional groups. Calhoun (2010) criticises the initial concept of the national public sphere because it does not cover public interactions and the ties generated as a result of information sharing during public interactions between marginalised groups of society. Asen and Brouwer (2001) have demonstrated through five different case studies that conflict situations in which discussions were held beyond the official national or state public sphere and had an impact on the overall public sphere, referring that the deliberation can occur outside the public sphere, unlike the Habermasian public sphere. Fuchs (2014) outlined the main criticisms of public sphere theory in three key points: (1) the 'working class critique,' which argues that Habermas' perspective on the working class is centred around the 'bourgeois public sphere,' neglecting other class categories and presenting two main issues: the restrictions on freedom of speech and public opinion, as well as on freedom of association and assembly; (2) the 'postmodern critique,' which contends that only 'educated, wealthy men' fit into Habermas' conception; and (3) the 'cultural imperialism critique,' in which Fuchs asserts that Habermas endorses the notion of Western countries dominating other cultures and imposing the Western model on them (Fuchs 2014, pp., 62-65). He stated, "the cultural imperialism critique stresses that the public sphere is a Western enlightenment concept that Western societies use for trying to impose their political, economic and social systems on other countries" (p., 65)

Guha (2003) and Chatterjee (1993) offer an alternative to the idea of counter publics and emphasise the need to focus on public spaces that have local salience and elucidate local

relationships. An example from South Asian societies is the South Indian caste councils, a social network organised around caste lines that regulates the relationship between its members, the states, and other national civil society organisations (Fihl, 2013). With the advent of the internet and social media, there are different debates regarding changes in the form of communication and many challenge whether Habermasian concept of public sphere is still relevant.

Papacharissi (2020) argues that the model of the virtual sphere is a metaphor, and it can take any shape when materialised. Adding to her argument, she believes spheres are also divided in the same way as traditional politics, but with more opportunities or space for ordinary people to express themselves. Papacharissi also notes that it is possible for typical political cultures to be adopted by digital technologies rather than changing them (Papacharissi, 2020). Burns and Highfield (2015) opine that the spheres are shaped based on interests, not on geographical boundaries. The public in this sphere is no longer limited to domestic or national audiences; rather, every media outlet or social media platform represents a distinct sphere. Many have contributed to the reimagining of Habermas's public sphere in the social media era. Fraser (1992) argues that there are multiple spheres, including “official governmental public spheres, mass-mediated mainstream public spheres, counter public spheres, and informal public spheres in everyday life within a society”, and are potentially different from each other (Fraser, 1992 p. 612). Additionally, social media platforms and multiple channels have divided the main uniform public sphere into many fragmented, divergent, yet overlapping public spheres.

Social media platforms have added more deliberation to the argument about the multiplicity of publics or public spheres. Social media provides a direct means of communication for the public, journalists, politicians and groups of people with similar interests. The question of “who controls the narrative” and how communication is used for political purposes requires further

investigation. Benkler (2006) argues that the rise of the networked public sphere has blurred the boundaries between mass media and new digital platforms, creating overlaps where mainstream media and social media interact and circulate content across both domains. A more refined and scientific approach to understanding communication mechanisms on social media is given by Gitlin (2002). He introduced the term “sphericules” to explain temporary spheres created by social media users around themes within their presence in domains such as culture, politics, gender, sports, or climate. In a sphericule, a public is created around a current theme or issue. They discuss that issue for a specific amount of time, and then it disappears. There is a consensus about this microlevel of construction of publics (sphericules) among many scholars like Bruns and Highfield (2015), and Gitlin (2002). Cunningham (2001) argues about sphericules of “diasporic media” by bringing examples of immigrants from different countries discussing their problems on media platforms (p., 131). Dahlgren (2005) suggests that issue publics are a further subset of sphericules. For instance, if a sphericule deliberates about gender discrimination, an issue the public will likely discuss is a policy or report related to gender reforms. Habermas (2006) is of the view that these informal discussions in the public sphere affect public opinion and attitudes towards certain issues. These sphericules may be generated by individuals and others join them to share their knowledge and opinion.

Raman (2011) supports the idea of a hybrid blended model of e-democracy for developing countries where the digital divide is often a significant challenge. In her work on Habermas’s conceptualisation in a non-Western context, using a case study of Bangalore city, India, Raman argues that a Western model cannot be simply replicated in India, where public discussions often involve conflicts and disagreements alongside careful reasoning. The study examines how digital technology, when strategically combined with existing civil networks, can enhance communication, bridge the communication gap, and foster narratives despite the digital divide. The level of complexity in examining the role of the virtual public sphere in empowering

ordinary citizens increases in the context of developing countries, where people are engaged in conflict and political struggle to gain access to basic resources such as clean drinking water and infrastructure such as paved streets. The idea of public sphere needs further investigation in developing countries to understand and expand the notion of the public sphere. This is because most of the population must deal with issues of physical access to technology, lack of infrastructure such as reliable electricity, lack of relevant content in local languages and disparate skill levels, besides issues related to low literacy rates, language barriers since local language fonts and content is relatively rare, and low self-efficacy about ICT use. Raman argues that if we assume educated and skilled citizens, appropriate technical infrastructure, and accessible online platforms are essential for fostering deliberative democracy through information technologies, then many developing countries will face a long wait before witnessing any significant evidence of citizen engagement and civic empowerment using ICT. Latif (2023) has argued that, unlike the Habermasian public sphere, interactions in Pakistan are often fractious, uncivil, and lead to scandals. In her case study about the relevance of the public sphere in “Dera” (tribal) culture of Pakistan, she reveals that people who run Deras are influential in those village settings and enjoy ruling the narrative, making decisions about local issues, and even mediating relations. She argues that the dynamics of the public sphere in Pakistan exclude marginalised groups from contributing to any narrative, making it important to understand the overall structure and mechanisms:

Beyond Pakistan, I make the case for how decoupling of the public sphere from the state can reveal interstitial spaces such as the *dera* and the local gatekeepers who manage such spaces, as well as elucidate how micro public spheres influence participation in formal political institutions (Latif, 2023, p., 99).

Other works like Pirzadeh and Pirzada (2019) have titled their research on the subject of the role of popular music in the Pakistani Public Sphere and the transformation of the public sphere in current democratic transfers of governments since 2008, but have not touched the technicalities of the concept. Mushtaq and Baig (2021) have discussed around three varied but interrelated topics of public spaces, gender and religion in Pakistan. In public spaces, women demonstrated unity and sisterhood, acting as a collective of like-minded individuals. The public response to the Aurat March, particularly the disproportionate outrage expressed by men, highlighted exactly why women marched for their rights.

The preceding discussion on the nature of the public sphere and interactions in South Asia, particularly India and Pakistan, reveals that the society, the dynamics of the public sphere, and the digital divide differ in the Pakistani setup compared to the Western concept of the public sphere presented by Habermas. It needs careful investigation into the flow of narrative and the utilisation of digital media for political communication. Considering the argument of Raman (2020) and Latif (2023), Pakistan has a digital divide, has informal influential elites, and the flow of narrative in this situation seems more complex. The existence of multiple spheres within the broader public sphere, such as issue publics, sphericules, and fragmented digital communities, supports this research's aim to examine the role of the Twitter sphere in shaping political communication in Pakistan, a context further complicated by digital inequality.

This study's theoretical framework adapts the ideas of Papacharissi (2020) who argues that the public sphere is "virtual" and takes different forms depending on social and political factors, is fluid in nature, and the concepts from Gitlin (1998) and Benkler (2006) who highlight how users engage across various platforms and issue publics, as the starting point to establish further how political parties manage to build narrative, run political campaigns in Pakistan in a complex political culture. I consider Twitter as part of a big digital sphere comprising other

social media platforms being utilised in Pakistan. Hashtags created on Twitter for projecting a narrative by political parties are conceived as sphericules and the spaces conducted on Twitter as issue publics

Figure 4.1 Conceptualising Twitter Sphere in Pakistan (self-contribution)

My research will further establish that in Pakistan, Twitter and mainstream media are intertwined, with journalists' professional and personal identities overlapping.

Figure 4.2 Visual presentation of offline public mainstream media and Twitter overlap (self-contribution)

Viewership of mainstream news media is established in Chapter 3, with 143 million offline users. Unlike Herman and Chomsky (2010)'s concept of connected society, and the Western educated public sphere where deliberations result in the production of knowledge, I establish through my findings that neither society is all connected in the digital sphere, nor are there educated deliberations in Pakistan, but Twitter and the digital sphere is part of the overall public sphere and plays role in narrative building. Agreeing with the research findings of Raman and Latif, this research will further establish how micro publics in rural areas are strategically

connected by political parties to build a narrative and run political campaigns at the grassroots level. Despite the decentralisation of discourse and the micro-level participation fostered by hashtags, it is the political parties in Pakistan that strategically construct and guide these political discussions. Figure 4.3 explains the basic concepts of the digital and public spheres on which this research will be developed and will explore further complexities through interview data to respond to the research questions. The figure represents the basic point from which the findings will be established in the second part of the thesis. There are various overlapping subsets in Pakistan's digital public sphere. This study looks explicitly at Twitter to show how political parties have their own subdivisions on the platform and how they shape political communication on this platform, and how that narrative set on Twitter is disseminated in the broader digital media sphere and to the offline public.

Figure 4.3 A visual depiction of the connectivity of the digital sphere and the offline public sphere (self-contribution)

4.4 Conclusion

In this chapter, the value of framing theory has been established as a critical lens for understanding the intricate landscape of political communication in Pakistan. By adapting this concept, the research aims to illuminate how political parties and mainstream media actively shape narratives and influence public perception within the unique context of the Pakistani (digital) public sphere. Framing theory helps explain how information is presented and interpreted, enabling an analysis of the strategic choices made by political entities and media

outlets in Pakistan in constructing their messages. This framework complements the examination of the public sphere, allowing for a nuanced exploration of the interactions between various stakeholders, including political actors and the media, and the implications these interactions have on discourse and civic engagement. By applying both framing theory and the concept of the (digital) public sphere, this research reveals the mechanisms through which political communication unfolds in Pakistan, particularly considering existing digital divides and socio-political complexities. The interplay of these two lenses will facilitate a deeper understanding of how narratives are crafted and contested, ultimately offering insights into the challenges and opportunities for democratic participation in a rapidly evolving media environment. In summary, the chapter sets the stage for a comprehensive analysis of political communication in Pakistan, highlighting the importance of framing and public sphere dynamics in shaping civic engagement and the overall political landscape. As the research progresses, this foundational understanding will guide the investigation into how political parties navigate these dimensions to influence public discourse and engage with citizens in a meaningful way.

Chapter 5: Methodology

5.1 Introduction

Building on the study's theoretical framework, this chapter details the research design and methods employed to investigate how political parties, mainstream media, and journalists in Pakistan strategically use Twitter for political communication. The application of framing theory and the concept of the transformation of the public sphere provide the analytical lenses through which the research questions are examined and guide the selection of the analytical approach. These theoretical perspectives shape the qualitative methodology, data collection strategies, and data analysis techniques used to explore the framing and dissemination of political messages across digital and offline spaces. I begin by outlining the study's research approach and methodology, before turning to the research questions. A predominantly qualitative research methodology is employed to explore the role of Twitter in shaping political communication in Pakistan, through a country case study. Figure 5.1 provides a visual representation of the research process.

Figure 5.1 Visual representation of the research plan (self-contribution)

5.2 Research philosophy

Melnikovas (2018) notes that research philosophy is the basis of research. It draws the line between the ontology, epistemology, and axiology of the study. Dobson (2002) also emphasises the importance of understanding the philosophical underpinnings of research for any researcher, arguing that it provides confidence in justifying their research activity. Grix (2004) also holds the view that scholarly work should be grounded in and derive from a philosophical position, as this leads to an appropriate choice of research questions, techniques, and methodologies to achieve defined objectives. This study is underpinned by an interpretivist research philosophy, which is consistent with the theoretical framework guiding the inquiry. Rooted in the concept of strategic framing, the study examines how political parties craft and disseminate messages within the public sphere, particularly through digital media platforms like Twitter. Framing theory emphasises the selective construction of meaning, where communicators highlight aspects of perceived reality to promote problem definitions, causal

interpretations, moral evaluations, or treatment recommendations. This process of meaning-making is inherently subjective, contingent upon the communicator's intent and the socio-political context in which communication occurs. Similarly, the digital public sphere is a discursive space where meanings are actively constructed, challenged, and negotiated through communicative interactions. As such, an interpretivist approach is most appropriate, as it allows for the exploration of socially constructed meanings, intentions, and practices embedded within strategic political communication.

Interpretivism is grounded in the belief that reality is socially constructed, meaning that there is no single, objective truth but multiple realities shaped by social, cultural, and historical contexts (Saunders *et al.*, 2015; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Ontologically, it adopts a subjectivist stance, recognising that human experiences and interpretations are central to understanding the world. Epistemologically, it values knowledge generated through the subjective meanings and perspectives of participants rather than through detached measurement. Axiologically, interpretivism acknowledges that the researcher's values, positionality, and reflexivity inevitably influence the research process. This philosophy is particularly suited to studies aiming to explore complex social phenomena, such as political communication, where meanings are negotiated, contested, and embedded in context. In this research, which examines how political parties and journalists in Pakistan use Twitter to construct and disseminate messages within the public sphere, interpretivism provides the flexibility to capture participants' perspectives and the socio-political nuances shaping communication practices.

5.3 Research design and methodology

Aligning with the interpretivist philosophical stance, the study employs an exploratory case study qualitative research methodology design, enabling an in-depth and contextually situated

examination of how political actors engage in strategic narrative construction in Pakistan. Qualitative methods are especially effective for exploring the personal experiences and viewpoints of individuals involved in political communication. According to Creswell and Miller (2000), these methods recognise that participants have their own unique perceptions of reality. This approach allows for a deeper understanding of how people interpret political messages and engage with the communication process. Burrell and Morgan (2019) also believe that the knowledge of reality is a subjective experience, and this is further reinforced by Smith (2024), who considers that reality is subjective. Patton (2014) emphasises that the world is complex and can best be understood through individuals' unique stories and lived experiences within nuanced contexts. This approach helps to avoid the oversimplifications that often arise from generalisations. Similarly, Azungah (2018) highlights the value of a qualitative methodology, which enables researchers to dive deeply into specific settings while remaining open to exploring the social phenomena at hand. Kaid (2004) quotes Laswell to remind scholars of political communication that they should focus on 1) who says, 2) what he says, 3) whom he says, 4) what channel he uses to say that and lastly 5) with what effect he says that. The focus of the present study is on 'who says' by utilising Twitter as a channel and how they say that. 'Who', in the current study, is political parties and journalists in Pakistan.

This study adopts a qualitative case study design to explore the strategic use of Twitter by political parties in Pakistan and the role of media actors in shaping and amplifying political narratives within the digital public sphere. The case study approach is well-suited to investigating contemporary, real-life phenomena within their complex social contexts, particularly when the boundaries between the phenomenon and the context are blurred (Yin, 2009). This design enables a deep, contextualised understanding of how political narratives are strategically framed and disseminated through Twitter in Pakistan, as well as how media actors participate in this process. According to Yin (2009), a case study research design is an

appropriate option when the research focuses on questions of how and why. Yin (2009) and Stake (1995) argue that a case study design is advantageous because it allows researchers to maintain a clear focus, preventing the study from veering into overly broad areas. Baskarada (2014) emphasises that this approach helps to keep the research within the defined scope, while Baxter and Jack (2008) highlight that case studies offer a deep and holistic understanding of the phenomenon being investigated. Overall, these perspectives suggest that case study research can provide both clarity and depth, making it a valuable method for exploring the complex phenomenon of the role of Twitter in shaping political communication in Pakistan, a country with cultural and political complexities and uniqueness.

5.3.1 Data collection methods

For this research, semi-structured interviews serve as the primary data collection method, providing insight into the motivations, strategies, and framing practices of political party representatives and journalists. To further support and contextualise the analysis, Twitter data collected over defined periods is used as a supplementary primary data source, offering concrete examples of message dissemination and public engagement in the digital space in Pakistani politics. The integration of interview data with social media content facilitates a comprehensive understanding of both the strategic intent behind message framing and its public manifestation within the digital public sphere.

5.3.2 Semi-structured interviews

Out of many choices of research data collection tools, semi-structured interviews were selected to collect in-depth data about the strategies of political parties and media representative utilising Twitter for their political activities. This research method was selected because I am interested in the strategies of political communication directly from those who are the main actors or influencers. Journalists and political parties are the primary producers of political

content on Twitter in Pakistan, in terms of political communication. Adeoye-Olatunde and Olenik (2021) consider semi-structured interviews as a good option because they help maintain focus on the issue under investigation while providing freedom to explore the phenomenon in-depth. Gubrium and Holstein (2002) note that the semi-structured interview offers greater flexibility than the structured format, enabling interviewers to probe new topics or rephrase questions in response to the flow of conversation, thus allowing the interview to remain both focused and adaptable. Furthermore, DeJonckheere and Vaughn (2019) demonstrate that semi-structured interviews foster a flexible and dynamic dialogue enabling interviewers to adjust wording, pose follow-up questions, and engage in open-ended conversation with respondents. This flexibility allows researchers to explore participants' thoughts, feelings, and beliefs in-depth while maintaining the flow of interaction. This basis was used to select the approach in preference to other methods. Interviews can yield highly personalised data and provide opportunities for probing (Gray, 2021). Furthermore, utilising interviews allows for the generation of direct information about the research topic at hand that was not available in secondary literature on this or similar topics (Kumar, 2018).

The face-to-face mode of data collection through personal interview has many advantages, such as accurate screening of the participants; checking any possible falsifications by the participants regarding information related to their demography or professional functioning; capturing verbal and non-verbal cues, namely, body language and reactions to specific questions; keeping track of the interview by ensuring the interviewee remains focused; and most importantly, capturing the participants' emotions and behaviours (DeLyser, 2010; Phellas, Bloch and Seale, 2011). In addition, interviews can allow for discussion of people's perceptions and interpretations of a given situation. Here, the researcher's role is to ask the questions that elicit a suitable response from the respondents. Furthermore, it is important that the researcher motivates the respondents to give full and precise replies whilst avoiding any

biases stemming from social desirability, conformity, or other constructs of disinterest. Qualitative researchers usually provide comprehensive descriptions of individuals and events in their natural surroundings, and interviewing has been considered a key factor in a qualitative research design. Kvale and Brinkmann (2009) pointed out that events are not often straightforwardly observable; therefore, conversation with respondents can be one of the most successful tools for accomplishing and investigating research. Moreover, as interviews are interactive, interviewers can elicit additional information that might otherwise not have been shared using other techniques. Hence, interviewing broadens the scope of understanding of the investigated phenomena as it is a more naturalistic and less planned data collection tool. McGrath, Palmgren and Liljedahl (2019) showed that this approach is effective because it allows the researcher significant flexibility to explore any given subject in depth. This approach is particularly suited to the present study, which examines how journalists and politicians utilise Twitter within Pakistan's political communication environment. Given the sensitivity of political discourse, a semi-structured format enabled participants to articulate their experiences in their own words while allowing me to follow up on issues such as framing practices, pressures from political actors, and perceptions of audience engagement that might not have surfaced in a more structured design.

I interviewed three different groups: the first group consisted of social media leaders associated with political parties and politicians from Pakistan, representing the three main parties, PPP, PMLN and PTI. The second group consisted of politicians from PPP, PMLN and PTI, each of which had held a federal government position at least once. The third group interviewed comprised of experienced journalists, each with over ten years of experience in both print and electronic media, to address research question 2. The selection criteria emphasised their active engagement on Twitter, coupled with their wealth of experience. These senior journalists have witnessed the three significant phases of political communication evolution in Pakistan, having

worked with many of the country's leading media groups as well as various international outlets. For the interviews, two interview schedules were drafted, each with seven questions at the initial stage (see Appendix C and D). One schedule was for the politicians and their social media team heads, and the second was for political journalists. Two separate interviews schedules were used because politicians - particularly those who are information secretaries of the political parties - and the social media team leaders have the same purpose and objectives for their presence and political communication on Twitter. In contrast, journalists have their own role on Twitter, which is different from the other two participant groups. Semi-structured interviews help to address all three research questions. Keeping in mind the interpretive nature of this study, this technique helped me to access in-depth data from the interviewee by asking probing questions while keeping the interview within the boundaries of the main topic area. The use of semi-structured interviews was particularly appropriate for this study, as the participants were politicians, media managers and journalists in Pakistan for whom English is a second language. Initially, the research schedules were created in English but recognising that not all participants were equally proficient in the language, an option was offered for them to express their thoughts in Urdu, which many found more comfortable. Ultimately, while one politician, four journalists, and two media managers chose to respond in English, the majority opted for Urdu. This flexibility allowed me to rephrase questions or pose follow-up queries as needed, ensuring that the data collected remained relevant and engaging while respecting the participants' language preferences. Semi-structured interviews also worked well because they provided both interviewee and interviewer with the freedom to shape the interview content (Lune and Berg, 2017). Additionally, politicians and journalists often have limited time to accommodate interviews due to the demanding nature of their jobs. Semi-structured interviews strike the perfect balance between rigour and flexibility, allowing the researcher to gather rich,

in-depth data while staying on track with good time management. This method not only maximised the quality of the insights collected but also kept the process efficient and focused.

5.3.3 Recruitment strategy

The interview population included at least one politician from each of the three selected political parties, two social media team leaders from each party, and ten senior journalists from the mainstream media who were active on Twitter. Only those politicians from the selected political parties who had served as Information Ministers in their respective party regimes were interviewed. These party members are experts in media management due to their roles within their respective parties. Among the journalists, nine were chosen who have more than ten years of experience in political journalism and had witnessed a shift in journalistic patterns due to the emergence of social media, particularly Twitter. In total, from June 2023 to January 2024, interviews were conducted with 17 respondents, detailed in Table’s 5.1.

Identifier	Organization
J1	Anchor, reporter and digital creator with experience working in three leading news media channels in Pakistan
J2	An Islamabad-based multimedia journalist working with a leading online international news organisation has collaborated with four mainstream news channels.
J3	Senior journalist, Rava.pk, worked at ExpressNewsPK, ARY, Geo News English
J4	Senior journalist, Voice of America
J5	A senior journalist, broadcaster, and anchor, working in a leading news media channel, has experience working with both state and private media.
J6	Award-winning Investigative journalist, ex-fellow of The New York Times, alumnus of LSE News
J7	Senior Journalist, Ex-USAToday, The News International, Ex geo News Urdu
J8	Senior journalist, Jang Group, The News, YouTuber
J9	Senior Investigative journalist in a top-ranking news organisation in Pakistan
M1	Former General Manager, Digital Media wing/ social media head
M2	Social media head, Twitter head, Political party
M3	Social media head/ provincial level Political
M4	Senior social media manager
P1	Senator, Government of Pakistan, former federal minister for information and broadcasting, Pakistan Muslim League Nawaz,
P2	Former member of the National Assembly, former federal minister for Information and Broadcasting, former secretary of Information, Pakistan Tehreek-e-Insaaf
P3	Former federal minister for information and broadcasting, former secretary of information, Pakistan People’s Party

P4	Member of the National Assembly, former secretary of information Pakistan people's Party
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Table 5.1 List of interview recruits

5.3.4 Twitter data

In addition to semi-structured interviews, to illustrate political communication via social media in action, three key events were selected for the data extraction from the Twitter API, Appendix I and J. These three events were:

1. On April 10, 2022, former Prime Minister Imran Khan was removed from office. Following this political development, his social media team conducted a Twitter Space event that attracted an unprecedented audience of 446,000 participants, establishing a record for the platform. To analyse the impact of this political upheaval, data spanning April 10th to April 26th, 2022, a period of 15 days, was collected for further examination.
2. The 9th May Riots, as reported by the BBC, highlight a significant conflict between supporters of former Prime Minister Imran Khan and the powerful Pakistani military. The situation unfolded on two main fronts: the streets and social media. Notably, Khan appears to maintain a favourable position in the social media landscape (Mao 2023). For the purposes of this research, data spanning fifteen days related to this incident were collected for analysis.
3. This data analysis examines the framing of political news by mainstream media and journalists on Twitter in relation to the PTI protest outside the Red Zone in Islamabad. The protest involved clashes between PTI supporters and law enforcement, alongside contrasting statements from the government and PTI. The analysis is based on five days of data, from November 25th to November 30th, 2024, sourced from the Twitter accounts of leading journalists.

The analysis of key political events from 2022, 2023, and 2024 in Pakistan is used to highlight the evolving dynamics of political communication on social media platforms, particularly Twitter. Through this analysis, we can better understand the role of social media in shaping political discourse and public perception in Pakistan.

5.4 Research ethics

Ethical approval was a fundamental component of this research investigation. In alignment with guidelines established by University of the West of Scotland (UWS), a participant information sheet was developed. This document clearly articulated the purpose of the research to the interviewees, detailing their consent options and reinforcing that participation was entirely voluntary. It is important to note that this research posed no physical risk to the participants, who were assured that their contributions would be utilised solely for the analysis and would remain anonymous.

A separate consent form was crafted and distributed to all participants during the initial communication phase, alongside the information sheet. I made it a priority to remain available for any further questions or clarifications participants might have had. Notably, the communication process did not rely on email. Instead, access to politicians and social media managers was facilitated through public relations officers (PROs), a routine practice in Pakistani media and political circles. Political parties and individual politicians typically appoint PROs to manage communication, and their contact details are circulated within professional networks of journalists and party workers. This reflects what Lilleker (2003) terms the “gatekeeper” role in elite interviewing, where access often depends on trusted intermediaries. My previous professional experience as a journalist and existing professional networks supported this process, aligning with approaches identified in the literature on recruiting high-profile participants (Harvey, 2011). In the case of journalists, access was facilitated through existing professional networks established during my career in media. This

reflects what Mikecz (2012) describes as a common strategy in elite interviewing, where trust and familiarity within professional circles enable access to otherwise hard-to-reach participants. In practice, I contacted journalists directly through professional channels and, in some cases, through referrals from other colleagues, which aligns with snowball sampling approaches commonly used in qualitative research (Noy, 2008). While these prior connections aided recruitment, I ensured that all interactions were conducted in accordance with ethical research protocols, including informed consent, confidentiality, and clear boundaries between my professional background and my role as a researcher. Scheduling interviews proved challenging due to their demanding work routines, characterised by unpredictable schedules. Consequently, interview timings frequently had to be adjusted, necessitating patience on my part. I remained conscious of their professional commitments, ensuring not to pressurise them unduly for interviews. For example, a senior politician who initially agreed to an interview became preoccupied with his political campaign considering the impending General Elections. After reaching out again two days later for his availability, he swiftly responded, inviting me to his office within an hour for the interview. This meeting proved highly productive, yielding rich data and insights from his extensive political experience spanning decades.

The information sheet and consent form were provided during the second stage of communication, following the initial messages I sent to participants about my identity and purpose for contacting them. Following this, the time and date for the interview were confirmed upon their approval. All interview data was securely stored on my password-protected laptop, UWS cloud storage, and OneDrive, with access restricted solely to me and my supervision team. Further, the participants were given assurances over privacy and confidentiality, as all the interviews were anonymised. This allowed them to speak freely and to provide significant examples and information. I coded the interview transcripts with numbers and letters. For journalists, participants are identified as J1 to J9. For political leaders it is P1 to P4 and for

media managers it is M1 to M5. In the research planning phase, particular consideration was given to ensure that no questions were included that could potentially offend or discomfort participants. This research received approval from the School Ethics Committee of UWS within the School of Business and Creative Industries, approval number 16721.

5.5 Data analysis: thematic coding

Thematic coding of the data collected from interviews was conducted. To analyse the interview data, I used NVivo. To do so, I followed an analytical approach endorsed by Braun and Clarke (2013). According to Braun and Clark, codes are the aspects of your data which answer your question and help you meet the objectives of your study. I followed the stages of thematic coding analysis one by one, starting with translations and transcription of the data, which helped me familiarise myself with the data. After completing all the transcriptions, interview data was transferred to NVivo under three categories: politicians, media managers, and journalists. I read the whole data set again to familiarise myself with it before starting with coding. This enabled me to proceed confidently with the next step. For the second phase of coding analysis, some of the codes were already apparent from the data, and I started thinking and writing about the word choices to name those codes. Then, I coded the data using a blend of a comprehensive coding approach, known as open coding and selective coding, which means I examined the entire dataset. Open coding involves examining the dataset in detail and breaking it down into discrete parts, closely scrutinising them for similarities and differences, and assigning conceptual labels (Strauss and Corbin, 1998). This process generated initial categories that remain close to the data and ensured that no significant themes were overlooked (Charmaz, 2006). Selective coding then allows the researcher to refine and integrate these categories around central, theoretically significant themes, thereby linking the data to broader conceptual insights (Corbin and Strauss, 2008). Employing both stages provided a balance between inductive exploration and analytical focus, ensuring the dataset was examined

comprehensively while maintaining coherence in theme development (Birks and Mills, 2022). While coding the documents, I was continuously analysing the data in terms of considering every new piece of information and making decisions as to whether it should go into the existing code or a new code should be generated. In the second coding cycle, I utilised the same strategy but also re-examined the codes created earlier. In the first phase of coding, there were some cases where codes were overlapping, and they were brought together into broader codes during the second phase. For example, in the initial coding process, codes for “strategic use of Twitter by PTI” and “strategic use of Twitter by PMLN” were identified. Both codes referred to the strategic use of Twitter, but by different political parties. At the second stage, I integrated these codes into one called “strategic use of Twitter by political parties”. This approach allowed me to organise the data into larger groups by identifying basic themes. I then created a smaller number of larger thematic issues that served as organising themes or sub-themes. Both Hesse-Biber (2010) and Medelyan (2019) suggest that either deductive or inductive coding can be used. Deductive coding starts with predetermined themes and categories, often generated from the literature review. This approach is effective, as it helps to guide the research process, and a researcher is limited to a given category. Inductive coding develops themes from the data collected. The inductive approach is iterative, and the researcher is expected to break down and analyse codes several times as they go over the data collected. Deductive codes were driven by theory, stemming from the literature review in Chapters 2 and 3 and the theoretical framework in Chapter 4. Inductive codes were not defined in advance but were driven by insights from the empirical data.

Overall, designing the coding frame involved several iterative stages. This allowed me to revisit and refine existing codes, as well as add new ones as they emerged. This was done to produce a methodical and robust analysis (Boyatzis, 1998), and to gain an understanding of the issues, perceptions, and significance of the experiences of journalists, politicians, and media managers.

A visualisation of the entire framing process is presented in Figure 5.2. Initially, 37 codes were generated during the first phase of analysis by using NVivo. During the second phase, some of the codes were linked with the other codes, therefore, they were organised as sub-codes under broader categories. For example, the interdependence of mainstream media and Twitter was categorised as a key code, as was the main code of mainstream media adopting Twitter.

Figure 5.2 A visual presentation of thematic coding analysis (self-contribution)

The power of mainstream media and Twitter as the primary source of news was also categorised as a key code under this main code. The total principal codes remaining were 20, which were further condensed into four overarching themes, which will be presented in the subsequent findings chapters.

5.6 Twitter data analysis

To complement the data collected through semi-structured interviews, data from Twitter was extracted to provide examples and complement the themes identified during the data coding process. Chen, Duan and Yang (2022) and Deacon *et al.* (2021) emphasise that materials posted by a public account on a public social media platform such as Twitter are acceptable research material, as unlike messages posted on closed platforms, such as WhatsApp or Snapchat, because they are publicly accessible material. After completing NVivo coding and finalising the themes that addressed the research questions, supplementary Twitter data were collected through the Twitter API to examine three key political events that generated heightened online activity (Appendix I and J). Across interviews, journalists, media managers, and politicians consistently observed that PTI was the most successful party in its use of social media. To explore this further, two events were selected for analysis: first, the ousting of former Prime Minister Imran Khan, and second, the 9 May riots following his arrest. For each event, fifteen days of Twitter data were collected, focusing on posts from the official accounts of leaders of PTI, PPP, and PMLN. For example, in the case of Imran Khan's ousting, posts from all three parties were compared to examine how they framed political messages around the event. These were then read alongside the interview findings to demonstrate how competing narratives complemented the theme of framing that had emerged from the qualitative analysis of the interview data.

Similarly, to explore the themes of bias and framing within mainstream media and journalism, posts from the most-followed journalists including Imran Riaz Khan, Talat Hussain, Asma Shirazi, Rauf Klasra, Umar Cheema, and Iqrar-ul-Hassan were examined. To capture the role of mainstream media and journalists in moments of heightened political tension, one further case was selected: PTI's "final call" protest at D-Chowk, Islamabad, where government forces dispersed demonstrators in the Red Zone. Data for this case were collected over a five-day period (25–29 November 2024). The posts from political leaders, journalists, and mainstream

media outlets were then reviewed comparatively against the interview themes to illustrate how the practices described by participants were enacted in real-time political communication on Twitter.

These posts often included links to their television programmes or organisational content, allowing comparison between their personal commentary on Twitter and the narratives promoted through their affiliated media outlets. In addition to the existing biases of journalists towards political parties, this provided further evidence of how journalists and news organisations actively shape political communication and how their practices align with or diverge from the perspectives shared in interviews.

Rather than applying a formal content analysis, which requires a systematic coding protocol and quantitative measurement of categories (Franzosi, 2008), the posts were examined thematically in relation to the interview findings. Following qualitative guidance that allows documents and online materials to be used illustratively to support or contrast with themes (Bryman, 2016; Silverman, 2024; Lomborg, 2011), the dataset was manually searched for posts that complemented, expanded, or challenged themes such as mobilisation strategies, framing of political actors, defence of party positions, or the role of journalists in shaping political narratives. Tweets in Urdu were translated into English, and images with embedded Urdu text were also described in English to ensure consistency in interpretation.

Figure 5.3 Visual representation of stages of framing analysis (self-contribution)

This dual strategy of examining both interviews and Twitter posts provided a form of triangulation, allowing the study to cross-check self-reported accounts with observable communication practices during key political events, thereby enhancing the validity and richness of the findings.

5.7 Researcher positionality

I am from Pakistan and have been a journalist for 15 years. I have worked with the state media and currently hold a position in the Department of the Ministry of Information and Broadcasting, Pakistan, as a journalist. I expect to continue working there after completing my PhD degree. I have reported on the three main political parties in my tenure as a journalist. As a journalist, I knew the parties' media managers and politicians who had served as Federal Information Ministers, which allowed me to secure privileged access to them. As a trained journalist, I also strive for objectivity in my work, and in this research, I sought to maintain neutrality. However, I had the advantage of gaining excellent firsthand insights into, and access to, political party representatives, senior journalists, and Social Media Team Managers (SMTS)

working with the political parties, which contributes to making this research unique. This is one of the main reasons for selecting interviews as the primary data collection technique. Those with less access to politicians and journalists are often forced to analyse data available on social media platforms in the form of posts. If I were not a journalist, I might not have had such good access to senior politicians and fellow journalists. I have also spent many years conducting interviews with senior public figures and politicians, which gave me confidence and expertise to conduct semi-structured interviews. In addition, the respondents were more comfortable and open with me, given my role as a journalist, whereas they may have been more cautious with an external researcher. Had I not been an employee and had this level of access as an insider, I would not have been able to do this research, or at least, I would have been unable to recruit the number of elite respondents. Insider status may provide deeper access and nuanced understanding, while outsider perspectives can enable critical distance; many scholars therefore recognise the existence of fluid positionalities that move between insider and outsider perspectives rather than fixed categories (Saime, Hashim and Mumin, 2025). Reflexive approaches highlight how researchers' identities, as shaped by profession, culture, or prior experience, both enable and constrain knowledge production (Bukamal, 2022). To manage these dynamics, strategies such as bracketing and reflexivity are recommended, allowing researchers to acknowledge but also critically interrogate their assumptions (Berkovic, 2023). Rather than undermining objectivity, such situated knowledge can strengthen the research by offering epistemic advantages when combined with reflexive practice (Harding, 1995). My commitment to journalism ethics, particularly the pursuit of objectivity, empowered me to conduct my research independently. As a researcher, I was encouraged to critically examine what the participants said and how it could be interpreted. Thus, I believe that my analysis is a critical examination of what is happening, as the research has included voices from all political parties, their social media teams and senior journalists.

Reflexivity in this study involved ongoing critical reflection on how the researcher's professional background, institutional position, and long-standing relationships within journalism and political communication could shape data collection and interpretation. While insider status facilitated access and openness, it also required conscious effort to avoid normalising professional assumptions or accepting elite accounts at face value. Throughout the research process, reflexivity was practiced by systematically questioning interpretations, comparing perspectives across political parties and journalists, and grounding analytical claims in empirical data rather than professional familiarity. In this way, reflexivity functioned as a methodological practice that both acknowledged positional influence and mitigated its potential constraints on critical analysis.

To further manage the influence of insider positionality, methodological triangulation was employed through the use of multiple data sources, including semi-structured interviews and Twitter data. Open coding was used in the initial phase of analysis to allow themes to emerge inductively from the data rather than being imposed a priori, reducing the risk of privileging professional assumptions. The use of Twitter content as a supplementary data source also enabled cross-checking of interview accounts against observable communication practices, strengthening analytical rigour and transparency.

5.8 Validity and reliability

The validity of data refers to the degree to which the data collected for the study accurately measure what the study intends to measure, and it relates to the ability of the thesis to examine what it intends to research (Bryman and Bell, 2015). In studies, validity refers to the plan and method of the study, including data collection methods, to ensure that the study accurately represents the outcomes for which it was designed. To ensure the validity and reliability of the research, multiple strategies were employed. Semi-structured interviews were selected as they

allow participants to articulate their views in depth while giving the researcher flexibility to probe for clarification, thereby enhancing the richness and credibility of the data (Kvale and Brinkmann, 2009). Conducting interviews in Urdu, the participants' native language, strengthened validity by allowing them to express complex ideas more naturally and reducing the risk of misinterpretation due to linguistic barriers (Temple and Young, 2004). Reliability was addressed through careful transcription and translation procedures, with attention to semantic accuracy to preserve meaning across languages (Van Nes *et al.*, 2010). To ensure the utmost accuracy of their meaning in both English and Urdu, I used the back-translation technique, which involves translating the target language back to the original source. Chen and Boore (2010) highlight that back-translation is a valuable strategy in both comparative and operational research. They emphasise that translation extends beyond words to encompass cultural meanings, noting that researchers must strive to produce a version that mirrors the original in both structure and format, while also remaining sensitive to the cultural nuances embedded in language use (p., 235). In addition, triangulation was achieved by combining interview data with content collected from the social media platform Twitter, which provides a separate but complementary dataset, thereby enhancing the robustness of findings (Denzin, 2012). The use of social media posts from Twitter as data presents inherent challenges to validity and reliability. Issues such as the authenticity of user accounts, representativeness of online discourse, and the brevity or ambiguity of posts can limit the credibility of findings (Bruns and Burgess, 2015). Furthermore, the dynamic nature of platforms where content can be deleted, altered, or taken out of context raises concerns about reliability over time (Lomborg, 2011). To mitigate these challenges, data collection procedures were clearly defined and consistently applied, ensuring replicability of the dataset. Only posts from verified accounts of journalists and political actors were included, strengthening validity by reducing risks associated with anonymity and bots (Marwick, 2018). Contextual analysis was also employed,

reading posts in relation to surrounding interactions and broader political events to avoid misinterpretation (Highfield and Leaver, 2016). By combining social media data with interview evidence, the study used triangulation to enhance robustness and address potential biases in any single source (Denzin, 2012). Reflexive practices, including continuous engagement with positionality and potential biases, further supported the trustworthiness of the analysis (Lincoln and Guba, 1988). These steps were taken to ensure that the meaning remained consistent and that participants would not be confused about the exact meaning of the questions.

5.9 Trustworthiness

To further strengthen the quality of this research, the criteria of trustworthiness were applied, encompassing credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability (Lincoln and Guba, 1988). Credibility was enhanced through triangulation of data sources, combining semi-structured interviews with social media content, and through conducting interviews in Urdu, which enabled participants to express themselves in their native language (Temple and Young, 2004). Transferability was supported by providing rich, thick descriptions of the context, participants, and data, allowing readers to assess the applicability of the findings to other settings (Shenton, 2004). Dependability was addressed by maintaining an explicit audit trail of coding decisions and analytic processes, ensuring transparency and replicability (Nowell *et al.*, 2017). Finally, confirmability was achieved through reflexivity, including critical reflection on positionality and potential biases, to ensure that findings were grounded in the data rather than researcher assumptions (Berger, 2015).

5.10 Conclusion

In conclusion, this chapter has laid the groundwork for a nuanced exploration of political communication in Pakistan, focusing on the strategic use of Twitter by political parties and media actors. By employing an interpretivist research philosophy framed within the broader

context of framing theory and the transformation of the public sphere, the study aims to uncover the complexities of how political narratives are constructed and disseminated. The qualitative methodology, inclusive of semi-structured interviews and focused content analysis, enables an in-depth understanding of the perspectives of key stakeholders involved in political discourse. As political parties adapt their strategies in response to the evolving media landscape in Pakistan, understanding the dynamics of framing within this digital environment becomes increasingly vital. This foundational knowledge not only serves to inform the subsequent presentation of findings and analysis but also offers valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities that lie ahead for political communication and public discourse in the country. In the next two chapters, I present my findings, outlining the interplay between political communication and the public sphere, providing a comprehensive view of how narratives are crafted and contested in contemporary Pakistan. Ultimately, this research aims to contribute to a more robust framework for understanding the intersections between media, politics, and society in Pakistan's unique context.

Chapter 6: Twitter, Political Parties and Campaign Strategies

6.1 Introduction

As discussed in the preceding chapter, a thematic coding approach was applied to evaluate and understand the role of Twitter in shaping political communication in Pakistan. In this chapter, I present two main themes identified through the analysis of interview data related to the strategic use of Twitter by political parties in Pakistan. The first theme concerns the presence of an elite public on Twitter, including politicians, journalists, and politically engaged citizens, which contributes to the formation of a distinct Twitter ‘sphere’. The second theme focuses on the strategic use of Twitter by political parties in Pakistan. I present findings on the strategic use of Twitter by political parties in Pakistan, including the use of social media teams, the mechanism of content creation, and strategically using social media to reach a wider public for narrative building. The chapter is divided into three parts. First, I outline the presence of an elite political circle that influences public opinion on Twitter in Pakistan. Second, I draw attention to the strategic use of Twitter, including the mechanisms used for building networks, generating content, framing information, utilising content and networking for running political campaigns. Finally, I discuss the importance of the connections forged between social media-driven online campaigns and offline political mobilisation.

6.2 Primary actors in Pakistan’s Twittersphere

In this section, I highlight the presence of an elite circle utilising Twitter for political purposes in Pakistan. I demonstrate that the leading political power brokers in Pakistan have a significant presence on Twitter and utilise access to that audience to advance their political agendas. Drawing on interview data, I illustrate the presence of political parties, young people, overseas Pakistanis, and of the political elite on Twitter in Pakistan. Table 6.1 illustrates how the main themes were generated with illustrative excerpts from interview transcripts.

Main Theme	Description of the theme	Codes	Illustrative excerpts
Primary actors in Pakistan's Twittersphere	The theme examines the presence of opinion makers, including political powers such as military leadership, political parties, and the Pakistani diaspora, on Twitter, making it an elite sphere that influences public opinion.	Presence of political parties	"Twitter has become a very powerful political tool for communication in Pakistan recently. And you know, all the major political parties have their Twitter presence and their leadership is also on Twitter" (J7).
		Presence of opinion makers on Twitter	"It is connected with the opinion maker of Pakistan, you know, in Pakistan. Opinion makers, top political leaders, top civil servants, and top military leaders all monitor Twitter, although not all 240 million users are on the platform."(P1)
		Presence of young people on social media	"It's mostly young people and obviously they want to interact it's very interactive there's a lot of feedback" (P4).
		Presence of overseas Pakistanis on Twitter	"During the removal of Imran Khan, PTI used Twitter very effectively. Despite the sanctions and political troubles they were facing, the expatriates, Pakistanis living abroad, played a significant role" (J1)

Table 6.1 Sequence of thematic generation from the interview data (self-contribution)

The study findings show that the leaders of all the prominent political parties, including the PTI, PPP, PMLN, Jamat-e-Islami (JI), Tehreek-e-Labbaik Pakistan (TLP), and the military establishment have adopted Twitter to enhance their political presence. For example, J1, a prominent journalist, has been working as a reporter and anchor since 2007 for major TV news channels in Pakistan, suggested that:

In 2023, we see that Twitter plays a very significant role. Whether it's a tweet from Imran Khan, the Prime Minister, the Information Minister, ISPR, Bilawal Bhutto

Zardari, or even Maulana Fazlur Rehman, everyone is on Twitter. Every political party posts their updates on Twitter.

There is significant evidence that Twitter is now an important and popular space for the dissemination of information and running political campaigns for prominent Pakistani politicians. As illustrated in Table 6.2, prominent political leaders and official party accounts have a presence on Twitter, where they disseminate official statements, reactions, and updates. This confirms Batool et al.'s (2022) findings that Pakistani politicians effectively utilised the platform for the first time to share information and engage voters during the 2013 General Elections.

Political leader	Political Party	Joining date on Twitter	Followers as of October 2024
Imran Khan	PTI	March 2010	20.9 million
Maryam Nawaz	PMLN	January 2012	8.1 million
Bilawal Bhutto	PPPP	July 2011	5.1 million
Mian Shehbaz Sharif	PMLN	April 2010	6.7 million
Mian Nawaz Sharif	PMLN	September 2020	1.1 million
Aseefa B Zardari	PPPP	April 2010	2.8 million
Ch Fawad Chaudhry	PTI	February 2010	6.7 million

Table 6.2 Data from Twitter accounts of political leaders, June 2025

According to Batool et al., a significant reason for the exponential growth of online information sharing was the threat of terrorism in the country. In addition to the individual accounts of political leaders, all prominent political parties have official Twitter accounts. Table 6.3 indicates the presence and following of these accounts.

Political Party	Joining date on Twitter	Followers as of October 2024
PTI official	March 2010	10.2 million
Insaf PK	December 2010	3.5 million
PPPP Media Cell	January 2013	1.1 million
PMLN	Feb 2012	2.5 million
PMLN media cell	December 2011	316.4k
PPP	Feb 2013	331.8K

Table 6.3 Official accounts of main political parties on Twitter as of July 2025

As evident from Table 6.2, Imran Khan joined Twitter in March 2010, Maryam Nawaz (PMLN) in 2012, Bilawal Bhutto, chairman of the Pakistan People's Party, in July 2011, and

PMLN chairman Nawaz Sharif in September 2020. What is evident from Tables 6.2 and 6.3 is that PTI leader Imran Khan was an early adopter of Twitter, and others quickly followed his lead, including those who were initially viewed as less social media savvy. As M1, social media lead and former General Manager of the Digital Media wing of a prominent political party, highlighted, “all political parties started utilising Twitter for political purposes four to five years after PTI”. He quoted Imran Khan, lauding the efforts of his social media team, and said that “PTI had millions of followers on social media when other political parties began to join”.

As highlighted by Ahmed and Skoric (2013), only once the success of PTI on this platform was evident after the 2013 General Elections, did politicians from other political parties follow in PTI’s footsteps and recognise the value of Twitter for their political campaigns and information dissemination. J8, a prominent journalist in the Pakistan news media industry, linked with news media since 1999, who has worked with leading media groups like The News and Geo English, highlighted that the other political parties were almost forced to join Twitter following the success of Imran Khan and his party’s presence on Twitter:

After Imran Khan, we saw Bilawal Bhutto, Maryam Nawaz, Nawaz Sharif, and Asif Ali Zardari. Nawaz Sharif and Asif Ali Zardari are old-school politicians. Maryam Nawaz and Bilawal are relatively young, so they adopted Twitter. However, even the old-school politicians had to join Twitter.

In terms of official political accounts on Twitter, Table 6.3 shows that PTI was the first political party in Pakistan to have an official page on Twitter, having been on the platform under the name Insaf.pk since 2009, before launching its official page in 2010. The PTI leader, Imran Khan’s, Twitter account was created in the same year. Other political party leaders, such as Mian Shahbaz Sharif, the former president of PMLN, also joined in the same year. However, their account did not attract the same number of followers as Imran Khan’s, as indicated by

M1's remarks. Other politicians started utilising Twitter four to five years after Imran Khan, despite creating accounts on the platform. Second-generation politicians also joined during the 2011-2013 period, but they similarly failed to attract the same number of followers as Imran Khan. Interviewees confirmed that the reason for the success of PTI on Twitter was its early adopter advantage, gained through active engagement with the platform's possibilities well before other political parties recognised its value.

Journalists, politicians, and social media heads agreed that political parties were motivated by the success of Imran Khan's experience. J2, who has been working in news media with main television news channels in Pakistan since 2007, highlighted the presence of the "second-tier leadership" of political parties also tweeting, commenting, and quoting tweets to enhance their profiles and public presence, influenced by the success of PTI in narrative building on Twitter. P3, a prominent political leader and former Federal Information Minister, expressed that, "I think the change took place with the increased activism and popularity of the PTI and they were the ones who really use that very effectively to promote and propagate their party and their party leadership especially on political communication and then a lot of their leaders developed large following". He was also of the view that PTI were the first to start it and they have still a better organised propaganda machine on Twitter, "It's very organised, they are good at setting trends and trolling".

P1, a former Federal Minister and Information Secretary of one of the main political parties, gave an example of how Twitter challenged the monopoly of mainstream news media against Imran Khan during the recent General Elections, "the way 8th February(2024) elections were held have proved how effective is social media and Twitter in terms of narrative setting and in terms of rebutting the negative propaganda against the political party and political leadership". The findings, however, also indicate that not all political parties have adopted and utilised Twitter in the same way, and with the same approach. For instance, the Information Secretary

and Provincial Minister for Information of a political party suggested that, “PTI is using Twitter as a war room. PPP never had a frenzy around Twitter use”. She further stated that PPP considers Twitter an important platform but uses it primarily for defensive purposes, to counteract negative propaganda. Under Twitter's new policy, which requires payment for verified accounts, political parties in Pakistan are paying fees to maintain verified status, ensuring the credibility and trustworthiness of their accounts. J2, for instance, said, “Being verified not only bolsters their connection with the public but also protects them from the dangers of disinformation. Without that verification, unverified accounts can easily impersonate them, spreading false information that can tarnish their reputation”. Therefore, maintaining a verified presence on Twitter is crucial for political parties to communicate with their constituencies and safeguard their integrity effectively. This establishes the importance political figure give to Twitter for their presence and indicates their consciousness about the reach of the platform to their potential voters.

The military establishment is considered a main political power in Pakistani politics (Siddiq, 2017). Apart from the political parties, J8 highlighted the active use of Twitter by the military establishment for disseminating information. He pointed out a specific Twitter post from the official account of the Inter-Services Public Relations (ISPR), media and publication wing of the armed forces in Pakistan that rejected a controversial leak by the Pakistani News media group Dawn, reporting on a closed meeting of military officials that was not meant for media coverage. Additionally, J8 mentioned another ISPR post that addressed accusations from the PTI, claiming that the military was conspiring against former Prime Minister Imran Khan to facilitate his removal from power. J8 emphasised the effectiveness of Twitter as a platform for the military establishment to communicate and respond to such accusations, “You might remember the famous tweet from ISPR saying 'Report Rejected' about the Dawn Leaks report. “It created a substantial political narrative.” He also referenced the recent tweet from the ISPR

in light of the political situation that unfolded during and after the ousting of former Prime Minister Imran Khan. During this time, posts from Imran Khan and the official PTI account alleged the involvement of the military establishment in his removal. In response, “ISPR tweeted, 'We are neutral.'” This statement sparked significant discussion about the role of the military in political matters according to J8.

In addition to the presence of political parties and the military establishment on Twitter, interviewees also suggested that the urban elites are also a major part of the Twittersphere in Pakistan. Ashfaq and Roofi (2023) argue that political culture in Pakistan is dominated by multiple elites and they influence voter behaviours and choices. Interview findings suggest that Twitter is important from a political communication perspective because of the presence of Pakistan’s urban elites on the platform. Khan et al. (2018) identified nine types of elites in Pakistan, including military elites, landlord elites, bureaucratic elites, religious elites, industrial elites, judicial elites, dynamic elites, taxing elites, and media elites. The findings of this study suggest that it is not a matter of “how many” people are on Twitter, but rather “who is on Twitter” in Pakistan, as highlighted by P3.

The majority of Pakistan is not on Twitter, voters are not on Twitter. So this is basically to influence the opinion makers so that they can formulate, maybe sometimes spread messages. Also, the impact is limited, but it is an influential section of Pakistanis who make and shape public opinion, and that is important.

Interviewees indicated that the politically educated elite in Pakistan often control the narrative, shaping and influencing public opinion. For example, J8 commented that “Twitter trends significantly influence the educated urban elite in Pakistan.” J3, an award-winning multimedia journalist and content editor, currently working with prominent media group in Pakistan argued

that “PTI’s strategy was well-received, especially by the middle class, which is the opinion-making class in Pakistan.”

J7, a former Chevening and Fulbright fellow, working as head of news with a prominent mainstream news media channel, also suggested that while Twitter is not the most popular medium in Pakistan, it is the medium of the educated class in the country. This is important, because it is this class who can convince or influence others, share and convey their thoughts to those less educated than themselves. P3, a prominent, political leader, former Minister for Information and Broadcasting, and sitting Senator, suggested that:

It (Twitter) is connected with the opinion makers of Pakistan, you know. The opinion makers, the top political leaders, the top civil bureaucracy, the top military leadership, everybody monitors Twitter, although not the two hundred and forty million people are on Twitter.

These findings suggest that even those political parties that clearly understand that their voter population is not on Twitter still consider it an effective platform. For instance, M3, the social media lead from one of the political parties, said that his party’s target audience is primarily from poorer areas and is less likely to be on Twitter. However, he still considered the platform to be an essential vehicle for political communication because of the presence of influential urban elites on it. He expressed the view that his party utilises Twitter to generate narratives and engage with those who are active there, including journalists and influencers. Politicians from the PMLN, PPP, and PTI confirmed that Twitter is most the useful platform for political parties and politicians to influence opinion makers, who then disseminate messages in other ways. P2, a senior politician, explained that there is a parallel between Twitter and English newspapers in Pakistan, stating that, “just like English newspapers in our country, they didn’t have a large readership but were opinion-making newspapers for the opinion-making class.

Twitter is also a platform of opinion makers in Pakistan”. In a country where the national language is Urdu and people speak many regional languages, the literacy rate is also low. English newspapers like Dawn, The News, Express Tribune and The Nation continue to enjoy the status of a credible news source for a small yet influential segment of the population.

According to the Election Commission of Pakistan, 34% of voters in the 2013 General Elections were under the age of 31 (Yousaf, 2016). One of the most significant factors for politicians and political parties in choosing to use Twitter as a political communication tool is the presence of educated young people on it. Interviewees confirmed that targeting the young audience on Twitter was a crucial factor in determining the likely success of a political party. Those who could connect best with young people were thought to be more effective in building and projecting their political narratives. For example, as indicated by Ahmad and Anwar (2018), young people comprise a significant percentage of voters in Pakistan and PTI was the first to focus its online social media campaigns on targeting these voters, which contributed to electoral success in the KPK province. PTI, the first major political party on Twitter, was very successful at targeting young people, while other parties were relying on outdated legacy media political strategies. Findings also suggest that PTI developed a strong base on Twitter by attracting tech-savvy young people. According to J1, “other political parties couldn't be as effective because they didn't have the grassroots youth support that PTI had.”

However, while most interviewees felt that PTI was the first and most effective party on Twitter, J3 expressed the view that young people felt disappointed and let down at certain points during the PTI government’s regime due to its incompetence. Yet, other journalists like the senior journalist (J5) who hosts a prime-time current affairs show, considered PTI as the most organised party in terms of their interactions with, and involvement of, young people. He considered it a significant factor behind PTI’s success on social media. He expressed the view that “most of them (young voters) are available or connected to social media. Most of them are

digital generation blogs”. Social media leads (M1, M2) also confirmed the focus of PTI’s campaign on Twitter to reach young people. They claimed that PTI had the support of young people, comprising 65% of the country’s population, indicating that “their (youth) tech-savviness and social media presence naturally make PTI’s presence the strongest compared to others.” Furthermore, M2 claimed that “The PTI is a party of youth. So youth is the target.”

While reaching young people via mainstream media has become more difficult due to the state restrictions as indicated by Khan (2024), in Pakistan, the regulatory framework for broadcast media particularly under the PEMRA Ordinance and its subsequent amendments has frequently been criticised for enabling state control and limiting political expression in mainstream media. Twitter (and other social channels) has provided an effective means for political parties in Pakistan to access them directly. Young people are always available on social media to receive political messages and circulate them among their own circles of family and friends. As discussed in previous chapters, social media platforms are invariably quick and easy to use and, crucially, tend not to involve an intermediary reinterpreting the intended message. P4, a senior politician, member of the National Assembly and former Information Secretary of a prominent political party, noted that PPP’s party leadership joined Twitter almost at the same point as PTI, but were not actively utilising it, limiting their ability to secure the same attention. This failure to be there early enough is important because the young audience is growing in Pakistan, and it is technologically sophisticated. This generation is well versed in contributing to two-way conversations online and so also represents a means of generating significant feedback to assess the efficacy of projected narratives.

Qaisrani (2022) suggests that the Pakistani state makes strong efforts to involve the Pakistani diaspora in politics and economic activities, aware of the fact that five per cent of the country’s population is living abroad, and Pakistan has the sixth largest diaspora in the world. Overseas Pakistanis are therefore an important target audience for political parties in Pakistan. Findings

suggest that overseas Pakistanis were the target audience for political parties on Twitter. Overseas Pakistanis, who are technologically skilled and emotionally connected to their homeland, play a crucial role in shaping the narrative for political parties at the international level. Several interviewees suggested that overseas Pakistanis play an essential role in the narrative building about Pakistani political parties. For example, J1, emphasised how these people became an asset for the party which was facing sanctions within the country. He claimed that:

During the removal of Imran Khan, PTI used Twitter very effectively. Despite the sanctions and political troubles, they were facing, the expatriates, Pakistanis living abroad, played a significant role. Even now, people like Hammad Azhar and Shahbaz Gill, who are fugitives, are playing their roles from abroad to align with the political party's agenda, despite Imran Khan and the main leadership being in jail.

Shahbaz Gill, former PTI advisor to Prime Minister on political communication has millions of followers on Twitter and is based in US. Sayed Z Bukhari, former PTI Minister for overseas Pakistani is an entrepreneur based in London, UK. Mirza Shahzad Akbar, former PTI Minister for accountability is a lawyer based in London and the social media head for PTI, Jibran Ilyas, is Director of Incident Response for leading Cyber security firm and is an adjunct professor at Northwestern University (USA). Considering J1's claim that these figures appear on social media platforms to establish the core party narrative, it is evident that these overseas Pakistanis are playing a key role. In addition, as highlighted by Mustafa and Sawas (2013), in Pakistan, the diaspora plays an important role in the formation of political discourse. The study findings indicate that beyond the patronage networks at constituency level politics, the diaspora is one of the most important players in political discourse formation at the national level. For example, PTI utilised Twitter effectively to coordinate with overseas Pakistanis. As P4 indicated "They (PTI) have actually a lot of overseas following, they have greater access of technology and

knowledge around that”. Twitter posts from PTI political leaders also support the interview findings. For instance, former Federal Minister for Information and Broadcasting in PTI, Fawad Hussain reposted on Twitter that Chairman PTI Imran Khan will hold a Zoom call with the ten most influential overseas Pakistanis Hussain (2024). The date of the meeting was also announced in the post, and it was revealed that the meeting would be hosted by the advisor to PTI on overseas affairs and focal person for Imran Khan in the USA. The post suggests that advisors and spokespersons for overseas Pakistanis are also hired by political parties, in addition to the state as well.

Findings also reveal that the social media experts working with PTI were overseas Pakistanis, in most cases. As one of the respondents, M1 highlighted:

It's essential to note that the PTI core team consisted of two to three individuals based in Pakistan, specifically in Islamabad. Additionally, there were around eight to ten other members who were actively working day and night on this project, most of whom were based overseas. One member, for instance, was based in Holland, another in Australia, one in New York, and another in Canada.

This section has shown that Twitter in Pakistan operates as an elite sphere, where political leaders, journalists, and politically engaged citizens interact to shape political discourse. Having established the character of this Twitter sphere, the next section examines the strategies political parties adopt to construct and disseminate their messages to achieve political communication goals.

6.3 Message construction and dissemination structures in political parties

Under the main theme, Strategic Use of Twitter by political parties, in this section, first, I present findings on the methods of narrative development (construction), the deployment of

social media teams and research cells, and their financing by the political parties in Pakistan followed by organisational content dissemination mechanisms of political information via Twitter. Then I will demonstrate elements of framing in the messages of all three political parties. Table 6.4 outlines the key themes and their development with illustrative excerpts from interview data.

Main theme	Description of the theme	Codes	Excerpts
Strategic use of Twitter by political parties in Pakistan	This theme examines how political parties strategically use Twitter by hiring social media experts, crafting and framing targeted messages, and disseminating them to influence public opinion. It also examines the connection between online campaigns and offline political engagement.	Hiring social media teams, recruiting social media experts for Twitter	“PTI’s social media team, led by individuals like Jibran, played a crucial role in crafting and disseminating the narrative during the crisis”(M1).
		Message construction mechanisms in political parties	“Sometimes, Imran Khan himself would suggest points to highlight, and our team would lead these efforts. We had groups and teams segmented by areas, each handling different aspects of the narrative, like graphics and videos.”(M1)
		Dissemination of content messages	“They have social media teams, WhatsApp groups, and party connections. Each party has special groups in every city and area that transmit messages from one platform to another” (J1)
		Framing of the messages	“We had to create specific content based on various trends, including anti-American sentiments. (M1) Specific campaigns are backed by research, videos, banners, and animations. Themes and colours are carefully selected to convey the intended message, whether to depict strength, victimhood, or historical events.”(J1)

		Connecting online media campaigns to the offline public sphere	They used Twitter essentially to convey the message that Imran Khan is in distress and has been kept in custody. So come out and protest. (J5)
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Table 6.4 Description of the codes under the central theme (self-contribution)

6.3.1 The role of social media teams

Interview data revealed that all political parties in Pakistan use Twitter strategically for their political campaigning, across the country, and abroad. Each party deploys social media teams, and recruits experts to help develop and spread their preferred narrative in the form of messages. Social media teams produce content as per their political party agendas and introduce that content into the Twittersphere with detailed planning. For example, J2 claimed that:

All political parties have established their own social media cells and social media heads. Then, at the central level, provincial level, divisional level, district level, and even down to the constituency level, there are formal and informal social media cells. The main social media cell of any party decides, for example, 'Today, we will tweet with this hashtag, and everyone should start tweeting with this hashtag at 9:30 PM.' Until 9:30 PM, no one tweets, but exactly at 9:30 PM, people start using that hashtag.

J2 articulated the process through which information flows from a central source to grassroots levels, highlighting its connection to a broader sphere of influence. The goal of this approach is to ensure that key phrases gain traction and resonate with the general public, making them more relatable and impactful. To illustrate the situation, J2 highlighted a significant trend on Twitter in Pakistan regarding the concept of “imported government,” sparked by the ousting of former Prime Minister Imran Khan. Following a constitutional parliamentary process, Khan’s government was replaced by an interim administration comprising members from other political parties. This shift occurred when opposition parties successfully voted Khan out through a vote of no confidence. In response to these events, PTI accused the military

establishment of being involved in the transition and claimed that the new government was effectively “imported.” To express their dissatisfaction, PTI launched a campaign on Twitter using the hashtag #ImportedGovtNotAccepted. This campaign rapidly gained traction, receiving 7.5million retweets and becoming widely popular among people of all ages in Pakistan, uniting supporters around their shared concerns (Lashari, Bhand and Katohar (2024).

Interviewees confirmed that political parties established social media cells and recruited experts to lead them. Senior journalist, J1, explained that the “space” feature of Twitter was utilised by PTI leaders, including Hammad Azhar, Fawad Chaudhry, and Murad Saeed, to interact with the public and respond to their questions, seeking to build relationships through two-way communication. While that appears to reflect an open, consultative process, there was still an element of message framing involved to advance their agenda. As J1 suggested, one approach was “the repetitive narrative of calling others’ thieves, to attract and engage the youth. This phenomenon of repeated messaging turned it into a perceived reality for the audience”. This all was organised by the social media teams of PTI, according to J2.

There is also evidence of carefully planned efforts by the political party social media teams to manage narratives. The consistency in messaging to establish the “thieves” phenomenon about rival political parties represents a good example of a strategic approach in action. Similarly, J3 mentioned how PMLN was strategic in its use of social media when its leadership was in jail. J2 and J3 highlighted that whether paid or volunteer, social media teams functioned to contest opposition accusations, whatever the context, having a duty to respond, to hurl abuse, to counter what was said against their leaders, “making Twitter well known to be a space where negative comments reach farther, encouraging toxic contributions”. When one side pushed an “Imran is Necessary” narrative, another, competing, “Mian Tera Show” (Pro Mian Nawaz, PMLN leader) trend appeared. Similarly, if content pertained to the PMLN leader, Maryam Nawaz Sharif’s, corruption derogatory remarks organised by competing parties would

accompany these. Research shows that this type of antagonistic and negative framing tends to generate more engagement online, as toxic, conflict-driven, and uncivil content is more likely to attract attention and circulate widely on Twitter than neutral or positive messaging (Freelon and Wells, 2020; Papacharissi, 2015; Theocharis *et al.*, 2016; Rossini, 2021).

Insights from politicians and social media leaders shed light on how these social media teams operate. For example, M3, the head of a social media team for Karachi City in Sindh province, provided a detailed explanation of the hierarchical structure within his team. By examining the frameworks and strategies employed by these teams, we can gain a deeper understanding of the varying levels of engagement and effectiveness across different parties. These insights highlight not only the importance of organised structures but also the potential for enhanced engagement through well-defined roles and responsibilities within the teams:

Currently, I have a workforce of six Information Secretaries and two Deputy Information Secretaries, totalling around 8 people at the district and division level. Additionally, there are 45 city areas, so approximately 60 people directly report to me. Their work includes managing social media and press at their respective levels and in their neighbourhoods.

The media lead claimed that volunteers, in addition to the officially deployed social media teams, support parties by managing social media campaigns and strategically promoting content to generate trending topics and public discourse online. This highlights the level of importance and investment parties place in managing online narratives. In addition to the volunteer setups and official social media teams at the central, provincial, and district levels, interviewees also confirmed that individual politicians hire their own personal social media teams to promote their campaigns at the constituency level. Former social media lead M1, for

instance, explained the competition among politicians within PTI to run successful social media campaigns:

In 2014-15, there was competition within PTI at various levels. PTI's central leadership began to worry about their own social media presence. Prominent leaders and teams, such as Team Umar, Team Usman Dar, Team Ali Zaidi, and Team Arif Alvi, created their own social media groups. These teams, being financed by the politicians, hired people to manage accounts and trends.

While mentioning a famous former social media team member, M1 revealed that they were on the payroll of a former politician and had left the party. Related to the funding of social media teams and cells, there is also evidence that political parties utilise state money to run their political campaigns when they are in government. For example, the News (Gishkori, 2021) reported that the Digital Media Wing (DMW) established by the PTI Government in the Ministry of Information and Broadcasting, spent 200 million rupees (approximately **£5.7 million**) on the department. Gishkori mentions a report from the auditor general of Pakistan about the illegal appointments in Digital Media Wing by the PTI government. Interviewees also indicated that financing of social media teams also came from the government treasury. J2 highlighted that:

Recently, a letter from the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa government surfaced, indicating that nearly 100,000 people were being paid 25,000 rupees (approximately **£70**) each to work from home on social media activities, with these payments coming from the government treasury.

The following section delves into how political parties organise their social media teams. It explores the strategies behind crafting messages and content designed to disseminate information, build narratives, and effectively target potential voters during political campaigns.

6.3.2 Organisational structures for message construction and circulation

Siddiqi (2020) suggests that each political party in Pakistan possesses a distinct political culture that shapes how it influences public opinion. He further argues that these parties form unique subcultures, acting as ideational agents that craft societal narratives, beliefs, and values. Research by Shabbir and Haider (2023) supports this view by revealing that political parties possess varying strengths depending on their ideological roots in different provinces. For example, the Pakistan People's Party (PPP) has deep ties in Sindh. In contrast, the Awami National Party (ANP) has a stronghold in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK), and the Pakistan Muslim League is historically dominant in Punjab.

In the 2018 General Elections, PTI made significant gains in KPK and Punjab, while the PPP maintained its influence over Sindh. Additionally, findings suggest that the social media strategies employed by these political parties are tailored to their voter demographics and party culture. There is also evidence of clear distinction in how parties' approach social media based on factors like provincial demographics, internet access, the presence of influential figures, and the literacy levels of younger populations. For instance, a social media leader from a prominent political party in Karachi noted that urban areas prefer Twitter for political news, while rural audiences gravitate towards TikTok. Furthermore, P3, an Information Secretary of a political party and Member of Parliament, highlighted the significance of having a physical presence in her Sindh constituency, underscoring the importance of direct engagement with the electorate. In Pakistan, centrally, political parties hire social media teams for their political campaigning, which is replicated by second-tier political leadership at the individual level. However, there are questions about the source of that content, who controls it, and how decisions are made about what content social media followers receive.

In this section, I discuss how social media teams develop their content and circulate it in specific ways to encourage followers to engage with it and act upon it in terms of voting intentions or for political activism purposes. I discuss how social media teams construct a particular political reality for their followers. Political parties and politicians operate strategically, actively framing issues and messages in ways designed to resonate with their intended audiences. As J2 suggests:

Every political party's social media team strategically designs hashtags and campaigns, selects themes, conducts research, and then launches them at specific times. This is all done according to a plan, utilising many resources.

Followers on social media receive carefully crafted narratives via official social media handles, with thousands of people working to share the same message. Communication is carefully thought out, crafted, and launched into the digital sphere. Interview data reveal that each political party has editorial or decision-making policies regarding content generation and propagation. In this sense, social media teams work under clear political leadership. For example, M1 told that “PTI’s social media team, led by individuals like Jibrán, played a crucial role in crafting and disseminating the narrative during the crisis (ousting of Imran Khan). M1 also said “sometimes Imran Khan himself would suggest points to highlight, and the social media team would lead these efforts”.

However, there is also evidence that content creation operates differently among mainstream political parties. Different approaches for content generation were found across the three main political parties. These differences in approach are important because they reflect how each party strategically frames its political messaging to align with its ideological positioning, target audience, and media capabilities. Understanding these variations offers critical insight into how political communication is tailored and disseminated within Pakistan’s fragmented digital

public sphere. In PTI, the social media teams work under hierarchical political leadership and seek guidance directly from the focal person of the party. Here, there are teams working under individual political party leaders who take guidance from that leader. As M1 suggested, “Even MNAs and city-level leaders formed their own teams. These teams were very strong in local political trends, always trending at the top”. He indicated that the social media teams who were working on the local level in different groups were utilised by state institutions because of their large number and expertise, “This gave (party name) around 1,500 active users or team members whose expertise was in planning and trending”. M1 shared that for his party, language planning and deciding what visuals to show were crucial. The content generated was checked by social media leads or the focal person of the party for accuracy and correctness. “Sometimes, Imran Khan himself would suggest points to highlight, and the team would lead these efforts”. He added that PTI had “groups and teams segmented by areas, each handling different aspects of the narrative, like graphics and videos”.

M2 contended that content was continuously being generated, in the form of videos, images and graphics, for use by social media teams. However, decisions about what would go first and what would be saved for later were taken at the media lead level. In recruitment, candidates were interviewed and filtered at an early stage to assess their capabilities and, crucially, to ensure that they understand the core party's stance. M2 elaborated on this when suggesting that based on “their creativity, their leadership skills, and their political views, so it's, everybody, anybody can come up with a topic if it fits, then teams propagate”.

M2 also explained that in PTI, the networked groups at the grassroots level are also asked to share important updates from their areas, and those updates also become part the overall political campaign, being amplified through the extended social network structure of the party (Figure 6.1). He also indicated that overseas Pakistani volunteers are an important part of PTI's social media network and their posts through the same network reach the grassroots level to

shape perceptions. P1, the former official spokesperson of one of the political parties who has served as Federal Minister for Information and Broadcasting, explained the systematic approach employed in PTI. He suggested that there were categories of content that PTI would generate and disseminate and that needed different levels of sign-off. The main political leader approved the most important content, while the second category, which included important content, would be signed off by the media manager. The social media team heads would handle routine content. There was a consensus between P1, M1, and M2 around approaches to content creation and distribution. The social media leads of each political party were well connected with experts in video graphics, and content editing because they had spent long careers in the field. Content generated by the developers (social media team members) is backed by the research cells working for the political parties. Figure 6.1 provides a graphical representation of the content approval mechanism in PTI.

Figure 6.1 Visual presentation of content approval development in PTI (self-contribution)

For the PPP, M3, however, suggested that their editorial policy was comparatively strict and limited, with content being suggested by the main leadership or second-tier political leadership only. At PPP, a social media team works under the main leadership and content is sent from that team for dissemination. There was a contrast with PTI where leadership qualities and

freedom to create content was valued. For this party, the social media lead at city level picks up content from the WhatsApp group and forwards it for dissemination. He confirmed that the main content originates from the team designated for content generation, which is then disseminated, although it may occasionally come from the main leadership. However, it was noted that the link between social media teams at the city level and the main central social media team was strong, but it was agreed that decisions initiating some trend would come from the main team only. It was also noted that only some of the second-tier political leadership is connected to the mainstream social media. This centralised model of digital campaigning reflects what Kreiss and McGregor (2018) describe as “command and control” structures in political communication, where strategic coherence and message discipline are prioritised over decentralised participation. The centralised flow of information helps maintain narrative consistency but may limit broader engagement within the party’s digital ranks.

In the case of PPP, the main leadership is the source; the central social media team sits in Bilawal House to coordinate with regional teams. Additionally, 2nd-tier political leadership can also occasionally command the team. Social media teams at the regional level coordinate further at the grassroots level. A graphical presentation of content construction and approval for PPP is presented in Figure 6.2, which can be compared with the structure drawn above for PTI in Figure 6.1.

Figure 6.2 Graphical presentation of the mechanism of content creation in PPP (self-contribution)

For instance, P3, a former Secretary of Information for a mainstream political party, and P4, a former Secretary of Information who has also served as Federal Minister for Information and Broadcasting, stated that second-tier political leadership was not in direct contact with the party's primary social media cell to receive content lines from them. P4 also confirmed that he had his own social media team, separate from the party's overall social media structure. This shows the lack of overall coherence in the social media team structure in PPP. This lack of coordination reflects a decentralised communication structure within PPP, which can result in inconsistent messaging and diluted narrative control. As Klinger and Svensson (2015) argue, coherent and centralised digital strategies are essential for framing messages effectively in networked political communication.

In the discussion about PMLN's communication strategy, M4 pointed out that the party's approach resembles that of the PPP, particularly in how content flows from the central leadership. He explained that party leadership sets the narrative, and the social media teams are tasked with spreading that message. They actively monitor public reactions to the leader's statements, using that feedback to amplify their content effectively. For instance, M4

highlighted the “respect the vote” hashtag, which emerged as a demand from their leader after his ousting in 2018, despite his position as the elected Prime Minister of Pakistan. This example underscores how the party seeks to engage with its audience and promote its narrative through social media. In this context, the social media team plays quite a passive role compared to the approach of PTI. In PMLN, the main and second-tier political leadership are the sources of the narrative. Narratives conveyed through available media reach the public. Social media teams amplify the topics and narratives which are already welcomed by the public. This indicates that the social media team's communication structure is weak in PMLN, and there is a lack of coordination between the social media cells and the central leadership. Content is also picked up passively, only when a statement from a prominent political leader receives attention from the public; social media teams then amplify it, rather than taking an active role in constructing and promoting the party's narrative. This can be linked with the previous theme about the presence of political parties on Twitter and the successful use of Twitter by PTI. M4 indicated that “PMLN enjoys support from supporters and volunteers, but there is no effort to coordinate with them to make them a strength for the party”.

Figure 6.3 The content-making mechanism in PMLN social media teams (self-contribution)

M4 also suggested that “PMLN was not investing money in the right place”, arguing that “PTI invests money for getting their narratives highlighted on Twitter by paying for artificial trends to highlight their narrative”. He claimed that the trend for “absolutely not” was fake. There were tweets for three hundred thousand people supporting Imran Khan.

Show me any tweet of Imran Khan that got three hundred thousand likes. The reason is that everything was fake, but it successfully created a narrative. This is human nature; when you see overwhelming support, you believe it's real. (M4)

The claim made by M4 is supported by research into another noteworthy trend promoted by PTI, known as *#imported-govt-unacceptable*. Findings suggest that the surge in likes and posts was not organic, suggesting that PTI invested money to artificially amplify support for this narrative. As a result, it appeared to the public that there was widespread backing for their position (Ahmed, Saeed and Alam, 2024). Forelle et al. (2015) conducted research on the social media activity of the six most prominent politicians in Venezuela. Their findings showed that fake accounts, often referred to as bots, were employed not only to disseminate political

messages but also to boost website followers, create false trends, and manipulate information distribution. This highlights the potential for deception in political discourse on social media platforms.

The findings also reveal notable differences in how the three political parties coordinate their social media efforts and generate content. Among them, the PTI stands out as the most connected and organised. Its operations seamlessly integrate local social media teams that excel in crafting narratives tailored to grassroots audiences. This strategy not only enhances local engagement but also allows PTI to amplify national messages effectively. PTI welcomes content contributions from a wide range of social media creators and researchers within its teams. However, there is a well-defined command and control system in place, ensuring that the messaging remains cohesive and impactful. This approach helps maintain a strong, unified voice across various platforms.

In contrast, PPP has social media teams operating at the local level, but there was little evidence that the social media teams working under individual politicians are adding to the overall amplification of the party's narrative at the national or international level. The PMLN appeared to be the least connected party in terms of a coordinated approach to content generation and dissemination, due to two factors. In addition to the organisation structure linking the central and second tier political leadership and the central social media teams, findings indicate that the social media teams are hired to work at provincial, district, city and grassroots level as well. J2 highlighted that “within their organisational structures, from the central level down to the provincial and even the local levels, social media cells are active”. For example, individual leaders and candidates also create their own social media cells, “which engage in propaganda, respond to opponents, and promote their narratives”. J2 argued that the activities previously carried out by central political parties using graphics and videos have now begun to occur at the union council and provincial constituency levels as well. At these levels, people also use

social media to promote their local political narratives. These structural differences are academically significant because they reveal how political organisations adapt to the affordances and pressures of digital media environments (Chadwick, 2013; Enli, 2017). From a political communication perspective, understanding these models offers insight into how message framing, coherence, and control are operationalised within party hierarchies, contributing to debates on mediatisation, digital campaigning, and strategic communication (Lilleker, 2014).

This section has identified the party priorities for content generation at the individual party level. The preferences of the political parties regarding the dissemination of content generated are discussed in the next section.

6.4 Content dissemination techniques: plural platforms

6.4.1 Use of WhatsApp groups

Having explored how content is created and framed, this section now turns to how it is disseminated which is a crucial step in ensuring that political narratives gain visibility, traction, and impact on platforms like Twitter. The use of WhatsApp groups for the sharing process was found to be common among all political parties. After the content is introduced to Twitter at the national level, passing through all the approval phases within each political party, the narrative is again disseminated using the already established WhatsApp group structure at the grassroots level. As J2 indicated, “A trend initiated from the centre reaches the union council level through WhatsApp groups and social media heads, who then tweet about it”. J4 considers that the use of WhatsApp groups is common in all political parties despite the fact that they have differences in terms of communication and coordination structures within their own political parties.

At the grassroots level, people mostly use WhatsApp for political communication. My personal opinion is that their presence on Twitter is just for show. They do not gain support from their supporters on Twitter; they gain support from their own supporters through the WhatsApp groups, which are pretty standard among political supporters.

The findings indicate that this WhatsApp group culture is deeply penetrated, complex, and utilised by all political parties. J4 explained the reason for the use of WhatsApp, indicating that these groups are made for those who are not on Twitter, “Twitter is just a platform to build a narrative; once a narrative is built, it is disseminated to the general masses through WhatsApp groups”. M4, who has been working as social media head with one of the most prominent political parties, indicated that his party developed WhatsApp groups in 2016 to connect with party workers and disseminate the narrative among the masses. M3 provided further insight about the use of WhatsApp and other social media. He said that each level (of narrative dissemination) has its methods, such as WhatsApp groups, Facebook tagging, and direct messaging, to ensure everyone gets the message promptly. M4, while discussing the WhatsApp group structure and its functioning, explained that “this structure is not just in Karachi but throughout Pakistan. We can quickly spread information through our proper administrative WhatsApp groups, where every member knows their role.”

As M4 explained:

We developed structures and created WhatsApp groups for every district, which still exist today. These groups include district-level core groups and even constituency-level groups. Our social media structure is hierarchical, similar to that of any political organisation. This well-organised WhatsApp group system connects to Twitter and other platforms.

This discussion highlights that while Twitter plays a significant role in shaping narratives, it is not the sole platform used by political parties. The insights from M4 and M3 suggest that the effectiveness of these platforms depends on various factors, including the level of education among users and the overall popularity of the platform. This indicates a more complex relationship between social media usage and political engagement, where different platforms may serve distinct purposes based on their audience and context. The following section will further extend the discussion about the connection between Twitter and other social media platforms to establish the complexities and nuances in current political communication patterns in the wake of the digital sphere in Pakistan.

6.4.2 The digital sphere and the dynamics of narrative flow from Twitter

Interview findings indicate that Twitter is utilised in many cities in Punjab province, like Lahore, Faisalabad, and the federal capital, Islamabad. It is used in rural and urban areas, but in terms of popularity, Facebook and TikTok are more widely used locally. The evidence suggests that Twitter is more popular at the national level. Interviews with media and political party leaders confirmed the existence of a digital sphere in Pakistan, as discussed in Chapter 4. As one of the media managers, M4, commented, there is at least one smartphone per family in Pakistan, and this is how they connect to the digital sphere:

Firstly, in Pakistan, approximately 60-70% of the population is digitally connected, either directly or indirectly. There might be one mobile phone per household, but it's there. The impact of Twitter extends to other platforms like TikTok and Facebook.

What starts on Twitter often spreads to these platforms, and vice versa.

M4 argued that even if people are not directly on Twitter, the narratives formed there reach other platforms, ensuring widespread reach. "For instance, if someone tweets about high electricity bills, that tweet can go viral on TikTok or Facebook, reaching a wider audience". A

report published by Datareportal in 2024 about the internet penetration and social media use in Pakistan indicates that there were:

111.0 million internet users in Pakistan at the start of 2024, when internet penetration stood at 45.7 percent, Pakistan was home to 71.70 million social media users in January 2024, equating to 29.5 percent of the total population, A total of 188.9 million cellular mobile connections were active in Pakistan in early 2024, with this figure equivalent to 77.8 percent of the total population (Kemp, 2024).

These numbers highlight the level of connectivity of people in Pakistan. The report also highlighted that the actual penetration of the internet could be more than the collected information. J2 gave the example of an uneducated relative who lives in a rural area, but she often discusses news and updates with him, which she watches on TikTok. He was of the view that most of the time, disinformation is propagated through social media platforms by political parties. However, this information is powerful and people with little formal education find it difficult to differentiate or assess the credibility of information.

According to interviewees, there is networking on Twitter as the main party pages are linked with the provincial, city and district level pages, and once the information is circulated within that network, other social media platforms are then utilised to disseminate the information to the public, depending on their popularity among the wider population. Interviewees suggested that Twitter, while used frequently at national and international levels, is less effective once you encounter provincial or local politics. TikTok is widely used in rural Pakistan, where its visual format appeals to lower-literacy users and mobile-first audiences (DataReportal, 2025). Facebook remains popular nationwide, especially among older users and political groups (Ahmed and Skoric, 2014; StatCounter, 2025). These patterns show how different platforms shape political content dissemination across demographics.

There are several factors behind the popularity of other social media platforms in the country. For instance, M4, the media lead expressed the view that PPP's focus is on a poorer, less educated base, who are less technologically advanced and have lower quality access to the benefits of the digital world in the Sindh province. He argued that this target audience are more likely to access news on TikTok because it is easier and relies less on the users' levels of literacy. This target audience can access news easily by watching videos instead of complex textual and meaningful text and image combinations. As noted by Sharif (Sharif, Ameen and Taj, 2024), focusing on the impact of Tiktok for propagating political messages, the mainstream political parties PPP, PMLN and PTI were using symbols and narratives to engage audiences. (Nadeem, Masood and Mahmood, 2024), have also conducted a quantitative survey to investigate the impact of short videos on TikTok, Youtube, Facebook and Instagram Reels and found that the reels were a useful source of information for teenagers in Pakistan. P3 and P4 indicated that most of the PPP's focus is on Tiktok and in some cases Facebook too, complementing the views of M4. M4 explained how he managed to run a political campaign on Twitter during an election in Karachi City and it was successful, emphasising the importance of that platform for national-level narrative building. M1, P2, and J2 also drew attention to the importance of Tiktok but interestingly they suggested that even if a leader joins TikTok, the news is still broken on Twitter. If a leader does not tweet for some time, it becomes a news story and if posts are made from the accounts of arrested leaders like Maryam Nawaz or Imran Khan, the public questions who is making those posts on the leader's behalf. So, while there is evidence that other social media platforms are becoming important for regional and local politics to reach targeted audiences, Twitter retains its primacy as the primary strategic tool of choice. As J2 highlights:

Twitter is used more, regardless of whether it is in rural areas, Islamabad, or Lahore. Locally, Facebook is more popular because of its larger user base, but for national-level narratives, Twitter trends are more significant

It is notable that the cities mentioned by J2 are all in Punjab province. This indicates that Twitter is more popular in Punjab than Sindh province as highlighted by M4, P2 and P3. Clearly, different social media platforms play different roles in provinces across Pakistan. This can be linked with studies about the priorities and slogans of political parties in Pakistan. For instance, Munir and Khalid (2021), commenting on voting clusters for the mainstream political parties in Pakistan, suggest, that PPP is considered to be a left, socialist party and its slogan “Roti Kapra and Makan” (bread, clothing and housing) attracted a significant voter cluster from that segment throughout Pakistan. However, Munir and Khalid indicate that the party, is more concentrated in the Sindh province, as it is still considered one of the three major political parties in Pakistan. This perspective aligns with the study findings about PPP attracting vote banks of poor, uneducated people who are easy to approach via TikTok or direct contacts in the form of corner meetings, funerals, and marriage ceremonies. According to Munir and Khalid (2021), the socio-economic development and comparatively higher levels of education in Punjab have made the province more receptive to digital engagement. As a result, the increasing urbanisation and widespread use of social media are critical factors that political parties consider when strategising to attract voters in the region.

As discussed, PPP was the only party focused on accessing the lower classes, while PMLN and PTI talked about Twitter because of their focus on the Punjab province. Furthermore, PTI considers overseas Pakistanis during their political campaigns and because of their proficiencies in technology, witnessing social media campaigns in countries like the US are contributing to PTI's social media strategies. J4, currently working with an international online news media outlet in Pakistan, based on her vast experience in mainstream media in Pakistan,

suggested that Twitter is not the only standalone tool used for strategic purposes by political parties. Rather, based on which audience is being targeted and where, different tools are utilised. For example, according to J4, PMLN has thousands of WhatsApp groups, and the party utilises these for grassroots-level information sharing; PPP also has these groups throughout Pakistan, and others indicated the utilisation of TikTok, Facebook, and YouTube too (J7, M1).

In addition to the social media teams of political parties, interview findings indicate that Twitter users also take narratives from that platform and spread them on other platforms. As M2 highlighted, “Twitter users receive the information disseminated by PTI and they share it in their individual groups or circles through WhatsApp, Facebook, and Instagram. Apart from the debate about voting clusters, the penetration and popularity of social media platforms in Pakistan emerged as is one of the main factors that political parties consider for their political campaigns. According to the Datareportal (2024) report, the most popular social media platforms in Pakistan are detailed in Table 6.5.

Social media platform	Users
Facebook	44.50 million
YouTube	71.70 million
Instagram	17.30 million
TikTok	54.38 million
Facebook Messenger	11.95 million
LinkedIn	12 million
X users	4.50 million

Table 6.5 report, the most popular social media platforms in Pakistan are detailed (Kemp, 2024)

When a user posts or publishes content, other users can interact using comments or spread the content using different mechanisms for example, shares on Facebook and retweets on Twitter. When these actions are repeated continuously, various processes occur among the users, such

as information dissemination as communities become communication agents. This discussion can be presented visually, reflecting information flows from Twitter to other platforms. This means that users from these communities mainly share information between themselves (Obregon, Song and Jung, 2019). What is clear is that every digital platform sphere is entangled with another.

Figure 6.4 The flow of information on Twitter occurs through its users (self-contribution)

Those who use Twitter are also likely to be connected to Facebook; the information someone provides on Facebook can also be shared on TikTok. This is how the narrative, which is constructed, decided and finalised among party leadership, SMTs, and social media teams, becomes part of the wider public discussion. The study findings revealed three types of information flow possibilities. First, people on Twitter receive information shared by politicians and political parties, and they spread it in their circle or influence the opinions of others who are not on Twitter. Secondly, findings also indicated that once the narrative is set on Twitter at the national level, that narrative is propagated to the grassroots level using already existing WhatsApp groups of political parties indicated by M3 and M4.

Figure 6.5 Twitter information Flow via political party WhatsApp groups (self-contribution)

The third possibility is that the same narrative developed on Twitter will be spread to the general public through the most popular social media platforms, such as Facebook, TikTok, YouTube, and Instagram.

Figure 6.6 Flow of information from Twitter to other platforms (self-contribution)

While all three patterns of information flow were identified, the findings highlight Twitter as the central node in the political communication landscape. Given the focus of this study, particular attention is paid to how narratives originate on Twitter and are then disseminated to other social media platforms, underscoring its strategic role in shaping political discourse

6.5 Framed political communication on Twitter

Having outlined how political parties construct and disseminate their messages, I now turn to the types of frames they employ. This section examines the actual content of political communication circulating within Pakistan’s elite digital sphere. This section focuses on the framing of messages by social media teams in Pakistan’s political landscape. Findings suggest

that the framing of messages posted on social media, including Twitter, reflect traces of old existing political cultures in Pakistan. Interviewees illustrated how political parties in Pakistan are adapting digital technologies like Twitter and hiring social media teams to craft content which can attract attention and disseminate that content to the grassroots levels. Matthes (2012) indicates that frames refer to the specific ways issues are presented and perceived, influencing how we understand and evaluate them. By highlighting certain aspects while downplaying others, frames shape our perspective of reality in distinct ways, leading to different interpretations and judgments about the same issue. Salam-Salmaoui and Salam (2023) highlight the framing of messages by two politicians, Maryam Nawaz and Imran Khan, on Twitter in 2022 after a unanimous vote of no confidence from the Parliament that ousted the former Prime Minister. Research by Salam-Salmoui and Salam, which contributes to the framing theory of Hallahan (2011), is based on the acknowledgement that framing is a dynamic process, susceptible to change. Their research establishes that the prominent political leaders in Pakistan frame their messages on Twitter as an act of “public relations”. The study focused on the techniques used for framing the tweets, which aimed to construct identity and influence public perceptions and attitudes.

Interview findings confirmed that all political parties frame their messages and craft their content with specific objectives. Words for the trends are selected and presented to the public multiple times to make that information part of their memory. The frames then serve as reality for the public when repeated numerous times. Senior broadcast journalist J1 highlighted the existence of a cultural phenomenon in the frames of messages posted on Twitter. He believed that political culture also plays a significant role in political communication. J1 suggests that:

The language used, audio, videos, and images against each other, it's clear that framing is intentional. The language used by politicians clearly indicates they want to give a particular angle to a topic.

J5 also noted that the language used in the posts is far simpler, reduced to the point of becoming a “pre-digested food”, which is the “hallmark of all propagandists”. As J2 highlighted, the trend 'imported government' was tweeted millions of times, reaching young people and adults alike. He suggested that all political parties in Pakistan carefully choose the information to convey to the “intended message”, including “victimhood, glorification or promotion”. Examples of the famous term in the politics of Pakistan in contemporary times, “thieves, or gang of thieves”, were mentioned by many interviewees. This narrative about “thieves” and “gang of thieves” was run by PTI against PMLN. Interviewees discussed the power of presenting the same narrative consistently. M4 indicated:

For example, it was argued that PMLN decided to present PTI as against institutions, and as a result they share older footage of PTI attacking Parliament House, creating content focused on that topic. Their attack on Pakistan television would be highlighted and in response, PTI would frame images, create video and text posts about PMLN attacks on the Supreme Court. Projection of narratives and counter narratives continue on Twitter from political parties.

The examples provided establish the presence of framing of political messaging by Pakistani political leaders. However, none of the interviewees identified examples of counter-narrative wars from the PPP. All the examples presented were about PMLN and PTI who are more concentrated towards Punjab. M3, the social media manager of a political party who was working under the official social media teams at the city level in Sindh province, suggested that the campaigns from PPP are mostly about the developmental works the party has done for people, projecting a positive image. Former Federal Minister for Information, P1 shared that his party used to design all types of content for the media, public, and other political parties and would craft the content accordingly. P3 gave an example to express his understanding about the framing of messages on Twitter:

Let's make you an example, it's hypothetical, of course, that in today's world, they will say, okay, the Imran trial, there are two views on that, some for, some against, so those trends will be set accordingly by the party that makes it into a popular trending issue.

Findings suggest that all political parties frame their leaders as the best solution to the problems of Pakistan. In doing so, language is strategically considered while crafting political messages. J5, for instance, commented, “Absolutely, the language is far simpler. It is toned down to the point of becoming a pre-digested food, which is the hallmark of all propagandists”. He also expressed the view that “there are simpler messages, short messages, direct messages, exaggerated messages, you know, taking the mickey out of your opponents, building yourself as a great hero”, adding that the language is appealing to the bare minimum understanding, political understanding that exists across the country and beyond the borders. The politicians interviewed for this research expressed the view that PTI was the most successful party in consistently presenting and crafting frames. P3, for example, said “I think that they try to frame their messages but they're not all successful. PTI has been successful because they are using it more frequently, more extensively and they were very strong”. Social media managers suggested that the political parties need to be wise in terms of what people like to see. If there is inflation and someone presents a post about their leader to be the best without contextualising it with a solution for inflation, it will not be popular, and the public will not accept it. Narratives linked with religion and anti-American sentiment are still popular. To illustrate, it is worth outlining some of the popular #hashtags used as frames from all three selected parties when Imran Khan was ousted, comparing how each party presented itself about this hugely significant event.

Starting with PTI, it is helpful to highlight examples drawn from the official handle of its leader, Imran Khan, after he was ousted from power in April 2022, especially as we know that this party's social media strategy is tied closely to its political leader. A narrative was built about a

foreign conspiracy and an imported government by PTI after Khan was ousted through the parliamentary process in a vote of no confidence. The posts contain frames that were repeated multiple times. Some of these frames were started by PTI after the ousting of Imran Khan, like “foreign conspiracy”, “American conspiracy” and “imported government”, and some were old, like “thieves”. For example, chairman PTI posted on Twitter

I want to thank all our social media warriors who have valiantly taken our fight against US regime change conspiracy forward on all social media platforms. Continue carrying on our movement for Pak's sovereignty & democracy. You are our frontline warriors. [#MarchAgainstImportedGovt](#) (Khan, 2022).

There are three main points to be made about the choice of language used in this post. The first is that the ousting of the former Prime Minister was because of a “US conspiracy”. Second, there is mention of “social media warriors” and third, is the reference to a “march against imported government”. The frames of “imported government” and “US conspiracies” suggest that these trends were repeated by the social media teams of PTI that brought success setting the narrative and gaining sympathy from the public. One post from Khan illustrates this dynamic clearly: it was retweeted over 57,000 times, liked 137,000 times, and attracted 14,000 replies a scale of engagement far above the typical interactions with political content on Pakistani Twitter. This demonstrates not only the visibility of Khan’s framing but also its resonance with a digital support base that actively amplifies such messages. Another good example of former PM Imran Khan using the same frames to establish his party narrative is the following Twitter post:

Thank you Karachi for your momentous & passionate support for our jalsa last night. This is our fight for democracy & the sovereignty of Pakistan & against a US-initiated

regime change conspiracy abetted by local abettors & corrupt political mafia.

[#امپورٹڈ_حکومت_نامنظور](#) (Khan, 2022).

The Urdu hashtag means “imported government not accepted”. The frame presents the then government as “imported” by the establishment in Pakistan. Secondly, there is a repeated frame about the “US-backed conspiracy”. Khan presents these frames alongside the older frames his party was using against the other political leaders of Pakistan, calling them the “corrupt political mafia”.

Furthermore, the same frames were also used by the second-tier leadership of the party. For example, a post made by Murad Saeed, former PTI Federal Minister, on Twitter not only repeats the frame about “imported government not accepted” but also presents information about how many times the hashtag about imported government was used, making it a record in Twitter history. Saeed (2022) quoted a Tweet from TweetBinder, Twitter Analytics Tool:

Now that @elonmusk has purchased Twitter, we feel it's a great time to share Twitter stats about the hashtag #امپورٹڈ_حکومت_نامنظور, maybe the biggest trend ever analysed in Tweet Binder. 106,433,419 tweets!!” using the same hashtag indicating it.

Research has also established that this hashtag was boosted using artificial accounts (bots). The PMLN media lead highlighted this hashtag as a successful investment by PTI for narrative building. Having looked at the frames and the number of reactions towards the posts from PTI leaders, it is necessary to highlight the frames used by the other two main political parties to defend their positions or counter the narrative spread by PTI at the time of the ousting of Imran Khan.

The PMLN social media account posted on Twitter after the ousting of the former Prime Minister,

In April 2022, PMLN took over a nation suffering from rampant corruption and incompetence under IK's regime. Rather than playing politics, they prioritized saving the state. Now, with a focus on [#RebuildingPakistan](#), PMLN is proving their commitment to putting the nation first (PMLN-SMT, 2023).

The tweet contained a video message of 38 seconds highlighting the areas the new PMLN government was helping to rebuild the country and rebuilding it from the damage caused by the previous PTI government. The frames used in the text highlight, first, the “incompetence of the previous PTI government”. Second, the emphasis is on “corruption” and third, the notion that “PMLN is rebuilding Pakistan”. The visual frames accompanying the tweet relate to developmental projects initiated by the PMLN government. However, engagement with the PMLN tweet was starkly different to the posts made by Imran Khan. PTI posts received 180k+ likes, while the PMLN leader post gained only 87 likes and 99 reposts despite having a visual component to attract reaction. Another post made by PMLN leader Maryam Nawaz Sharif at the ousting of the former Prime Minister Imran Khan is comparable with the celebratory post about [#ImportedGovtnotaccepted](#) made by PTI leadership.

Another IK lie exposed, another Conspiracy unveiled. Turns out that the slander campaigns against State institutions & lies about international conspiracy were churned out & spread by no more than a handful of people employing hundreds of fake accounts & BOTS (Sharif, 2022).

The post was reposted only 3k times and was liked by 7.2k people. Similarly, another tweet was posted by Maryam Nawaz with the graphical presentation of the data - a graph showing the activity of the trend [#importedgovernmentnotaccepted](#). She posted

All the activity on this trend is entirely coordinated not organic. All tweets, comments, replies, likes go up and down together, generated by automated bots. PTI is using

botnets to generate coordinated spam activity and artificially boost its trends on Twitter (Nawaz 2022).

The two tweets from PMLN leader Maryam Nawaz are designed to highlight that the PTI's historically popular trending topic was artificially created. She is using the frames, "Imran conspiring against state institutions", "false foreign conspiracies" and, "disinformation via use of AI". The interactions on Twitter using competing frames conform with Batool et al. (2022), who find that these two political parties identify each other as their main rivals. This rivalry is heightened by both parties competing for power in the most important province of Punjab. These parties are considered rivals, and the frames used by both leaders identify that rivalry. By way of contrast, the third mainstream political party, PPP, celebrated the removal of Imran Khan as representing a positive democratic move. Twitter posts from the PPP chairman, Bilawal Bhutto, highlight this framing, "Democracy is the best revenge! Jiye Bhutto! Jiya Awam! Pakistan Zindabad" (Bhutto, 2022b). 13k likes and 4.5k reposts is still far less than PTI reach but a little better than PMLN post reactions. Bilawal Butto made another post using the same frames with a link to his full speech, available on YouTube, "After trying every unconstitutional trick, IK couldn't stop us. Democracy won. My short speech congratulating PK <https://youtu.be/jeqFZr4aPy0> via @YouTube"(Bhutto, 2022a). There is consistency in the frames used by PPP leader Bilawal Bhutto, who established the removal of Imran Khan as a positive constitutional and democratic move for Pakistan, claiming that the former Prime Minister was using unconstitutional tricks to stay in power. The frames used in the above two posts focus on "democracy wins". In addition, PPP slogans like "Jiye Bhutto" (long live Bhutto) align with the party's political campaign remembering the killing of founder PPP Zulfiqar Bhutto. "Jiye Awam" represents the PPP's link with Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto again, who was projected as "awami" (public) leader by PPP. It represents one of the characteristics of political culture in Pakistan mentioned by Siddiqi (2020). He suggested that there is a culture

of personality in Pakistani politics. Either military or civil, personalities always dominated as the face of political powers in Pakistan. PPP still runs the legacy of its founder, Zulfikar Ali Bhutto, and maintains a slogan that Bhutto, the leader of democracy, the leader of the public is still alive among us. It is also noticeable that Bilawal Bhutto posted a link of his video message which he uploaded on Youtube. This demonstrates that the frames are being created to share on other platforms, which are then amplified via Twitter.

The second-tier leadership of PPP also celebrated the removal of Imran Khan, using visual frames, for instance, posts from PPP political leader Qasim Gillani on Twitter indicated that “Bilawal Bhutto emerged as the most valuable player in the successful vote of no confidence against Imran Khan in April 2022. As a young politician, he (Bilawal Bhutto) skilfully brought together various political forces in Pakistan and was instrumental in toppling the powerful one-page regime” (Gillani, 2023). The frames evident in the post are “bringing political forces together” and highlighting the “one-page regime” of Imran Khan. Importantly, there is a clear pattern with the frames used by Bilawal Bhutto in his posts, accusing Imran Khan of using unconstitutional tricks to remain in power. The post received 916 likes and 610 reposts. This presents the difference in reach of political parties on Twitter. It establishes that the frames are there from all political parties, but PTI’s strong presence on Twitter, the party structure for the projection of every message, contributes towards greater reach. The example posts and discussions about the three main political parties on the same political development in Pakistan indicate that all three political parties were actively engaging on Twitter and framing political developments according to their own political positions, whether posting from their official accounts or those of their main leadership. All three political leaders were posting on the development from their official Twitter handles, but PTI was the only party with a huge number of interactions and responses for their posts. The factors discussed earlier, like strong party coordination, organised social media team structure, and planning for launching trends on

Twitter are the strengths of PTI. The PTI leader was calling for protests and appraising those who attended the protest against his ousting, and he was framing his ousting as a US-backed conspiracy by a “thief gang” of other political parties. The PPP leader, Bilawal Bhutto, was framing it to be a constitutional and democratic move and PMLN was posting about the corruption of the Imran Khan regime and was expressing commitment to develop instead of “playing politics” also defending and countering PTI narrative about ousting of Imran Khan.

Interviewees confirmed that there are separate teams to work on both positive and negative frames in each political party. J2 argued that “the teams designated to project a positive image of the leader or the party's achievements, construct positive frames using text, video and images. The teams designated to project negative framing, target other political parties and seek to undermine their leadership”. As highlighted by J7, they manipulate opinions through Twitter and they seek to influence how the public will interpret a specific incident, “Someone might say a person died because of a particular political party without verifying”.

The frames highlighted in the posts of mainstream political leaders in Pakistan represent the country's political dynamics and are reflected in the style of political communication. All highlight an anti-establishment narrative, often focused on anti-corruption which Siddiqi et al (2020) and Hussain et.al (2018) suggest is evident in the frames used by Imran Khan. Furthermore, Siddique also highlights that political parties keep claiming that they are the custodians of democracy and these frames are evident in the Twitter posts of all political leaders. This proves that the frames on Twitter are not devoid of the traditional political culture of Pakistan. Rather, technology has provided platforms for projecting those same frames with new tools. The frames reflect political leadership branding as well which reflects what scholars have described as a growing ‘cult of personality’ in digital political communication (Enli, 2017), where leader-centric branding and emotional appeals become dominant frames.

The findings reveal that the propaganda machines of political parties while framing events to build their narrative also spread fake news and disinformation on Twitter as identified by J5, during the 9th May unrest, PTI accused state security agencies of conducting sexual assaults against women political workers and these things went viral and gained public support for PTI.

Take the incident of May 9, a major event in Pakistan where the line between a political party and the military was crossed. The event led to the distribution of altered images and accusations of sexual assault against women, all of which went viral on Twitter.

J6 was also of the view that both paid and volunteer social media cells of the political parties often operate under fake names. “Even if someone uses their real name, they aren't well-known individuals. Their job is to hurl abuses, regardless of the content”. He also gave an example of one of his posts he made to console the death of a politician's son, and his post received harsh remarks from a volunteer from the opposing party. He was of the view that it is not only the information, which is fake, but the identities are fake/unknown as well. These findings reflect wider concerns in the literature about how political actors exploit social media platforms to manipulate public perception through disinformation and identity obfuscation. Scholars like Howard, Woolley and Calo (2018) have documented how political parties globally engage in computational propaganda, employing bots, trolls, and fake accounts to spread misleading narratives and attack opponents.

6.6 Digital-to-physical campaign strategies

In this final section, I outline what happens once narratives are built, and political parties recruit social media teams to propagate them. Political mobilisation is:

any verbal or physical effort to attract people more toward one's party or manifesto. It includes interaction with people about various issues and highlights the gravity of the

situations. It also focuses on ensuring people's participation and mental preparedness toward one's strategies (Khan, Jan and Khan, 2022, p. 562).

The findings suggest that creating narratives on Twitter helps political parties in Pakistan mobilise voters during election campaigns, influence their voting intentions, and encourage them to participate in protests. There is also evidence that narratives created online also reach offline audiences as political parties develop social media campaigns in conjunction with offline efforts to maximise their impact. Interviewees suggested that politicians in Pakistan are sophisticated in the way they connect online and offline political activities to meet their objectives. For example, on May 9th, 2023, riots broke out in Pakistan following the arrest of former Prime Minister, Imran Khan. Interviewees suggested that the riots were incited by a Twitter narrative that had been preparing supporters to protest and build an anti-military establishment sentiment. According to J1:

I think if you look at the trends and topics trending before May 9th, they were quite instigating. The confrontation between PTI and the establishment was evident from Imran Khan and his followers' posts, suggesting possible confrontations.

J3 described how people stormed the house of a military official who had stated the arrest was right. The PTI chairman was arrested, and the party projected the victim narrative against the military establishment:

The reaction was heavily influenced by the narrative they had built over the last year and a half. It was very reactive, and their politicians, most of whom have now left, were consistently propagating that certain individuals were the cause of all problems (J3)

J5 suggested that the frames used by PTI leaders during the 9th May riots were used as evidence to lay charges against PTI later. J7 also agreed that the 9th May riots did not occur in isolation, arguing that it was predictable because the anger generated by the former PM's arrest was

directed towards military institutions, buildings, and personalities. J8 agreed that the “PTI leadership and social media teams were posting against army chiefs, and that narrative had an impact because these trends generated such hatred that people came out on May 9th and attacked military installations.”

Analysing the Twitter handles of PTI political leaders around this important political moment demonstrates how Twitter was used to create fervour amongst the Pakistani population. Analysing 15 days of Twitter data before and including 9th May, PTI-related Twitter posts were leading people to act to “protect Imran Khan” and “express hatred against the establishment”. In late April, Imran Khan posted:

Interior Minister says my life is under threat from foreign agencies. Let me make it clear to the entire country that the only threat to my life is from the three people I named after the Wazirabad assassination attempt. Same 3, + 3 more I have identified in a video statement, tried to eliminate me.....I want to make it crystal clear to the nation that the only ppl responsible for any attempt on my life will be the ppl I have identified. They are petrified I will be elected back to power & hold them accountable, hence their efforts to assassinate me. (Khan, 2023).

Prominent national and international media outlets including Voice of America, Aaj English News, and Dawn News, reported about Imran Khan’s allegations which are apparent in this post. Voice of America reported “PTI released a copy of Khan's letter to Alvi in which the opposition leader repeated his allegations that Prime Minister Shehbaz Sharif, the interior minister and a senior official of the Inter-Services Intelligence (ISI) had plotted the attack. Khan claimed he had information from within Pakistani intelligence agencies that a plot was being hatched to assassinate him”(Gull, 2022). In the posts, he establishes that these people will be responsible for whatever happens to him in the future. The Twitter post Khan made just

one day before his arrival at the Islamabad High Court building and his arrest, in response to the sitting Prime Minister and PMLN leader Shehbaz Sharif's Twitter post was also a continuity of the same narrative. The posts from PMLN leader were "Imran Niazi's act of routinely maligning and threatening Pakistan Army and Intelligence Agency for the sake of petty political gains is highly condemnable. His levelling of allegations without any proof against Gen Faisal Naseer and officers of our Intelligence Agency cannot be allowed and will not be tolerated" (Sharif, 2023), received 2.2 million views, and Khan's post "as someone who has suffered 2 assassination attempts on his life in last few months, can I dare to ask SS the following Qs: 1. Have I, a citizen, the right to nominate those I feel were responsible for assassination attacks on me? Why was I denied my legal & Constitutional right?" (Khan, 2023a) received 5.2 million views, which is more than double the number of views, clearly establishing the PTI leader's upper hand in Twitter public reach. One notable thing in this example is that the posts of both party leaders can be seen and compared in terms of the number of views. Shahbaz Sharif, the PMLN leader, criticises Imran Khan for making false allegations about military personnel and maligning state institutions. Tweets from the second-tier PTI leadership on the arrest of Imran Khan contained emotionally persuasive messages to mobilise people to protest, to come out and save the former Prime Minister.

Based on the anti-military establishment narrative, the emotions and anger of the party workers resulted in the burying of many military installations in major cities of Pakistan. On May 9th, PTI leader Murad Saeed took to Twitter following the arrest of former Prime Minister Imran Khan, delivering a powerful message to his supporters. He urged the public to act in the face of potential internet and mobile service shutdowns and leadership arrests, stating, "In the event of internet and mobile phone services being shut down and leadership being arrested, the public should hold sit-ins in their respective cities, making life difficult for those who consider themselves gods on earth. I repeat, our silence and weakness today mean we have handed over

our leader to these murderers and our future to these bloodthirsty beasts. May Allah be the protector and supporter of Pakistan” (Saeed, 2023a). This post garnered 1.5 million views, calling on PTI followers to protest for Imran Khan’s freedom.

In another post that day, Saeed compared the PMLN government and establishment to Egyptian Fero who was tyrant king and according to Islamic beliefs has been made a lesson for the world, “The one who challenged the authority of the Lord (Allah) of 'Be, and it is' remains, even centuries later, a cautionary exhibit in the museum, yet some shortsighted individuals, intoxicated by their fleeting power, sit claiming divinity”(Saeed, 2023c). This message received 838k views, with 36k likes and 14k reposts. Saeed also made an emotional appeal, stating, “Once again, a death trap has been prepared for Imran Khan. Pakistani nation, remember, Imran Khan is our last chance to change our destiny. #عمران_خان_ہماری_ریڈ_لائن” (Saeed, 2023b), which translates to “Imran is our red line.” This post attracted 1.4 million views, 58k likes, and 27k reshares. In a final call to action, he declared on Twitter, “Revolution” (2023d), stating in another post on same day (9th May) “Erdogan's Turkey or Morsi's Egypt. Today, the Pakistani nation will decide its freedom or slavery #نکلو_خان_کی_زندگی_بچاؤ” (Translation: come out to save Khan’s life). These messages highlighted the intense atmosphere during the riots as PTI supporters rallied for their leader on May 9th.

These examples highlight that PTI leaders were posting comments from Imran Khan, naming the military leadership for any potential future action the state would take against him before his arrest, a pre-emptive social media strategy. On 9th May, the PTI leadership were using Twitter as a platform to ask their followers to come out and protest to protect Imran Khan. The anger among followers, due to Imran Khan’s arrest, already had a direction and an outlet. People attacked military installations, even memorials of previous wars, and the house of a military official. The data from the Twitter official accounts of PTI leaders from April 2023 to

9th May 2023 complements the views expressed by interviewees that political parties in Pakistan utilise Twitter for political activism and mobilise the public for protests.

Hence, these varied responses to Imran Khan's ousting reflect the intense rivalry among the major political parties, with each leveraging social media to frame the narrative in their favour. While PTI's dominant engagement indicates its stronger foothold on digital platform, despite the political upheaval, the contrasting reactions from PMLN and PPP suggest a struggle for relevance and resonance within the public discourse. PMLN's attempts to position itself as a reformative force stand in stark contrast to the tumultuous portrayal of PTI, yet their limited interaction may signal the challenge they face in capturing public sentiment amidst a fierce digital landscape. Conversely, PPP's framing as a champion of democracy not only appeals to historical legacies but also attempts to align itself with current democratic movements in Pakistan. The emphasis on democratic revival and coalition politics marks a strategic pivot for the party, aiming to reinvigorate its base and attract new supporters. Overall, the social media activities and the framing tactics of each political entity reveal deeper insights into the dynamics of Pakistani politics, showcasing how narratives are constructed and contested in the digital realm.

6.7 Conclusion

This chapter has demonstrated why Twitter is a vital tool for political parties in Pakistan, functioning as an elite digital sphere that enables strategic narrative building and frames political messages for wider circulation across both online and offline publics. The findings show that while parties vary in their expertise and targeted constituencies, a common pattern emerges: Twitter is used as a central platform to frame messages, which are then amplified across other social media channels such as Facebook, WhatsApp, and TikTok to reach diverse audiences.

The chapter also highlighted the organisational strategies that underpin this communication, including the use of dedicated social media teams and localised expertise. Among the parties, PTI stands out for its pioneering and decentralised approach, which has enabled it to mobilise young people, overseas Pakistanis, and the urban elite more effectively than its rivals.

Taken together, these findings reveal that Twitter is not simply one tool among many, but a central arena where political narratives are constructed, contested, and disseminated. The next chapter builds on this analysis by examining how these practices intersect with the role of journalists and mainstream media in shaping political communication in Pakistan. These findings demonstrate that Twitter functions not merely as a site of political expression but as a strategically managed platform in which political actors actively construct and amplify narratives through cross-platform visibility. This deepens existing debates on political communication by showing how, in Pakistan's hybrid media environment, agenda formation increasingly emerges from interactions between political actors, journalists, and platform logics rather than from traditional institutional gatekeeping alone. The importance of this lies in highlighting how strategic communication practices shape political salience in contexts where media authority and digital platforms are closely intertwined.

Chapter 7: Twitter, Political Communication and the Evolving Media Landscape in Pakistan

7.1 Introduction

In this chapter, I examine the third theme emerging from analysis of interview data, the role of mainstream media and journalists in shaping political communication on Twitter in Pakistan. As previously discussed, political parties, the urban elite, young people, and overseas Pakistanis are actively engaging on Twitter, creating an elite domain within Pakistan's digital landscape. As Afsheen, Ahmed and Butt (2022) argue, despite the convergence of media and extensive Twitter usage in Pakistan, traditional electronic TV news media remain a popular medium, and the Twitter traffic of Pakistani journalists depends on their active presence on this conventional media. They argue that Twitter has fundamentally altered the dynamics of journalism affecting news generation, the duties of journalists, news gatekeeping, ethics and conventions of the profession. In this chapter, I demonstrate how mainstream media organisations and prominent journalists influence political communication through Twitter. Media outlets use institutional accounts, while journalists leverage their personal accounts to share programmes and, increasingly, to post polarising political content. This content reflects not only their professional roles but also their political affiliations, the pursuit of visibility through likes and retweets, and pressures from parties and organisations. The first part of the chapter establishes the presence of mainstream media organisations and journalists on Twitter, showing how their adoption of the platform has reconfigured news generation and circulation practices and positioned Twitter as a central arena for political information in Pakistan. This helps the reader to understand the dynamics of the digital sphere and the evolving relationship between social media platforms and mainstream news outlets before turning to how these actors frame content and build narratives. The second part draws on interview data to analyse how

the framing and posting practices of media outlets and journalists influence political communication, revealing how professional pressures, political affiliations, and the pursuit of digital visibility contribute to polarisation and perceptions of bias.

To complement the findings from the interview data, I also draw on examples from Twitter posts made by verified accounts of selected media channels and the most popular political journalists in Pakistan to illustrate the key arguments.

Main Themes	Description of the theme	Codes	Excerpts
The transformation of journalism and political communication through Twitter	This theme explores the platform's dual role as both a tool and a space for media actors, highlighting its impact on the dynamics of news dissemination, professional journalism, and political discourse	Presence of mainstream media and journalists on Twitter	“The mainstream media, all the major mainstream media in Pakistan, media institutions in Pakistan, have their verified Twitter accounts and they post on Twitter almost instantaneously and after every minute and sometimes after a few seconds” (J7)
		Twitter has changed the news operations mechanism.	“The media no longer needs to find the relevant leaders with a microphone and camera or a DSNG van. Instead, we see leaders often posting their videos on Twitter. Bilawal Bhutto has set a trend by tweeting his videos or statements. This is a significant change that has greatly affected the media industry” (J8)
		Twitter is the primary source of news.	“Now the formal media follows the line from social media. and among social media, in terms of political narrative, Twitter tops the trend in Pakistan” (P1).
		Twitter is working as a source and a consumer.	“Regarding whether mainstream media feeds off Twitter or vice versa, I think it's a two-way process. However, I feel that Twitter feeds more into mainstream media” (J7).

		Twitter as a challenge and opportunity for journalists	1) “Another dilemma for journalists in Pakistan is the massive polarisation into pro-PTI and anti-PTI camps. Neutral journalists face significant challenges”(J1). 2) “Journalists have also adopted a new approach where they tweet news that they cannot broadcast on TV or other news platforms”(J2).
		Political news framing by the media on Twitter	“well, the journalists sometimes drive the discourse on Twitter, political discourse on Twitter, and then the political parties, you know, carry forward that agenda” (J7).

Table 7.1 Sequence of the discussion as per thematic analysis of the interview data (self-contribution)

7.2 Presence of mainstream media and journalists on Twitter

Research on the relationship between Twitter and mainstream media in Pakistan suggests that the social media platform influences the structure and mechanisms of news gathering and generation. A study conducted on three major media outlets, Dawn, The News, and Express Tribune, revealed that these newspapers primarily present straightforward, episodic frames of news on Twitter. They often lack the detail, background, or context typically characteristic of mainstream media news structures (Ashfaq Shahid and Zubair, 2022).

This study’s findings demonstrate that major mainstream media organisations in Pakistan post stories on Twitter to target potential audience on elite digital sphere and using their verified Twitter accounts, post updates frequently, every day, or at the same time as they publish articles online. It demonstrates how mainstream media integrate Twitter into their core news distribution strategies. By posting through verified accounts in real time, often in parallel with their websites, they reinforce their credibility and ensure their narratives reach politically active and elite audiences. This highlights Twitter’s role as a parallel news space where media actively shape political communication. For example, senior journalist and anchor-person, J7, suggested that media organisations in Pakistan understand that Twitter and other social media platforms drive news traffic:

They (mainstream news media) have their verified Twitter accounts, and they post on Twitter almost instantaneously and after every minute and sometimes after a few seconds, they post their stories because they know that the traffic is driven from Twitter.

Furthermore, J2, who works with an international online media outlet in Pakistan highlighted that, “Twitter is a valid and accepted source of information in Pakistan. Mainstream media feeds off Twitter, and digital media does too”. As a result, these media channels maintain a strong presence on social media platforms. Several interviewees also expressed the view that it is essential to highlight the prevalence of mainstream media outlets and journalists on Twitter in Pakistan. Table 7.2 details the date of joining Twitter and the number of followers of mainstream media groups in Pakistan. According to the Global Media Registry’s project, Media Ownership Monitor (2022) in Pakistan, eight main media groups reach 68 per cent of the population in Pakistan. Based on available information on the audience of mainstream news media channels, I investigated their presence on Twitter. This data was manually searched from Twitter in October 2024. Column one represents the leading media group, and the second column indicates the news channels and newspapers owned by that media group. As context, these mainstream electronic news media channels in Pakistan are among the most popular in terms of viewership according to PEMRA (2025).

Jang and Geo Group	Geo TV	Joined July 2010	5.6M
	Jang Newspaper	Joined July 2010	1.0M
ARY.	ARY News Channel	Joined May 2013	5.8M
	ARY Urdu	Joined March 2014	3.5M
Dunya	Roznama Dunya	Joined September 2012	0.73M
	Dunya News	Joined December 2009	3.7M

Express Group	Express News	Joined October 2009	4.1M
State-Owned Media	Pakistan Television Corp.	Joined August 2011	1.8M
Samaa	Samaa TV	Joined February 2009	3.1M
Dawn	Dawn News	Joined July 2009	2.5M
	Dawn.com	Joined February 2011	1.4M
Nawa-e-Waqt Group	Waqt News TV	Joined September 2011	0.41M
	Daily Nawa-i-Waqt	Joined April 2009	0.43M
	The Nation	Joined May 2008	0.11M

Table 7.2 List of media groups, their presence and followers on Twitter, October 2024

Table 7.2 illustrates that most media groups in Pakistan joined Twitter between 2009 and 2014. It is clear from the table that the number of followers for television and electronic media is significantly higher than that for newspapers within the same media groups. For example, both Jang Newspaper and Geo TV belong to the same media group and joined Twitter on the same date. However, Geo TV has 5.6 million followers, while Jang Newspaper only has 1 million followers. In addition to these traditional media groups, there are digital media outlets, such as Siasat.pk, which operate independently and also have a substantial Twitter following. Siasat.pk has 2.3 million followers, while Independent Urdu has 343.1k followers. Other channels, like Aaj TV, have 1.3 million followers. Additionally, individual journalists on Twitter have amassed millions of followers. The significance of this presence lies in the way it illustrates how Twitter has become an integral part of Pakistan's political communication environment. The adoption of Twitter by mainstream media groups, combined with the large follower base of television channels compared to newspapers, reflects a shift towards immediacy, visibility, and influence in the elite digital sphere. This distinguishes Pakistan's case, where, despite relatively low internet penetration compared to some countries, Twitter functions as a disproportionately influential arena for political discourse. Alongside media organisations, individual journalists also command significant followings on Twitter. Their personal accounts

often attract audiences comparable to, or even greater than, those of established outlets, positioning them as influential actors in shaping political discourse. Table 7.3 details some of the most followed political journalists in Pakistan, along with their dates of joining and follower counts. Table 7.3 lists some of the most followed political journalists, along with their dates of joining Twitter and their follower counts. The data was collected directly from Twitter in October 2024.

Affiliation	Journalist	Twitter Milestone	Followers (millions)
Geo News	Hamid Mir	November 2010	8.5M
Bol Network	Saddique Jan	December 2012	2.3M
Youtuber	Imran Riaz	May 2013	5.9M
ARY News	Iqrar-ul-Hassan	January 2010	7.1M
Lucman TV	Mubasher Luqman	July 2009	5.8M
Hum News/BBC Urdu	Asma Shirazi	February 2011	3.8M
Jang Group	Umar Cheema	July 2011	1.6M
Channel 24	Nasim Zahra	May 2011	1.5M
Samaa TV	Syed Tallat Hussain	April 2011	3.8M
Neo News/Youtuber	Rauf Klasra	April 2013	2.3M

Table 7.3 List of most followed journalists on Twitter in Pakistan, October 2024

The table shows that individual journalists have more followers than many of the mainstream media outlets on Twitter. This is important as it alludes to the potential impact of journalists on shaping public opinion, specifically whether journalists adhere to a specific editorial policy established by the media outlets with which they are affiliated, or if they post political content based on their inclinations.

Scholars, including Pintak, Bowe and Nazir (2018) and Sarwar, Umber and Bajwa (2020) have indicated that mainstream media in Pakistan have always been polarised, and different media groups support the narratives of specific political parties. For instance, Sarwar et al (2020) note

that Pakistani media groups were polarised when reporting political news, either pro-PPP, anti-PPP, or neutral. The research also indicated that PPP boycotted Geo News for spreading a pro-PMLN narrative and taking a firm stand against the PPP regime (2008-2013). Bajwa also revealed that the PPP regime was supporting Express and Dunya News. During the PTI sit-in in Islamabad in 2014, ARY News, SAAMA, and Express News were on PTI's side, while Geo was defending the PMLN. My research explores if Twitter has inherited these biases and polarisations in Pakistan. After examining the presence of mainstream media outlets and individual journalists on Twitter in Pakistan, the following section highlights how Twitter has altered the functioning of news operations in the country. Understanding these evolving mechanisms is essential before exploring the role that media and journalists play in political communication.

7.2.1 Overlapping mainstream media and Twitter in Pakistan

In this section, I draw on interview findings to elaborate on the argument that Twitter is considered the primary source of information in Pakistani political news and updates, with mainstream media drawing its lead from the social media space. I also discuss how mainstream media and journalists frame messages and post links to their official websites or other social media handles on the platform to exploit the penetration of Twitter in the elite political circle in Pakistan. Studies show that Twitter is widely used as a news source in Pakistan. Research by Naz and Shafiq (2021) found that 73% of the 200 journalists surveyed reported using Twitter as a news source in their media organisations. Qaisar and Riaz (2020) note that Twitter often sets the agenda for the mainstream media in Pakistan. This study's findings, however, reveal that while journalists, politicians, and political parties' media managers consider Twitter to be an essential platform for political news updates, a degree of interdependence is at play. Study respondents considered Twitter to be both a source (a primary medium for news and updates) and a consumer (utilises news from mainstream media articles, blogs and video clips of the

prime-time shows are shared) of news. Evidence shows that traditional news patterns are changing due to Twitter's growing role as a news source. I found evidence that the military establishment, government officials, politicians, and other influential figures are now releasing their statements and press releases directly on Twitter, bypassing traditional media channels. For example, a senior journalist, J1, shared his observations on the evolution of news operations during his 18-year tenure in mainstream media. He highlighted that Twitter has significantly influenced this change, emphasising that the platform's primary focus is on news, current affairs, and the political arena:

If I say that 30-40% of our news content or political content comes from statements given on Twitter, it wouldn't be wrong. Earlier, it was common practice for politicians to be given the opportunity to speak on a programme, and their statements would be aired. Now, politicians themselves are present on Twitter, posting their statements, which are then available for news content.

This quote highlights several significant developments in Pakistan's news landscape. First, Twitter has emerged as a primary source of news. The active presence of political leaders and parties on Twitter allows their official statements to be quickly picked up by mainstream media outlets. These statements are then broadcast on television for the public. This process ensures that news also reaches those who do not use Twitter through more traditional mainstream media. Second, J1 suggests that before Twitter, political stories were filtered through press conferences, and through inviting politicians to TV programmes or talking to them directly. The emergence and development of Twitter have altered this dynamic, with less time spent chasing politicians for statements and more effort devoted to scanning Twitter for updates and notifications.

J1 also illustrated the role of Twitter as a consumer of news. He explained that if a politician is invited onto a TV programme and provides some interesting or new information, the social media teams assigned to gather news via social media platforms will upload the video content on Twitter from the official accounts of their media groups or via individual journalists. This is how Twitter utilises news generated from mainstream media and promotes it, meaning that news travels from Twitter to other digital spheres and vice versa. This interdependence among social media and traditional media strengthens the main argument I advance in this thesis about the role of Twitter in shaping political communication. Specifically, it highlights three key points.

First, political parties can post messages directly on Twitter, which significantly amplifies their reach and impact. This platform not only allows them to engage with their audience but also enhances the political narratives that are broadcast by mainstream media, making these narratives more prominent in public discourse. Additionally, Twitter provides a steady stream of political content that feeds into mainstream media coverage, creating a loop where online discussions influence traditional news outlets and vice versa. This interconnectedness plays a crucial role in shaping public opinion and political discourse.

Furthermore, considering the biases that often accompany mainstream media and journalists when reporting on political news, Twitter presents a unique opportunity to influence the evolution of political communication significantly. This dynamic emphasises the vital role Twitter plays in shaping political discourse today. In a post by the ARY news channel, which boasts 5.8 million followers on Twitter, concern was raised about the PTI protest scheduled for October 26, 2024. The outlet highlighted a critical angle involving senior politician Ali Amin Gandapur and Bushra Bibi, wife of former Prime Minister Imran Khan. The headline read, “PTI protest faces setback as Bushra Bibi and Gandapur disappear” (ARY, 2024). This framing paints a picture of disarray within PTI leadership, suggesting that they left the protest abruptly,

without informing their supporters who had travelled from various cities to join them. The narrative raises questions about the leadership's commitment and ability to guide their supporters effectively during a crucial moment.

The post includes a link to the complete news story, along with a video hosted on the channel about the development. The story emphasises that the workers in the protest were unable to convince Bushra Bibi and Ali Amin Gandapur to lead them, and both leaders left the protesters abandoned at the D Chowk in Islamabad. This scenario illustrates how mainstream media, influenced by their own editorial policies and business interests, plays a vital role in shaping public discourse. By utilising Twitter to share their coverage, they enhance their viewership while simultaneously contributing to the political communication landscape. Moreover, the inclusion of statements from politicians made during their interactions with mainstream media further underscores the media's role as a key stakeholder in Pakistan's political communication on social media. This multifaceted interplay between mainstream media and politics and Twitter exemplifies the importance of the platform in contemporary news dissemination and public engagement in Pakistan.

7.2.2 Redefining news gathering and reporting in the Twitter era

Twitter has also played a significant role in changing how mainstream media news operations and political communication operate in Pakistan:

Now, a tweet from the DG ISPR (Director General of Inter-Services Public Relations) signifies that something significant is about to happen, and within a few minutes, the tweet comes out. The screenshots of this information are displayed on TV, which means that the information appearing on TV is coming through Twitter, and Twitter is being credited. Mainstream media has accepted Twitter as a source. (J2)

A good example of the change in political news operations facilitated by Twitter is in how politicians' chosen narratives are pushed out to the wider public. J2 suggested that in 2010, a female colleague indicated that the TV ticker and the scrolling news strip would eventually shift to Twitter in Pakistan. Furthermore, in 2015, when J2 was covering an all-party closed-door, in-camera conference, waiting for a spokesperson to come out and brief the media about the proceedings, one of the participating political leaders was posting frequent updates on Twitter. As J2 suggested, "I was following him, and he was tweeting live about what was happening inside the meeting." When he realised the potential importance of these updates being posted on Twitter directly from the closed-door meeting, J2 shared them on his channel and the mainstream media outlet he was working for, and the other reporters started receiving calls from their TV channels asking them to share updates too, as J2's channel was stealing a march on them.

Furthermore, J2 noted that the shift in news operations has not been embraced only by the media and politicians. Significant organisations, such as the Inter-Services Public Relations (ISPR) and other public relations wings of security organisations, have also adapted, impacting news gathering, generating and dissemination in the broader political news sphere in Pakistan. In the past, updates were sent to media organisations via DVDs, then transitioned to FTP downloads. Eventually, WhatsApp groups for beat reporters were established to share press releases with one another. Twitter has added a new dimension to this communication between journalists and the political powers:

This is a way for political parties to interact with the public. For any issue, propaganda, information, or event, if Imran Khan wants to give his reaction, he does so through a tweet. Thousands to millions of people respond to him and Maryam Nawaz within minutes, and the speed of retweets can be in the thousands. (J2)

J2 provided examples of trends and issues that became major news stories of the day, including the DG ISPR's tweet "Notification Rejected," which was posted in response to an inquiry team's findings in the wake of a news report published by the prominent news outlet, Dawn. The news was about the in-camera meeting of higher officials of security forces. As highlighted by Rahman and Shurong (2024) and Upadhyay, (2019), the then Federal Minister for Information had to resign because of the pressure he faced due to the news leaked by Dawn. "Many of Imran Khan's tweets provoke reactions and responses, while if Maryam Nawaz goes silent on Twitter, it becomes news". For instance, following a post from the official social media lead Jibran Ilyas made on 20th April 2022, at the advent of the ousting of former Prime Minister Imran Khan about a historic Twitter space conducted by the PTI social media team strengthens the argument brought forward by J2. This historic Twitter space, which was attended by 165K+ people, was published by mainstream media outlets.

Thank you all for attending the historic [#ImranKhanLIVE](#) Twitter Space. Thanks to @TwitterSpaces for increasing limits, we were able to get to 164K+. The previous record was around 57K, we beat that by 100,000+. Loved the heartfelt questions & responses! [#امپورٹڈ حکومت نامنظور](#) (PTI 2022).

The hashtag used in the above post [#امپورٹڈ_حکومت_نامنظور](#) (Imported government not accepted) was used by Imran Khan. According to Pakistan Today (Jaffery, 2022), an English news media outlet, the hashtag became a historic trend, with ten million posts created using this trend, many other news media outlets, such as The Express Tribune, Pakistan Frontier, and News360.

These examples shared by J2 and extracted from Twitter establish how an event organised on the platform (space conducted by PTI), a trend generated on the same platform, was covered by mainstream media. Additionally, in terms of changes, J1 highlighted that "if a news channel misses a story, it is considered a failure of the social media desk, unlike the traditional pre-

social media era when reporters were held responsible for missed stories”. J5, an anchor person and senior journalist in one of the leading news media channels suggested:

Every channel now has social media desks that follow Twitter feeds and Facebook feeds, and they pick up news from these social media channels and follow them. The production teams of mainstream media programmes ensure that parts of the programme, especially those with high news value, whether in the form of videos or statements, are posted on Twitter. It is also posted what we are going to discuss in today's programme, and feedback from users is taken.

However, J8, a senior journalist, suggested that Twitter works more as a source:

Twitter is doing it more because, as I mentioned, all major political leaders have Twitter accounts. All these leaders are directly present on Twitter, making it the easiest way for their followers and supporters to interact with them.

J4, who works with an international media outlet in Pakistan, supported the same argument and acknowledged that conventional media followed the same news stream from Twitter, “like for me, like I'm running a newsroom most of the time, I pinned my story from Twitter”. Similarly, J5, a senior journalist and broadcaster, suggested:

You do see Twitter having a decisive edge because Twitter is fast. It doesn't have those restrictions that apply to normal journalistic platforms and mediums where you have to apply your editorial judgement.

This indicates that despite Twitter cannot be considered journalism in the conventional sense, but in practice it functions as such for journalists, political parties, and the public in Pakistan. Journalists increasingly treat it as a news source, political actors use it as a channel to bypass editorial filters, and citizens consume it as if it were equivalent to mainstream reporting. This blurring of boundaries between journalism and social media highlights the hybrid nature of

contemporary political communication (Hermida, 2010). J3, a senior journalist working with online media and covering the Sindh province in Pakistan for more than a decade, agreed that Twitter feeds more news to mainstream media. She suggested that “Twitter has become a 'fourth pillar' of the state, which influences policymakers as a powerful journalism tool”. She also gave an example of a Twitter campaign of Jamat-e-Islami in Karachi city, which influenced many progressive groups supportive of other political parties to vote for Hafiz Naeem.

M2 also noted that Twitter provides better access for political parties to disseminate news than explaining it to individual reporters and channels. When a journalist breaks a story through their channel, there is a chance that other channels might miss it. However, if it is posted on Twitter, the social media desks of all channels monitor these updates and capture important political developments.

Furthermore, M2 mentioned that Twitter has changed the dynamic of the media's race to get the first "soundbite." He described Twitter as a “platform where updates on political activities are readily available, and users can instantly share their opinions”. While talking about preferences for political communication, he suggested that on Twitter, if an opinion resonates with others, they can easily retweet it, highlighting the post in a way that is not possible with mainstream media. He also emphasised that his political party, prefers to use Twitter because it allows party leaders to engage directly with the public through Twitter Spaces:

This format enables them to speak as long as they need, unlike TV shows, which have limited airtime and often include other guests, hindering the ability to convey the party's narrative effectively.

He believed that Twitter is the primary source of political news for people in Pakistan. In the case of mainstream media, he said, “Because they also pick up things from Twitter. So people

go for the alpha, and that's the source” (M2). These findings indicate that the tools of political communication have evolved in Pakistan. The mainstream media, which had a decisive edge as the outlet for political campaigning, is now accessing its news feeds from social media platforms, particularly Twitter. This is supported by Naz and Shafiq (2021), who found that journalists in Pakistan increasingly rely on Twitter as a real-time source of political news, using it to track breaking developments, statements from political actors, and public discourse trends, although traditional verification processes remain in place.

Figure 7.1 illustrates how Twitter functions as both a source and consumer of news, simultaneously. According to the findings presented in the preceding section, Twitter acts as a news source in scenarios where politicians share their comments, party activities, or statements about new developments, especially when they are not easily accessible for direct communication but are active on Twitter. The upper part of the diagram represents Twitter as a source of news.

Figure 7.1 Twitter as source and consumer of news in Pakistan (self-contribution)

Senior journalist, J2, highlighted the importance of social media desks within news organisations in Pakistan, which serve two primary purposes. First, they disseminate the organisation's publications by sharing them on platforms like Twitter, Instagram, Facebook, and YouTube. Second, they monitor daily Twitter trends to identify topics of public interest and incorporate public opinions and tweets into their news coverage, reflecting what people are saying about specific issues. As J2 highlighted, "trending topics on social media are used to create video packages and write articles for that day". This suggests that political parties' efforts to shape Twitter trends are a strategy to influence mainstream media and journalists. This is also linked with the remarks provided by M3 about the use of Twitter only for targeting social media.

Twitter consumes news when journalists upload stories after discussions with prominent figures or the social media desk. Journalists also share noteworthy excerpts from their reports or reactions from political figures regarding recent events. The lower part of Figure 7.1 represents Twitter as a news consumer. According to journalists, mainstream media channels monitor all verified accounts of senior politicians and political parties. Their social media teams ensure that they do not miss any significant updates. For example, as J3 suggests, "if there is a targeted killing or any other major incident, they will observe how political leaders from that particular province react and what statements they issue in response". Mainstream media often take those statements from Twitter and report them as breaking news. Journalists also use Twitter to observe how law enforcement agencies respond to various situations and what measures they implement.

In many cases, statements from these agencies are sourced from Twitter, as they often post updates based on the importance of the elite circle and the influence of opinion makers. "We make sure not to miss any of their movements". In addition to the reactions of politicians to

incidents, journalists also monitor their political activities, meetings, and community work. Politicians frequently update this information on Twitter:

For instance, the no-confidence vote story I broke was based on following their tweets and verifying with my sources. While others were speculating, I broke the story by closely monitoring the tweets and sources. (J3)

J4, who has worked with Pakistani mainstream media for over a decade and is currently collaborating with international media, noted that Twitter sometimes provides valuable clues for further investigation into issues that mainstream media might otherwise overlook. She acknowledged that she often uses Twitter to gather insights and expand on them. Furthermore, J5 said that media, politicians, and everyone monitor Twitter; he can find big statements, breaking news, big claims, and acquisitions made, and that is the reason he monitors his Twitter feed carefully:

They have direct medium, and they can, you know, put out the news through their Twitter accounts. And mainstream media will have to pick it up because, you know, these are authentic, sometimes blue-ticked Twitter accounts, and they are authentic sources

J8 explained the political news mechanism, saying that statements are made on Twitter and responses are given on that platform. Political leaders also highlight their party performances on Twitter and react to social issues on the same platform. The immediacy of Twitter means that the media landscape has undergone significant changes. The media no longer needs to find the relevant leaders with a microphone and camera or a DSNG (Digital Satellite News Gathering) van to telecast political developments. Instead, leaders often post their videos on Twitter. Bilawal Bhutto, for instance, has set a trend by tweeting his videos or statements. Hence, the above findings suggest that social media, particularly Twitter, has changed the

mechanism of news generation, gathering and dissemination. It indicates a change in the mechanism of political communication in Pakistan as noted by Ashfaq, Shahid and Zubair (2022) Mainstream media are adopting news framing from Twitter. In the next section, I present findings that elaborate on news content and the role of media and journalists in the existing and evolving political news mechanism in Pakistan.

7.2.3 Breaking the monopoly: Twitter's challenge to mainstream media

Senior journalist J2 suggested that Twitter has challenged the mainstream electronic media's monopoly in Pakistan. He maintained that the public largely disregards traditional electronic media and newspapers; instead, social media platforms, particularly Twitter, significantly influence the narrative, "No one cares what electronic media is saying and what the newspapers are suggesting, so social media now dominates the narrative, and others just follow". He termed Twitter a "basic" medium and other media "supplementary" mediums. Twitter has become a pivotal tool in journalism, almost like a fourth estate, influencing opinion-making. In addition to journalists, media managers shared their insights about Twitter's role in the media landscape. For example, the social media head of a political party, M2, pointed out that:

mainstream media in Pakistan has damaged its credibility due to its commercial interests, leading people to seek more authentic news on Twitter. As a result, political parties now post every news update and statement on Twitter, which traditional media then pick up and use for their reporting.

He mentioned that his party turned towards social media due to the perceived bias of mainstream media, the restrictions on media coverage of his party, and, most importantly, the ease of reaching people through social media. These findings relate to the research conducted by Saeed *et al.* (2021) who found that students in the University of Lahore (Punjab) consider mainstream media in Pakistan non-credible.

Senior anchor person, political analyst and YouTuber, J5, pointed out that “Twitter has fewer restrictions and there are no editorial policies to filter views or news, allowing people to express themselves freely”. He noted that people can easily "shoot" whatever they want since it is readily available at their fingertips. Due to these practical features, he emphasised that “Twitter has become the go-to platform for breaking news and opinions”. He also argued that sometimes, “it drives the coverage of mainstream media as so many stories are sourced from social media, especially Twitter, as the major political leadership has a verified account on Twitter, currently X”. J7 also expressed the view that:

If someone in Pakistan is following Twitter, it is highly unlikely that they will miss any major political news. However, if they are following mainstream media, there is a chance that they might miss some of the nuances in political communication.

This is because prominent political leaders of the main political parties in Pakistan have Twitter accounts and are directly present on Twitter, making it the easiest way for their followers and supporters to interact with them. They can tweet something and tag the leaders. There is no doubt that Twitter is not only leading and feeding political discourse to the media, but it also shows that whenever a leader makes a statement, they usually use Twitter:

As a result, mainstream media often refers to these Twitter statements, saying, 'Imran Khan tweeted this statement on social media.' The same goes for other political leaders.

This is a common trend across the board. (M3)

M3, the social media head of one of the selected political parties, however, stated that his party uses both social and mainstream media simultaneously and does not rely solely on social media to disseminate its news. As a political party whose target audience consists of low-income workers, they recognise that their potential voters may not be active on social media, unlike another political party which views itself as a party for young people. The social media teams

of the political party which claims to have young supporters believe they can reach the grassroots levels through their connected networks. However, M3 acknowledged that his party posts updates on Twitter in the hope that mainstream media will pick them up as that is where they feel they can reach their largest constituency. The findings align with research by Qayyoom *et al.* (2022), which examined the news about economic issues that transition between traditional media and Twitter in Pakistan. Their study identified a correlation between the news coverage agendas of Twitter and mainstream media. Fifty-seven days of coverage from Twitter and mainstream media news channels were analysed, and it was found that “a one-day time lag exists between transferring of agendas from Twitter to traditional media” (p. 63). The research concluded that mainstream media takes its line from Twitter trends and updates. Twitter is a platform for sharing information it is not a news channel. The findings indicate that it is viewed as a publisher of news in the context of Pakistan politicians, journalists and public.

The social media head, M4, expressed the view that people often have limited time to watch TV, and he noted that “social and mainstream media do not function in tandem for political communication in Pakistan”. Politicians from all three political parties expressed a similar pattern of views. P1, who has served as the Federal Minister for Information and Broadcasting believes that “social media has replaced traditional media as the primary platform for shaping political narratives”. He stated that Twitter is regarded as “the main source of political news and has significantly impacted political communication in Pakistan”. He argued that all political parties, including the Prime Minister and various ministries, prefer using Twitter to make announcements. He considers Twitter to be the primary platform for policy announcements in Pakistan.

Politicians from all three major political parties interviewed emphasised the importance of Twitter in news operations in Pakistan. However, politicians from one of the main political

parties (P3, P4) held the view that mainstream media has not completely lost its significance. Instead, they argued that Twitter has just added a new dimension to political communication alongside other social media platforms like TikTok and Facebook. In fact, P4 argued that mainstream media programmes continue to provide a platform for politicians to establish and explain their party stance on political or national developments, in detail. Social media head, M3, was of the view that they use Twitter to attract mainstream media, but they do use other social media platforms for the propagation of their party narrative and run political campaigns.

In this section, I have outlined Twitter's pivotal role in shaping political communication in Pakistan. I have laid the groundwork for a deeper analysis of how news operations have evolved in this digital landscape. The findings show that Twitter is the dominant force in this arena. However, traditional media continues to play a significant role, often sourcing news from Twitter or contributing content that feeds into the platform.

As the preceding discussion establishes, Twitter is considered easy to access, with few restrictions, no editorial policies, and everyone who has the access and digital literate can post about political developments. However, there is evidence that this license to comment has also facilitated more hate and disinformation in society. For instance, J2 noted that “Until some time ago, especially in electronic print and digital media, there were issues with fake accounts. People would tweet, and TV channels would immediately broadcast it as breaking news”. He gave another example of the effect of fake accounts, highlighting that, “In the UK, there's an institution called Independent, and there is a mock account called Dependent to deceive people. They tweet something, and it becomes breaking news on Pakistani media”. He also commented on the credibility and authenticity of individual accounts on Twitter:

The funny thing is, we often don't know who is actually talking. Whether Waseem Ahmad is real or not, or if Rashid is a real person, we don't know. It's possible that these

are fake accounts. Two unknown people, about whom there's no certainty of existence, are just computers fighting. These computers continue to fight until one of them becomes exhausted or the shift changes.

Ahmed, Saeed and Alam (2024) highlighted the prevalence of fake accounts for political mobilisation in Pakistan, building on a study conducted about the role of fake accounts on Twitter during the 2016 US presidential elections (Grinberg *et al.*, 2019). J2 also indicated that this information is received everywhere via social media platforms and people accept it without verification. M3 talked about one of the prominent former social media team members who created “25-30 celebrity, accounts”. These accounts provided updates that seemed authentic, as many people did not know how social media worked and there were no verification checks. As M3 suggests, “These fake accounts, some gaining followers between 25,000 to 50,000, would push political trends alongside updates from these supposed celebrities”. P2 and P3 also indicated that disinformation and hate spread through Twitter. P3 suggested that “Twitter is the source of information, you learn something new, but you can also make it into an instrument of hate speech at times, which is unfortunate”. These findings can be contextualised by considering literacy levels in Pakistan, which remain at around 60%, with pronounced disparities across provinces, including higher literacy rates in Punjab (approximately 66.3%) and Sindh (around 57%), compared to substantially lower levels in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (about 51.1%) and Balochistan (approximately 42%) (Gallup Pakistan, 2024). Literacy rates also vary significantly by age and location; for instance, the highest literacy levels are observed among 13–14-year-olds living in urban areas, where literacy reaches 88.8%, a demographic group that largely falls below voting age (Gallup Pakistan, 2024). However, literacy alone does not ensure meaningful engagement with political content on digital platforms. Digital literacy the ability to critically assess, interpret, and navigate content online remains limited, especially given that percentage of all literate individuals is between 13–14 years old, live in urban areas,

and are below voting age. As Ali and Qazi (2022) note, low levels of digital literacy in Pakistan hinder users' ability to recognise misinformation and algorithmic manipulation, making it difficult to engage critically with political messaging on platforms like Twitter and Facebook. These algorithmic systems tend to reinforce users' existing beliefs by directing them toward content that aligns with their previous preferences, further narrowing their exposure to diverse viewpoints.

7.3 Political news framing on Twitter: navigating challenges and opportunities for the media

The findings demonstrate that Twitter is the preferred medium for political communication in most cases in Pakistan. However, it is also important to explore how the platform is used by media and journalists themselves to frame news and to assess whether the polarisation present in mainstream media is also prevalent on social media, particularly Twitter. Pintak et al. (2018) identified the reasons behind mainstream media biases, finding that in Pakistan, even after the 2001 PEMRA regulation, the media continued to serve the elites, and the individual media organisations were polarised due to their alliances with political camps. The PEMRA ordinance, enacted by then-President Pervez Musharraf, licensed private media channels for the first time in Pakistan's history, freeing the media from direct state control.

Researchers such as Saeed *et al.* (2021) indicate that the mainstream media has lost credibility among young people, who now prefer social media for updates on political developments in Pakistan. Given the growing significance of social media platforms and the prominent role journalists play on Twitter in Pakistan, it is crucial to examine how they operate on the platform and whether biases evident in the pre-Twitter era persist ul Haq, Hussain and ud Din (2024) suggest that the emergence of digital media has introduced new complexities to journalistic and media operations by removing the traditional editorial or gatekeeping role. This shift exposes journalists and media organisations directly to audiences, subjecting them to

commentary, criticism, misinformation, hate speech, and trolling. The findings of my research indicate that Twitter has provided an opportunity for many journalists. For instance, according to J1:

A low-profile journalist, either freelance or associated with a small local media organisation, who posts an important story on Twitter. This story gains traction and is subsequently picked up by mainstream media organisations, spreading further through the journalist's individual Twitter account.

Twitter provides a platform for journalists to share stories they may not be able to publish through more established channels. It also highlights the positive role of Twitter from a democratic perspective, as it provides a space for marginalised voices and issues to be heard as part of public discourse in Pakistan. The platform has provided an opportunity for journalists to post news they cannot broadcast on mainstream media channels. The data also suggests that journalists can also challenge posts made by politicians. For instance, J2, working with mainstream electronic media indicated that he had experienced the positive impact of Twitter. As Graves (2016) notes, the rise of social media has expanded the scope and urgency of fact-checking practices, allowing journalists to contest misinformation at the point of dissemination. Similarly, Brandtzaeg and Følstad (2017) argue that platforms like Twitter can serve as essential arenas for accountability, where journalists and informed users publicly challenge the accuracy of political statements. J2 shared how he could challenge a tweet made by Imran Khan:

When Imran Khan claimed that 1.2 million people left the country due to poor conditions, I tweeted my 2020 report, which mentioned that his government aimed to send 800,000 people abroad due to COVID-19 restrictions. This served to counter his claim.

J3, a senior journalist working in a prominent news outlet in Karachi, Sindh province, shared how she could help a madrasa abuse victim by sharing a video of the child who was brutally beaten in Karachi Madrasa. Local law enforcement agencies took notice of the post, and the culprits were arrested as a result, “Karachi police responded to my Tweet”, she added. The task, which would otherwise be performed by some mainstream media outlet, was done by the journalist’s individual efforts on Twitter. J4, who works with an international media outlet and refrains from posting on political developments due to her organisational policy, also pointed out the positive aspects of Twitter in Pakistan. She illustrated the importance of Twitter for highlighting those important stories that would otherwise not have been covered:

There are many good people in Pakistan, activists, and journalists who highlight the issues on Twitter, which are totally blackout from the mainstream media. They are the hope for me, for us, then we take that story from Twitter, which is nowhere else, and then we develop it (J4).

Interview data findings also indicate that journalists play a role in shaping political communication by providing real-time developments, expert opinions, and news feedback:

When we attend events like Supreme Court hearings, we share real-time happenings with our offices and tweet simultaneously so that people can see it. Some people are followed because they tweet from the Parliament, offering inside news. Others cover the Supreme Court, defense, or foreign policy, gaining followers interested in these areas. Each journalist has a niche and followers rely on them for specific content. Many of my followers, for example, are there because I share my news links and get responses on my tweets and feedback. (J2)

Having said that, findings of this study suggest that political journalists using Twitter in Pakistan to interact with the posts of politicians and political parties, sharing and commenting

on political developments, and with a substantial number of followers, are influential actors in the media space, helping to propagate a political party's messages. In the absence of any clear social media regulations in place in Pakistan, highlighted by Al Abd (2022), the study findings indicate that mainstream media and journalists play a significant role in shaping the narrative coming from the political parties by framing those messages in their posts, commenting and criticising or appreciating political statements coming from the political parties.

Party media heads claimed that the mainstream news media is one of their target audiences on Twitter. M3, the social media lead, for instance, said that they share content on Twitter to be picked up by the media to reach a wider public. A senior journalist working in a mainstream English language newspaper, J7, stated that:

journalists in Pakistan are contributing and shaping political communication because they are tweeting, retweeting, commenting, and criticising politicians and political parties. They are practising journalism on Twitter by asking questions and then reporting their comments to the mainstream media by sharing video clips from their shows or sharing links from their YouTube channels.

Hence, Twitter serves as a vital platform for journalists in Pakistan, enabling them to amplify marginalised voices, challenge political narratives, and engage with real-time developments. The dynamic interaction between journalists and their followers creates a space for important stories to emerge, often bypassing traditional media constraints. However, despite these advantages, the use of Twitter also presents various challenges for journalists that warrant further examination. I now explore the complexities and obstacles they face to hold objectivity, neutrality and question political narratives while navigating this influential platform.

7.3.1 Ethical challenges and pressures for journalists

This section presents findings on the influence of personal biases and political affiliations among journalists in Pakistan, particularly in their engagement on Twitter. It highlights the tendency for journalists to support specific political parties, leading to inconsistent reporting and criticism. The analysis reveals a lack of organisational restrictions on personal expressions, underscoring the impact of individual beliefs on public discourse and the resulting polarisation in political conversations. It indicates that social media exacerbates the problems rather than resolving them. J7 suggested that:

Sometimes the journalists become parties (supporting specific political parties, taking their side) also, and they become, you know, critical of one set of parties and supportive of another set of parties.

He considers Twitter as a polarising factor, also in terms of politics. A senior anchor-person, J1, suggested that:

Journalists share their opinions about posts by the political party official accounts or party representatives' personal biases and likes and dislikes play a role; journalists criticise some political parties but refrain from criticising other parties.

The information provided by senior journalist and anchor-person, J1, also indicates that journalists' personal opinions and biases play a role. It indicates that journalists do not simply post on Twitter on behalf of their respective media organisational policies. None of the journalists working with Pakistani media outlets highlighted restrictions placed upon them by their respective news organisations for posting on Twitter or any other social media platforms. J2 elaborated on this phenomenon further when suggesting that:

Sometimes, interesting tweets prompt comments from journalists, who then share their opinions. Personal preferences and biases also play a role. For instance, if someone

favours the PML-N, they might not criticise PML-N leaders but will criticise PTI leaders by quoting or replying to their tweets.

For example, prominent journalist Rauf Klasra reposted a tweet by Neo TV on November 28, 2024, about the post-PTI protest development, indicating within-party rifts within the PTI. The tweet had a video from the programme of Rauf Klasra himself because he works as an anchorperson in the news channel, “I am answerable for my deeds to Imran Khan only, not to his family, Salman Akram Raja (PTI leader)’s blunt response to Bushra Bibi; is political leadership in PTI compromised?”(Neo TV, 2024)

Klasra is analysing the situation that arose after November 26, when the PTI leadership called off a protest organised following the final call given by PTI leader Imran Khan. He refers to the internal conflicts within PTI and highlights a heated argument between Salman Akram Raja and Bushra Bibi (Imran Khan's wife). During this exchange, Bushra asked Salman why he had not joined the protest, to which he bluntly replied that he did not feel accountable to anyone except Imran Khan. There are points in this post that complement the interview findings. Firstly, it shows how mainstream media, individual journalists and Twitter are inseparable. A narrative which was presented to the channel audience was posted on Twitter for the audience of this sphere particularly. It is also important to note that Rauf Klasra has more followers on Twitter than the TV channel he works for, as he has been working in the media for decades and is known for his work with other leading media groups like Dunya Channel. Comparing the Dunya channel and Rauf Klasra’s followers from Table 6.1 and 6.2, it is also evident that the journalist has more followers, and his Tweets reach a wider audience.

Secondly, after the 26th November situation, Rauf Klasra was framing and highlighting the rifts within PTI. On the other hand, Imran Riaz Khan, another one of the most followed journalists on Twitter, was criticising the sitting government (PMLN) and the other major political party,

PPP, for conducting a clearing operation in D Chowk Islamabad and firing at people. He was not framing problems within PTI. On the 28th of November 2024, he posted an artificial intelligence-generated photo of D-Chowk Islamabad, showing all of the roads flooded red with blood instead of using an original photo of the event. He wrote, “In search of the question of why the crime scene was washed immediately after Benazir's martyrdom, People's Party, along with PML-N, washed the crime scene of D Chowk” (Riaz 2024). It refers to the journalist framing the deaths and martyrdom side of the event. The post was viewed 820k times, and was retweeted 18k times, and liked 35k times. The journalist has created a relationship between Benazir Bhutto's death and the cleaning operation at D Chowk and said that PPP and PMLN have washed D Chowk crime scenes as it was washed in BB's case. This shows that journalists use AI as well to post on Twitter in Pakistan. Umar Cheema, another popular senior journalist on Twitter, pointed out the post made by Imran Riaz, highlighting the image used in the post as AI-generated and fake in his post on 29th of November 2024. The post attracted 152k views, 3.1 k likes and 1.3k reposts. There is a clear difference in the reach of the posts made by both journalists. Translation of the post made by Umar Cheema is as “If someone runs fake news by mistake, it is forgivable, but if someone is pointed out repeatedly but does not even bother to delete it, then will it be considered journalism [@ImranRiazKhan](#)? Another 'truthful' journalist is angry as to why I objected to his fake news. The number of shares and likes also indicate the possibility of the popularity of the comment made using AI images” (Cheema, 2024).

Interview data suggests that journalists in Pakistan working for international organisations tend to refrain from posting personal opinions on social media platforms like Twitter because they follow organisational policies. J4, who runs a newsroom for an international news organisation in Pakistan, said “I take many storylines from Twitter for further investigation and developing

news stories but refrain from posting personal opinions about political developments or statements from political leaders.”

These illustrations align with the comments made by J2 about the role of journalists in narrative building. Journalists who have followings in the millions effectively frame political developments according to their individual perceptions and followers endorse those perceptions in the form of likes and reposts. As J2 said:

Some fellow journalists play a significant role in building the narratives of various political parties. Almost all the journalists covering PTI, except for one or two, appear to be working as PTI workers on social media. Similarly, many friends who cover PML-N sometimes seem to be promoting the PML-N agenda.

The former Federal Minister for Information and Broadcasting, P3, discussed the issue of narrative-building and the potential bias among journalists. He noted that individuals have their own preferences and inclinations, which can influence how journalists share content on social media. According to him, journalists often post based on their personal inclinations rather than as representatives of their media organisations. Similarly, senior politician and the former Federal Minister for Information, a senator since 2018 from, P2, “suggested that the bias from journalists can have many reasons for social media”. According to him, journalists might post according to their political preferences:

They might like Mr A instead of Mr B, so they post like that. Secondly, according to P2, political parties can request that journalists support their narrative.

Journalist interviewees like J3 indicated that the polarisation apparent in the mainstream media is reflected on Twitter through journalists and their biases. This can be related to the remarks by J5, who has a media team to research for his TV show for a prime-time show. He focuses

on the issues he prefers to post on Twitter which he takes for his channel as well. According to J3:

Major journalists have become biased. Each has their own reasons, but they end up promoting their favourite political personalities through their accounts. For instance, if I like Maryam Nawaz, I will promote her positively on my account, ignoring any negatives.

However, according to J2, it was not necessarily the impact of mainstream media; it was about journalism, the journalist, “for example, Tweets of Hamid Mir, Naseem Zahra, and Kamran Khan contribute. They promote messages”. Prominent journalist J1, however, suggested that the polarisation on Twitter in terms of political communication was exacerbated by digital journalists who started journalism on their own for money and fame. He said that they post biased content to get likes and earn money:

A genuine journalist with a proper journalism degree hasn't played that kind of role. But digital journalists who have gained fame using digital platforms, like those who rose to fame because of YouTube likes and hits, have played a significant role. This has damaged journalistic ethics and norms. If you look at the thumbnails of these digital media journalists, they deviate greatly from journalistic values. They mislead, offend, and use abusive language because, for dollars, hits, and likes, they never bother to look back at journalistic values.

This observation highlights a critical transformation in journalism's political economy, where the platform logic of Twitter facilitates a shift from institutional journalism to individualised, market-driven content production. In this context, journalists are no longer just reporters but also content creators, brand builders, and entrepreneurs. This aligns with scholarly work on the entrepreneurial turn in journalism. Diaz Ruiz (2025) highlights how some actors make money

from digital platforms. The market encourages them to create content that can go viral, which leads to financial rewards for sharing controversial claims, confrontational stories, and false information. Manzoor and Shahzad (2024) indicated in their research how financial pressures cause journalists to compromise basic journalism ethics in Pakistan. Manzoor and Shahzad (2024) also found that the Pakistan Press Foundation has asked journalists to follow a code of ethics but there is no mechanism in place to ensure that journalists adhere to it. This suggests that digital platforms encourage journalists to adopt roles shaped by market incentives where visibility, monetisation, and audience engagement increasingly shape editorial decisions. As such, the rise of digital journalists operating outside traditional norms represents not only a departure from ethical journalism but also a broader reconfiguration of journalism's professional boundaries and economic structures. The impact of the monetisation phenomenon was indicated by social media lead, M4:

You see this (mainstream media's) polarised effect on Twitter too. However, since social media became monetised, journalists' views have been influenced by likes and views, chasing trends rather than providing genuine perspectives. Before monetisation, journalists were considered to provide genuine views. Now, they follow the public pulse and run after views. It was said before that journalists were influenced by money from political parties, taking advantage of their following on Twitter for political gain

The remarks from M4 indicate that journalism practice is affected by social media, particularly due to monetisation trends. He indicates that journalists are compromising their professional ethics to get likes, followers and money, and this makes them refrain from reporting neutrally. Their posts are driven by public likes instead of impartiality. M4 also indicates that journalists were influenced by the money from political parties, indicating that social media has added a new challenge for the profession of journalism. The National Union of Journalists (NUJ) (2021), representing UK journalists, code of ethics for social media emphasises that journalists,

while using media to gather information and disseminate it, should consider sending their posts to the public. Acknowledging that every individual has opinions, likes, and dislikes as a member of society, the code of ethics stresses that journalists should refrain from presenting their personal opinions on social media, as this might influence the opinions of their followers. Existing journalists' unions, including the Pakistan Union of Journalists, the Rawalpindi Union of Journalists, and the National Press Club in Pakistan, have developed codes of conduct for journalism practice but remain silent to date about ethical considerations for journalists when posting on social media (NPC Islamabad, PFUJ 2025).

Zaman (2023) has noted that journalistic norms and ethics are compromised more on social media than on mainstream media because of the absence of editorial control. Research which compared coverage of the same news stories on mainstream media and social media noted that fake information is circulated easily on social media because of the absence of any checks and controls. Interview findings also suggest that high-profile journalists have social media teams who research the trends and topics for them to respond to and post about. For instance, senior journalist, J5, who has been working in Pakistani news media for more than two decades and enjoys 3.7 million followers on Twitter, said that he has a social media team to look for the subjects where his tweets will generate debate. He also mentioned that the content is usually hardcore news about which he can take to his news channel prime time news and current affairs show. This also suggests the link journalists create between mainstream and social media. It also indicates the shift in journalists' role after the advent of social media in Pakistan. The posts on Twitter are made on political developments, which generate debate, and journalists post their analysis on the developments after confirming the authenticity of the news. There is evidence that politicians do not need journalists for news as a medium anymore; they can directly post on Twitter, "journalists put that news or statements made by politicians in the context and present analysis as per their understanding, which may or may not be biased", as

discussed previously. But this also suggests that with their 'biases and following' that specific parties do need journalists to do their work for them and to give validation to their frames.

Additionally, a senior anchor person and YouTuber, J5, elaborated on the topic of journalist bias, explaining that regardless of whether journalists offer praise, criticism, or factual reports about corruption or developments, they often become targets of trolling from those who oppose them. Supporters of political parties frequently attack journalists for their analyses. He pointed out that journalists are caught up in various factions in Pakistan's highly polarised political environment on social media. J1 indicated the pressure he is facing being neutral:

Another dilemma for journalists in Pakistan is the massive polarization into pro-PTI and anti-PTI camps. Neutral journalists face significant challenges. I am an example of this. If I tweet something about Imran Khan, PML-N supporters call me a "Youthia." Similarly, if I tweet about Maryam Nawaz's arrest, PTI supporters call me a "Patwari" or "Lifafa." It has become very difficult for journalists to maintain neutrality

"Youthia" is an abusive, derogatory slang used for PTI followers and "Patwari" is a derogatory political term used for PMLN supporters to portray them as ignorant. Finally, "Lifafa" is a term used for journalists who are accused of taking bribes from political parties. Li *et al.* (2023) highlight the phenomenon of trolling of political journalists in Pakistan. They identified the 12 most active journalists on Twitter and conducted content and textual analyses of the comments on their tweets. The data indicate that these journalists primarily faced negative remarks, including personal insults, culturally sensitive language, and assaults on their professional integrity. It was also noted that the trolling comments were different for male and female journalists; female journalists were targeted more with gender-related slurs. To complement the findings of the interview data, responses to the posts of one female Asma Sherazi and one male political journalist from the collected data were reviewed. Asma Sherazi is one of the

most followed female journalists on Twitter and a prominent name in mainstream electronic media in Pakistan who also writes for international media. On 26th November 2024, she posted a video clip from her programme on Hum News along with a text about a political development after PTI's protestors were dispersed and the protest was called off. Translation of the post is:

Allegations of Faisal Vawda on Bushra Bibi: They want to do politics for the rest of their lives by trading Imran Khan's life. The army chief, who was DGISI at that time, presented evidence of Bushra Bibi's corruption to Imran Khan, but IK was blindfolded. The General Faiz network used to give information to Bushra Bibi, which was called witchcraft. Later, Bushra Bibi was part of General Faiz's planning to prevent General Asim Munir from becoming the Army Chief (Sherazi, 2024).

The post had 49K views, 658 likes and 60 comments. All the negative comments noted were gender-based slurs calling the female journalist "Gashti" (whore), "Randi of GHQ (prostitute who is serving the military establishment)". A screenshot taken from the comments section of the post illustrates the nature of the personal attacks. Comments made about the politician who said the words posted by Asma Sherazi were few and they included words like Ghaddar (traitor), Kutta (dog).

Related to the same incident, on the morning of 26th of November 2024, a prominent social media journalist and YouTuber, who is also one of the most followed journalists on Twitter, posted a photo of Bushra Bibi leading the protest and entering Islamabad along with a caption "This is how to enter D Chowk (Islamabad)" (Riaz, 2024). The post was viewed 400k times, received 47K likes, 12k reposts and 777 replies. It was an appreciation post for PTI leader Bushra Bibi, who was leading the protestors to enter Islamabad. In the reply section, there were two types of comments: celebrating and praising PTI from PTI followers and supporters and counter remarks from the critics of PTI with abusive remarks for Bushra Bibi. The negative

comments and the slurs were similar to the slurs thrown at the female journalist, Asma Sherazi, Randi (whore), a woman who is in the habit of running away with men. Some of the replies used [#پینکی پیرنی نس گئی](#) (Pinki Peerni ran away). Pinki is Bushra Bibi's informal name; Peerni is a word associated with Bushra Bibi based on her past. Its literal meaning is a spiritual healer, but the term is sarcastically used by political workers and followers of other parties to accuse her of being a black magician. These findings not only resonate with the wider global concern about the online violence female journalists are facing, but they also contribute to the online misogynistic behaviours directed at female politicians. A survey conducted across fifteen countries, including developed Western nations and the United States, involving 1,100 respondents, found that women journalists are encountering similar patriarchal behaviours and threats in the form of misogynistic attitudes (Posetti *et al.*, 2022). In addition, there was evidence of disability-shaming words for the journalist. The word "Thatha" is used for people in Pakistan who have partially disabled speech issues. People in the comments calling the journalist as "thatha" to address him. Trolling phenomenon for journalists is highlighted by many, like Dagoula (2023), who finds journalists opting for self-censorship and considering whether they should stay on the platform or not.

The insights gathered from interviewees underscore the critical role that media plays in shaping public discourse and awareness. Their experiences reveal not only the challenges faced in an evolving media landscape but also the ethical responsibilities that come with the profession. Understanding their perspectives is essential, as it highlights the importance of journalistic integrity, the need for transparency, and the ongoing struggle for accurate reporting in an age of misinformation. By prioritising these values, journalists can foster a more informed society, which ultimately benefits democratic processes and community engagement.

7.4 Conclusion

In this chapter, I have explored the intricate relationship between the Twittersphere, mainstream media, and journalists in shaping political communication in Pakistan. The findings underscore Twitter's dual role as both a source and consumer of news, reshaping traditional journalism and amplifying its interdependence with digital platforms. This transformation has been fuelled by the active participation of politicians, journalists, and media organisations, leveraging the platform to influence narratives and engage with a wider audience.

The immediacy and accessibility of Twitter has altered the mechanisms of news operation. Politicians often bypass traditional gatekeeping by directly sharing statements, while media outlets and journalists increasingly rely on the platform for breaking news, content amplification, and audience engagement. Moreover, the monetisation of content and the quest for engagement have influenced journalists' practices, introducing challenges to traditional journalistic norms and ethics.

Notably, the findings reveal that the framing of news on Twitter has not entirely replaced mainstream media but rather added a dynamic layer to it. While the platform enables broader participation and can help democratise information dissemination, it also reflects the biases, preferences, and polarisations inherent in traditional media practices. Journalists' personal inclinations and monetisation-driven content strategies often shape the framing of political discourse on Twitter, sometimes echoing the same biases observed in mainstream media in Pakistan. It also highlights the use of AI and disinformation by the most followed journalists based on their biases on Twitter. Mainstream media and journalists continue to wield significant influence over political communication in Pakistan. Their framing of news and active engagement on Twitter shape narratives that resonate across digital and traditional platforms, reinforcing their centrality in the political discourse. By strategically navigating both

mediums, journalists and media organisations amplify political messages, mediate public opinion, and contribute to the broader dynamics of political engagement.

Despite these challenges, Twitter offers unique opportunities for journalists to highlight stories overlooked by traditional outlets, engage directly with their audience, and challenge misinformation. The platform's ability to foster direct interaction and amplify diverse voices has redefined the landscape of political communication in Pakistan, reinforcing its role as a critical space for shaping narratives and public discourse. This chapter sets the stage for further exploration of how journalists and media organisations, using Twitter, frame the news and influence political communication. It invites reflection on the ethical implications of this evolving media ecosystem and its impact on democratic engagement and public trust in journalism in Pakistan. These findings extend current discussions on platform journalism by illustrating how journalistic practices on Twitter can shift from verification and mediation towards amplification under conditions of political polarisation, economic pressure, and platform visibility incentives. The impact of this is not uniform across all journalists, but it reveals how platform environments can intensify pressures that blur professional boundaries and reshape journalistic authority. This is important because it shows how established journalistic norms are reproduced, negotiated, or challenged within platformed political communication rather than simply displaced.

Chapter 8: Exploring the Nuances of Digital Political Communication in Pakistan

8.1 Introduction

Building on the findings chapters, this discussion explicitly addresses what the results mean for existing debates on strategic political communication, framing, and platform journalism, and outlines their broader implications for Pakistan's hybrid media environment. In this discussion chapter, I delve into the contemporary landscape of political communication in Pakistan, focusing on the pivotal roles played by political parties and the media. The chapter is organised into three distinct sections, each addressing one of the study's research questions and drawing on findings and existing literature. In the first section, I analyse the significance of Twitter as a prominent platform within Pakistan's broader digital environment, discussing how political parties leverage the platform strategically to construct their political narratives. Discussion focuses on the unique features of both digital and public spheres in the country, noting the varying strategies employed by different political parties across provinces. In the second section, I analyse the relationship between Twitter and mainstream media in Pakistan, exploring journalistic ethics and the challenges that the use of social platforms by political actors poses for traditional forms of news dissemination. In this section, I shed light on how journalists are navigating the complexities of reporting in the age of social media. In the final section, I assess the overall impact of Twitter and the digital landscape on political communication in Pakistan. By examining these dynamics, I illustrate how digital media intertwines with political discourse, providing insights into the evolving practices of journalism and illustrate how these elements are deeply embedded within the broader framework of Pakistan's political culture. Through this exploration, I present a nuanced perspective on the intersection of digital media, political strategy, and journalism, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of the current state of political communication in Pakistan.

8.2 Strategic narratives and Twitter's role in Pakistan's political sphere

Considering the political concept of the public sphere provided by Habermas (2022), which is closely tied to the sustainability of democracy and the “political integration of citizens” (p. 146), in this section, I respond to the research question “How do political parties in Pakistan utilise Twitter as a strategic tool to reach their potential voters?” My study highlights that the “structural transformation” of the political public sphere is not merely a result of new media technologies, such as mainstream media and digital platforms, as presented by the works of Habermas (1962, translated in 1989, 2006, 2022). Instead, my findings demonstrate that the structure of the Pakistani “public sphere” exhibits distinct characteristics in terms of communication and participation, influenced by the country’s unique political culture. This cultural context means that the characteristics of the public sphere, communication styles and methods of involvement differ significantly in Pakistan compared to other contexts. I have shown how the political parties in Pakistan craft their political communication strategies in alignment with the specific features of the political public sphere. This contributes to the ongoing debate about the idea of the “structural transformation” of the public sphere. Previous research has demonstrated that Twitter plays a significant communicative role in Pakistani politics. For example, some scholars have pointed out how Twitter shapes citizen narratives during periods of political instability (Zaman and Abbas, 2022). Similarly, Shami, Khan and Ashfaq (2019) investigated how politicians leverage public relations on Twitter, focusing on their language and content strategies. Diou *et al.* (2018) explored the intersection of media and political participation, particularly among young people in Khairpur District, Sindh, highlighting their active involvement and support for political figures, and the affordability of platforms like Facebook and YouTube in promoting political engagement. Shafiq (2021) analysed patterns of political hate speech on Twitter. Together, these studies demonstrate that

Twitter's influence in Pakistani politics extends to themes including political instability, public perception, sentiments, coalitions, hate speech, and ideological strategies.

My study findings demonstrate that the Pakistani political elites, overseas Pakistanis, the media, and young people use Twitter extensively, making the platform an indispensable feature of the public sphere and influencing political narrative building in the country. I argue that the influence of Twitter cannot be reduced to the *quantity* of Twitter users, but instead it is who uses the platform and with what planned outcomes that matters. I have demonstrated that those politicians and political party machines seeking to influence public opinion are very active on Twitter and use it as their preferred framing platform, from which wider political strategies extend. This aligns with Ashfaq and Roofi (2023), Rizvi (2015) and Hussain (1979) who have also suggested that political elites in Pakistan have a powerful influence on public opinion and voting choices. Considering the basic characteristics of the public sphere, “as communicative spaces where participation is open, where matters of common concern can be discussed” (Eisenegger and Schäfer, 2023 p., 61), and opinions can be developed, Pakistan presents a case in which political parties use Twitter to spread narratives among those who influence public opinion. Ashfaq and Roofi (2023) have identified the various types of elites, including military, bureaucratic, industrial, religious and political. My study findings indicate that the three major political parties in Pakistan, PTI, PMLN, and PPP, have a clear strategic presence on Twitter. The first and second tiers of political leadership of all three political parties are present on Twitter and operate to a set plan for creating unique narratives and communicating them through their party structures. While there are examples of individual politicians, such as Imran Khan, who are key to the social media success of their party (Usman, Munawar and Amjad, 2013), my findings suggest that it is the strategic alignment between the politician, party, and the public that generates traction in the digital public sphere. Garnham (2020) considers the public sphere as a platform where politicians and policy makers’ credibility is questioned,

which can help strengthen democracy. However, while I found that each of the main political parties in Pakistan operates on Twitter according to a similar logic, not all enjoy the same following or influence, questioning the equal accountability of all politicians and political parties. PTI is the most popular party on social media using Twitter very effectively to promote and propagate their party messages, exploiting the personality politics of their leadership and using that popularity to advance their wider message. As noted by Graham, Jackson and Broersma (2016) for digital platforms, every post has an economic value. The posts made by most followed accounts are promoted more by the platform undermining the potential of Twitter as part of political sphere for strengthening democracy.

My findings indicate that following the success of PTI, other parties were pressured into joining Twitter, reinforcing Ahmed and Skoric's (2013) research, which found that after the PTI General Election victory in 2013, other political parties followed them on to social media. Study findings also demonstrate that PTI drew on overseas expertise to develop and implement their social media political strategy. The PTI social media team was led by overseas Pakistanis, residing in New York and other developed western countries where there is a history of Twitter being used for political campaigns (Fraia and Missaglia, 2014). The social media experts of PTI, based in these countries, adopted Twitter for political campaigning purposes, observing trends in the West, while other political parties initially relied on more traditional political communication strategies. PTI uses bots to boost trends demonstrating the party's social media team's understanding of hashtag algorithms, learning from elections in the US and the UK. My findings also demonstrate the presence of the Pakistani diaspora on Twitter and the popularity of Imran Khan among this group. Ahmed, Saeed and Alam (2025) have shown that the majority of PTI followers, "came from the Pakistani diaspora in Europe and North America. It was the diaspora and influential users in the Global North that he had addressed most through his tweets initially, criticising the fiscal and foreign policies of the then-sitting Pakistani government" (p.

286). Those influential Twitter users actively engage in the Twittersphere to project the PTI narrative. Considering the concept of sphericules, a public can be created around any issue (Gitlin, 2002; Cunningham, 2001; Burns and Highfield, 2015). These groups facilitate informal discussions and play a significant role in shaping public opinion. In the context of Pakistan Tehreek-e-Insaf (PTI), the party's decentralised structure allows members within the network to feel supported and encouraged to contribute content. This participation helps PTI to build a cohesive public opinion by creating multiple sphericules focused on similar topics, such as the Urdu hashtag `#نامنظور_حکومت_امپورٹڈ` translated as (imported-government unacceptable). Essentially, this strategy fosters engagement and mobilises collective sentiment around key issues. The findings of my research indicate that PTI leaders participate in spaces on Twitter discussing various issues and interact informally with Twitter users (creating issue publics around the main sphericule #), but these activities are not random; the content and topics for creating sphericules are generated through a systematic approach.

The study findings also indicate that Twitter has become the platform of choice in Pakistan as indicated by scholars like Al Abd (2022). As far as the structure of the political digital sphere in Pakistan is concerned, Twitter holds the prime position but there are also other platforms now being utilised by the political parties to reach their audiences. While there are examples of successful campaigns run via Twitter in urban areas, such as Karachi, Sindh province, and KPK province, as well as other cities in Punjab, Twitter is not the only mechanism for narrative building used in Pakistan. For example, the PPP uses TikTok as an effective platform in the province of Sindh, because their target voters are often from the lower socioeconomic segment, with lower levels of education and lower levels of digital literacy (Shabir and Haider, 2023). However, the PPP continued to utilise Twitter to disseminate news to the mainstream media, as the press considers Twitter a credible news source and picks up news from the platform, broadcasting it and spreading the narrative to rural areas where internet access is limited. The

findings support Benkler's (2006) argument that various digital platforms converge to create a political sphere. This overlap occurs not only among digital platforms but also between the digital sphere and mainstream media, which link the online space with the offline public sphere in Pakistan.

In Pakistan's hybrid media system, regional and structural differences shape how political parties engage with Twitter. Punjab, the political heartland dominated by elite interests, remains the primary battleground, where PTI and PMLN actively use Twitter to frame opponents and mobilise support (Shabbir and Haider, 2023). The findings suggest that the digital public sphere is not uniform across regions. Instead, it reflects broader socio-political and cultural dynamics. These variations highlight how strategic communication on Twitter is shaped by local political cultures and disparities in access, reinforcing the need to contextualise framing practices within Pakistan's evolving digital and political landscape.

In the case of PTI, the content posted on Twitter to create sphericules and issue publics online is dictated by the party leadership like Imran Khan and disseminated to the grassroots for wider circulation. The second-tier political leaders also have their own social media teams at the constituency level, informed by the main social media team, highlighting the networked nature of social media teams in the party. As discussed in the findings chapters, PTI utilises Twitter for setting agendas through the creation of powerful narratives. For example, during the 2024 election campaign, amid a media ban, PTI used Twitter to mobilise supporters, raise awareness, and call for protests such as those on 9th May. It also utilised the "space" function of the Twitter to connect with people, directly engaging with followers and talking to them openly without any time constraints or barriers imposed by mainstream news channel editorial policies. While PTI demonstrated the most structured and decentralised social media strategy, PMLN and PPP showed less coherence and tactical use of platform-specific features. For instance, despite Maryam Nawaz's large Twitter following, PMLN's use of affordances like hashtags and Spaces

was limited, suggesting missed opportunities for interactive engagement. In contrast, PPP's highly centralised model, where content is disseminated top-down from Bilawal House, the political headquarter of PPP. It was also found that the second-tier leadership have their own social media teams, separate from the main leadership. Additionally, the presence of separate social media teams within PMLN and PPP's second-tier leadership reflects a fragmented communication structure, lacking the coherence observed in PTI's digital strategy. This fragmentation limits the formation of unified sphericules and coordinated issue publics. In contrast, PTI's strategically aligned messaging across leadership levels facilitates the creation and amplification of targeted hashtags, enhancing message salience and extending reach within the digital public sphere. As Barberà *et al.* (2021) suggest, political parties are undergoing organisational changes to adapt to digital platforms. Among the three major political parties in Pakistan, the PTI has adapted to a social media age more effectively than their competitors. PTI's use of digital platforms to frame Imran Khan as a charismatic saviour positioning him as the nation's last hope and a leader of the Muslim Ummah (Saeed, 2022) combined with its decentralised strategy that empowers grassroots members to generate and circulate content, situates the party between the two models of digital political parties outlined by Deseriis (2020).

According to Deseriis, one model reflects a 'digital vanguard party' with centralised control over messaging, while the other represents a 'platform party' that relies on distributed participation and user-generated content. PTI blends elements of both, maintaining narrative authority through its leadership while leveraging a decentralised base for amplification. One is the platform party, and the other is the networked party; the former is highly centralised, led by a charismatic leader, and the latter allows policy proposals and leadership positions to emerge from the network. The other two main political parties in Pakistan have less effectively exploited the potential of digital media platforms. As indicated by Lachapelle and Maarek

(2015), political parties need more technologically proficient activists to run their campaigns, and my study findings suggest that PTI is the only party to utilise young people and overseas activists in their network. Second, in the case of Pakistan, the need for digital platform adaptation is also different from other countries. There are parts of the country where political communication requires a physical presence. Despite the growing influence of digital platforms, these findings highlight the continued importance of physical ground presence in certain regions, particularly in Sindh. The PPP's dominance in the province, for example, is sustained through strong local networks and consistent on-the-ground engagement. Shah Mehmood Qureshi, a senior politician and former Foreign Minister of Pakistan, saw his daughter lose an electoral race to the son of Yousaf Raza Gillani, a former Prime Minister of Pakistan. This defeat was largely attributed to her being absent from the constituency during the election campaign. This suggests that while digital tools are central to strategic communication, their effectiveness remains contingent on contextual political cultures and the strength of offline networks a dynamic consistent with findings in hybrid media system research (Chadwick, 2013). Raman (2011) advocates for a blended hybrid public sphere model in developing democracies, arguing that not everyone is technologically skilled or connected to digital platforms. My study findings highlighted the significance of offline political campaigning in local communities, using more easily accessible digital tools.

Considering Castells (2009)'s concept of the network society and how the digital sphere operates within Pakistan's public sphere, the interplay between these elements reveals the growing influence of social media on political discourse in the country. The public sphere in Pakistan reflects a virtual, fluid structure (Papacharissi, 2020). Based on socioeconomic factors and persistent digital divides, political parties utilise Twitter strategically to reach out to their potential voters and build their narratives, but they are not wholly reliant on an online-connected society. Rather, in the Pakistani political context, Twitter can be considered the

primary sphere within a wider digital sphere, operating as one of several digital media platforms utilised to convey political messages to the public. Moreover, my study findings demonstrate that political parties also continue to spread their narratives through engagement with mainstream media, carefully framing messages on Twitter, knowing that legacy media organisations will pick up this news and broadcast it. Hence, due to the complex and intricate nature of the political public sphere in the country, political parties utilise both online and offline platforms to connect with opinion makers and shape public narratives. By adapting their approaches, they can engage different segments of the population and address the unique challenges present in the political landscape.

Pal (2017) argues that political messages are deliberately crafted to appeal to specific audiences, a process that remains central even as the medium shifts from traditional platforms to social media (Graham, Jackson and Broersma, 2016). This is evident in my findings, where political parties in Pakistan use Twitter not simply for communication, but as a strategic tool to frame events, mobilise supporters, and counter opposition narratives. As Salahuddin (2024) notes, social media multiplies the possibilities for framing a point that aligns with how parties like PTI construct leader-centric narratives and deploy hashtags to build issue-specific momentum. Similarly, Voltmer and Kraetzschmar (2015) emphasise how the framing of political developments shapes public perception, a mechanism clearly visible in the way events such as the 9th May unrest were framed differently by each party to serve their strategic ends. Thus, these studies help interpret how framing on Twitter is not merely rhetorical, but tightly linked to the strategic objectives of political actors in Pakistan's hybrid media system. Hassan (2018) argues that the way political developments are framed in the media significantly influences public opinion in Pakistan. This aligns with broader framing literature (e.g. Entman, 1993; de Vreese, 2005), which emphasises that frames help audiences make sense of political events by highlighting certain aspects of reality while omitting others. Together, these studies

underline how framing operates not only as a journalistic practice but also as a political strategy that shapes how citizens interpret and respond to political developments. However, what appears more context-specific in the Pakistani case is the high level of emotional and moral framing, particularly around themes of glorification, victimhood, and betrayal, often reinforced with symbolic visuals, religious references, and emotionally charged language. This reflects Pakistan's unique political culture, where elite-driven narratives and populist appeals operate within a polarised media system and a historically fragile democratic context (Yusuf *et al.*, 2013; Hussain, Abbas and Shah, 2024; Jalal, 2009). While the intentionality behind framing is a common feature globally (Pal, 2017), the framing tropes and the tight coordination between party digital teams and offline political structures are more distinctly observed in Pakistan, according to the findings of this study.

The data from Twitter reveals how PTI systematically deployed framing strategies to construct Imran Khan as an indispensable saviour for Pakistan's future, while simultaneously promoting a sense of collective victimhood. This aligns with Entman's (1993) notion that framing serves to define problems, diagnose causes, and propose remedies, with PTI positioning Khan as the remedy to a corrupt and externally manipulated political system. By repeatedly invoking narratives of a foreign conspiracy and labelling the opposition as an "imported government" or "thieves," PTI reinforced an 'us versus them' dichotomy that resonates with populist communication strategies (Moffitt (2016). Additionally, anti-establishment frames, including those targeting the military, suggest a deliberate attempt to challenge traditionally powerful institutions in Pakistan, which is significant given the military's historical influence on politics (Shafqat, 2019). These findings suggest that in the Pakistani context, social media acts as a powerful site for political actors to amplify populist and anti-elite frames, reinforcing group identities and mobilising supporters, in line with broader patterns observed in global populist movements (Gerbaudo, 2018).

Nehal (2024) highlights that Imran Khan gained popularity through rhetoric promoting a ‘corruption-free Pakistan’ labelling both the PMLN and PPP as corrupt parties. He also emphasised the sovereignty of Pakistan and the need to save the country from external interventions, part of the PTI manifesto, which its leaders keep repeating in his posts (p., 28). Nehal found that Khan employed the same slogans during the 2018 General Election campaign. Research from Batool (2023), Yilmaz and Shakil (2021) indicates that the combination of Khan's charisma and messages about a corruption-free Pakistan, along with anti-establishment slogans, helped PTI attract voters during the 2018 General Elections, linking it to the characteristics of populist leaders. These findings resonate with the current study's evidence that PTI's digital communication particularly on Twitter relied heavily on emotionally charged, populist frames. By amplifying narratives of victimhood, betrayal, and national salvation, PTI reinforced its populist appeal online, particularly during political crises such as Khan's ousting. This framing was strategically constructed and widely disseminated by party-affiliated accounts, showing continuity with past campaign strategies while adapting them to the evolving digital landscape.

These patterns illustrate how framing operates on Twitter as a mechanism of political legitimisation and contestation in Pakistan. PTI's repeated emphasis on a corruption-free Pakistan, foreign conspiracies, and nationalist sovereignty themes consistent with its 2018 slogans (Nehal, 2024) demonstrates the use of diagnostic and prognostic framing (Benford and Snow, 2000), identifying corrupt elites and foreign interference as the problem, with Khan positioned as the remedy. This supports the argument that populist leaders mobilise supporters through moral binaries and anti-elite narratives, consistent with Moffitt's (2016) conception of populism as a performance of crisis.

In contrast, PMLN leaders, particularly Maryam Nawaz (2022), attempted to reframe PTI's populist claims as disinformation, highlighting bot-generated trends and promoting a message

of economic stability following Khan's removal. This represents a counternarrative that contests frame resonance (Snow and Benford, 1988), seeking to delegitimise PTI's crisis frames and replace them with messages of institutional competence. The PPP, meanwhile, positioned Khan's ouster as a democratic correction, celebrating it with slogans such as 'democracy is the best revenge' (Nehal, 2024), thereby reinforcing its longstanding legacy as a defender of democratic continuity rather than populist rupture.

Overall, these dynamics show that in Pakistan's contemporary context, Twitter functions not simply as a broadcast platform but as a contested arena for framing battles, where political actors compete to define public understandings of legitimacy, crisis, and authority. This expands existing framing scholarship by demonstrating how social media intensifies rapid and polarised frame competition, particularly in politically strategic regions like Punjab (Shabbir Haider, 2023), Pakistan's electoral heartland.

Beyond the content of leaders' Twitter posts, study findings underscore how this platform has become a site for negative and hostile framing, full of abusive language and trolling, particularly directed at female journalists and politicians. This is consistent with research showing that negativity and outrage tend to generate higher engagement on social media, including likes, shares, and retweets (Brady *et al.*, 2021; Bellovary, Young and Goldenberg, 2021; Schöne, Parkinson and Goldenberg, 2021), incentivising political actors to adopt increasingly hostile framing to maximise attention.

Three key features of these framing practices are worth noting. First, PTI and PMLN are locked in a competitive framing battle, consistently reaffirming their own moral and political narratives in opposition to each other. This supports the notion of framing as an interactive and contested process (Gamson, 1992), where actors continuously adapt frames to compete for public support. Second, the prevalence of patriarchal and gendered abuse directed at female

politicians and journalists highlights how social media can magnify gendered mediation in political discourse (Ross and Comrie, 2012; Megarry, 2014), while also benefiting from the higher click-rates such negative and emotionally charged content attracts (Papacharissi, 2015). Third, the continued use of religiously coded frames invoking saviour figures, victimhood narratives tied to the Muslim Ummah, and anti-military sentiment, echoes Pakistani political culture as noted by Siddiqi (2020) and Hussain et al. (2018). It is also consistent with how affective populism operates online in other settings, such as Trump politics, where highly moralised, polarising messages proved especially viral (Ott, 2017). This reflects the principle of cultural resonance (Snow and Benford, 1988), where familiar narratives, when coupled with emotionally charged language, become even more powerful in an algorithmically driven attention economy.

Taken together, these findings demonstrate that Twitter in Pakistan acts not just as a stage for political framing, but also as an amplifier of negativity and patriarchal discourses, rewarding polarisation and reinforcing structural power inequalities through its engagement-driven design. This section has demonstrated how political parties in Pakistan strategically use Twitter to engage voters and shape public narratives, but its significance extends beyond the national context. The study findings expand on recent work on populist online communication (Engesser *et al.*, 2017; Krämer, 2017), demonstrating how culturally resonant and emotionally charged narratives including nationalist, religious, and anti-elite frames gain traction in polarised digital environments. The evidence also suggests that negative, moralised, and crisis-driven messaging is incentivised on social media through higher levels of engagement, echoing contemporary research on affective polarisation and algorithmic amplification (Tucker *et al.*, 2018; Freelon and Wells, 2020). In doing so, this study advances understandings of framing as an interactive and iterative process (Gamson, 1992), one that is not static but actively negotiated through digital platforms where political actors both construct and contest

legitimacy in real time aligning with Bruns and Weller (2016)'s observation of Twitter as a "first draft of the present" (p. 183).

The analysis further contributes to framing and populism scholarship by showing how cultural resonance (Snow and Benford, 1988) functions in a digital age: while populist and religiously coded frames draw strength from familiar offline political cultures found by Hussain et al., (2018) and Siddiqi (2020), their reach, emotional intensity, and polarising effects are amplified through the platform dynamics of social media (Papacharissi, 2015). This challenges the notion of social media as a democratising force and instead positions it as an active agent in the reproduction of existing power inequalities, including gendered and class-based hierarchies.

These insights suggest that studies of framing on social media must pay closer attention to how technological affordances (Treem and Leonardi, 2013) intersect with local political cultures to shape communication strategies. The Pakistani case highlights the need for greater comparative research into how digital platforms enable or constrain political actors in different contexts, and how these dynamics may reshape both electoral politics and democratic participation globally.

8.3 Framing, agenda-building, and hybrid media logics

In this section, I respond to the second research question, "How do journalists and mainstream media utilise Twitter messages from political parties to increase the salience of party messages?" Responding to this question, my research contributes to an understanding of the role of contemporary journalism in existing mechanisms of political communication in Pakistan, particularly concerning Twitter. Existing research on the role of mainstream media in political communication in Pakistan indicates that the media was polarised, biased and served the interests of wealthy political elites (Michaelsen, 2011; Pintak, Bowe and Nazir, 2018). In addition, Sarwar, Umer and Bajwa (2020) noted that Geo News, which was a trend

setter after the advent of freedom of media in Pakistan for more than a decade, was boycotted by the ruling PPP in 2010 for projecting the PMLN narrative. Additionally, the *Dunya* and *Express* media groups were projecting PPP, whereas some media groups, like those owned by the *Dawn* media group, were neutral. Hussain (2012) argues that after 2001, electronic and print news media were out of government control, but then it was media financiers, journalists, anchor persons, and the business owners of media houses who controlled the media. Previous research has noted that social media provided an alternative, enabling political parties to post political news directly to potential voters. The increasing reliance on social media particularly among young voters in Pakistan challenges the traditional gatekeeping role of mainstream media (Saeed et al., 2021; Ahmed et al., 2019; Ejaz, 2013; Ali and Chaudhary, 2024). Research indicates that young people, who make up 60% of the population and 45% of registered voters, actively use platforms like Twitter and Facebook for political news and expression. For example, Ali and Chaudhary (2024) found that 72.7% of respondents cited social media as their primary source of political news, compared to just 51.7% who relied on mainstream headlines. This shift highlights a fundamental change in the communication environment, one where political parties can bypass traditional media filters and engage voters directly. My findings confirm this trend, showing that social media, particularly Twitter, plays a central role in shaping political narratives and influencing youth political behaviour. Accordingly, this section examines how journalists and news organisations on Twitter play a dual role as both consumers and producers of political content, selectively amplifying party messages in ways that merge professional journalistic practices with platform incentives. In the absence of consistent editorial guidelines or robust social media codes of conduct, journalists' personal accounts may mirror and even magnify existing biases in the pursuit of visibility and monetisation, further blurring the distinction between neutral reporting and partisan amplification. This hybrid practice of platformed journalism, a term used by Poell (2013), illustrates a transformation of

political communication in Pakistan's hybrid media ecosystem, where framing and agenda-building occur dynamically across intertwined traditional and digital environments.

Sharma and Sivakumar (2023) argue that social media has become a source for journalists to return to for story ideas, and the race to get more likes and attract public attention on these platforms has become a discussion point in mainstream media newsrooms. Study findings indicate that the news operation in Pakistan has changed after the advent of social media platforms, particularly Twitter. Mainstream news media organisations have appointed social media teams to monitor political development, and Twitter is accepted as a valid source of information in Pakistan. Hermida (2012) emphasises that mainstream media organisations worldwide have eagerly adopted social media, changing how citizens and journalists approach news in the current landscape. The preceding discussion has highlighted the presence of all political parties on Twitter, establishing that while some political parties use other social media platforms to target specific types of potential voters, they also continue to utilise Twitter because they know mainstream media will pick up the posts from the platform. As a source, Twitter represents a platform on which politicians can post statements, the ISPR, and political parties, which are broadcast as news. Political parties also utilise other social media platforms, but Twitter is the only medium cited as a source on mainstream media screens. In the changed political news landscape, journalists no longer have to chase politicians for updates on political developments and statements. Instead, social media teams within news organisations and individual journalists monitor the accounts of prominent politicians, political parties, and military leadership to stay updated. My study findings suggest that mainstream news media organisations are propagating the framed messages of political parties originating from Twitter. It also suggests that the Twitter and mainstream media spheres are entangled, whereby political parties, political elites, media organisations and journalists are operating simultaneously. A good example of this is the hashtag #ImportedGovernmentNotAccepted. A message framed by

the political party PTI about a political development, which was being framed as a democratic move by PPP leader Bilawal Bhutto (2022), became a trending topic on Twitter for many days, and the same frame became news for the main media outlets. Twitter as a source can be visualised as in Figure 8.1. This resonates with the findings of (QAISAR, 2021) who found that the social media and mainstream media in Pakistan are interconnected and integrated, and there is agenda setting between social media platforms and newspaper websites.

Figure 8.1 visual presentation flow of framed political messages from political parties (self-contribution)

This again brings the idea presented by Benklar (2006) about multidirectional connections and overlapping platforms in which information travels from one platform to the other. My findings indicate that PTI's historical trend using the hashtag #ImportedGovernmentNotAccepted functioned as a powerful frame contesting the legitimacy of the sitting government. The widespread uptake of this frame by prominent mainstream media organisations, which reproduced and amplified the hashtag's narrative, demonstrates how journalistic actors can contribute to the salience of party-framed messages, effectively co-constructing political meaning with partisan voices. This suggests that mainstream media, rather than critically interrogating such frames, may reinforce partisan messages by prioritising highly resonant, conflict-driven content in their news agendas, consistent with research on agenda-building (McCombs, 2005) and the dynamics of framing in hybrid media environments (Chadwick, 2017).

Journalists share their opinions about posts by the political party official accounts or party representatives' personal biases and likes and dislikes play a role; journalists criticise some political parties but refrain from criticising other parties. This shift is captured by the concept of platformed journalism (Poell, 2013), in which journalistic routines adapt to platform logics, privileging speed, engagement metrics, and shareability over traditional editorial verification. In this environment, journalists no longer function purely as watchdogs but become part of the networked flow of partisan frames, often reinforcing polarisation and diminishing editorial independence (Hermida, 2022; Kreiss and McGregor, 2019). This transformation challenges normative ideals of journalistic impartiality and suggests that in Pakistan, social media has entangled journalists in a cycle of frame amplification and agenda-building that can reproduce existing elite interests.

My research suggests that journalists in Pakistan have increasingly used Twitter to surface stories that mainstream editors may deprioritise, allowing lower-profile journalists to gain audience traction. This partly supports Schäfer (2015) argument that digital platforms can expand the public sphere by giving diverse voices a publishing channel. However, my findings also reveal a more complex picture. Several participants reported that some digital journalists use social media to pursue personal visibility and monetisation opportunities, sometimes relying on inflammatory or abusive language to drive engagement. This pattern resonates with emerging literature on affective journalism (Papacharissi, 2015), which shows that journalists working on platforms may shift toward emotionally charged, attention-seeking content to meet platform incentives for virality and personal brand-building. Such practices also echo concerns about platformed journalism (Poell, 2013), where editorial norms are weakened by algorithmic pressures that reward controversy and speed over verification (Hermida, 2012).

These findings raise critical questions about how far digital journalism in Pakistan is contributing to a more inclusive public sphere versus reinforcing polarisation and undermining

professional norms. While social media offers an opportunity for more voices to be heard, the platform's commercial and algorithmic structures may simultaneously incentivise harmful discourses and erode the watchdog role of journalism, as documented in international studies of hybrid news ecologies (Kreiss and McGregor, 2024).

The concept is again consistent with the platform journalism discussed by Poell (2013) and Hermida, (2022) where individual journalists become personal brands competing for engagement, visibility, and monetisation. In this context, journalists are no longer just reporters but also content creators, brand builders, and entrepreneurs. This aligns with scholarly work on the entrepreneurial turn in journalism Diaz Ruiz (2025) highlighting, how some actors make money from digital platforms. The market encourages them to create content that can go viral, which leads to financial rewards for sharing controversial claims, confrontational stories, and false information. Manzoor and Shahzad (2024) and Adnan, Ali and Aslam (2019) indicate in their research how financial pressures cause journalists to compromise basic journalism ethics in Pakistan. For instance, the Jang and Geo Group (Pakistan's largest media conglomerate) shut down three publications and two bureau offices. Dunya Media Group and The Express Media Group (the two newer players in Pakistan's media industry) made more than 200 journalists redundant, and other media outlets, including Dawn (the oldest media house in Pakistan), curtailed their employees' salaries between 15% and 35% in the last 5 years (Rehmat, 2019). The financial strain resulting from the contraction of the media industry and the evolving methods of news collection has given journalists another incentive to generate income through digital platforms. This suggests that digital platforms encourage journalists to adopt roles shaped by market incentives where visibility, monetisation, and audience engagement increasingly shape editorial decisions. As such, the rise of digital journalists operating outside traditional norms represents not only a departure from ethical journalism but also a broader reconfiguration of journalism's professional boundaries and economic

structures. The example of Imran Riaz demonstrates how journalists are operating in their individual identities and enjoying a large following on social media platforms. Riaz is an independent youtuber journalist and one of the most followed journalists in Pakistan. An AI generated fake image posted by him receives far more engagements and likes than those who criticise him. Zaman (2023) has noted that journalistic norms and ethics are compromised more on social media than on mainstream media because of the absence of editorial control. Ekström and Westlund (2019) argue for a “dislocation of journalism” (p., 259) due to the advent of social media, which has blurred the lines between personal opinions and professional news commentaries by journalists because of the absence of editorial control.

In addition to a shift in the political economy of journalism in Pakistan, there is also pressure from political parties and party followers. As indicated by Bruns and Nuernbergk (2019), political journalists are more exposed to political parties, public and politicians than they were practising in mainstream media. My research findings indicate that journalists are facing challenges and pressures for being neutral on Twitter. Journalists criticising a political party end up being accused of supporting the other. There is also evidence that journalists are targeted with abusive language. The findings from my study align closely with previous research, indicating that the PTI government employs social media teams to harass journalists, particularly those who criticise its policies (Hussain et al., 2022). The polarised digital environment in Pakistan reveals that Twitter is not merely a platform for political communication but a site where ideological battles are enacted through harassment and trolling. While the findings chapters outlined that journalists, particularly women, face coordinated online abuse, this should be seen as part of a broader trend that undermines the democratic function of journalism. Personal attacks and culturally loaded slurs are commonly used to delegitimise journalists and suppress dissent (Posetti *et al.*, 2022; Li, 2025). However, my study shows that such abuse is not limited by gender; male journalists also face politically charged

trolling when their reporting is perceived to favour the opposing side. This behaviour signals how political identities are weaponised online to shape media narratives and exert social control. These dynamics contribute to the literature by highlighting how journalists' roles as watchdogs are compromised in fragile democracies, where strategic communication by political actors converges with digital disinformation and harassment tactics. Understanding this helps expand global scholarship on political communication by showing how partisan online abuse affects press freedom and weakens deliberative democratic ideals in countries like Pakistan.

In the context of this study, it was observed that prominent journalists affiliated with mainstream media, including figures like Rauf Klasra, Asma Shirazi, and Imran Riaz, actively engage with political content on Twitter, often presenting the same political events through distinctly different frames. These journalists, despite their institutional affiliations, operate with considerable independence on digital platforms, and their posts gain significant traction due to their large follower bases. The findings suggest that political content broadcast on television is further circulated by these journalists through their personal Twitter accounts, amplifying narratives that align with their known political leanings. This indicates that mainstream media, while already criticised for partisanship in traditional formats, continues to reinforce polarised narratives on digital platforms too. Such patterns reveal how mainstream media remains influential to political communication, not only through structured programming but also via the informal, personalised amplification strategies of journalists on Twitter (Saeed *et al.*, 2021).

This ongoing presence and bias of traditional media in the digital sphere suggest that political communication in Pakistan does not merely reflect citizen participation online but is still largely shaped by elite-driven narratives. As media partisanship spills over into Twitter, journalists contribute to a fragmented and polarised public sphere. The selective amplification of content that supports specific parties undermines the platform's potential for balanced

deliberation. Research by Khan (2023b) shows that media houses often align with political interests, and these biases are reproduced on social media platforms, further influencing public discourse and shaping perceptions among online users. This has serious implications for the role of journalism in democratic societies, where strategic alignments and algorithmic amplification compromise the media's function as a watchdog.

Crilley and Gillespie (2019) argue that unregulated social media platforms have a significant and detrimental influence on journalism. They note that political actors utilise these platforms to disseminate propaganda and misinformation. As Culloty and Suiter (2021) conclude, disinformation strengthens the existing bias and prejudice among users as these frames are well received by the followers of the political party they support despite being AI generated. Bentivegna and Marchetti (2018) call it a 'hybrid normalisation' in which journalists have adopted new media with old practices, like gatekeeping, that were still there. Interestingly, the study was conducted on the Twitter posts of Italian journalists, and it resonates with my study findings. Acknowledging that every individual has opinions, likes, and dislikes as a member of society, the code of ethics stresses that journalists should refrain from presenting their personal opinions on social media, as this might influence the opinions of their followers. Existing journalists' unions in Pakistan, including the Pakistan Union of Journalists, the Rawalpindi Union of Journalists, and the National Press Club in Pakistan, have developed codes of conduct for journalism practice but remain silent to date about ethical considerations for journalists when posting on social media (NPC Islamabad, PFUJ 2025). Journalism has traditionally been defined by values of verification, impartiality, and independence, where the journalist's role is to filter information through editorial judgement and provide accurate, balanced accounts (Ward, 2011). Similarly, the Press Council of Pakistan's codes emphasise accuracy, balance, and avoidance of sensationalism (Jamil, 2023). However, my findings

suggest that these ideals are increasingly difficult to uphold in the digital sphere, and this has direct implications for how the public sphere operates in Pakistan.

First, verification long considered a cornerstone of professional journalism is undermined by the affordances of Twitter. Journalists and politicians alike emphasised the speed and reach of the platform, which bypasses the editorial processes that traditionally ensured accuracy. As Hermida (2010) observes, Twitter is better understood as ambient journalism than as conventional reporting, as it circulates unverified information in real-time. From a framing perspective, this creates conditions where strategic frames can be disseminated without challenge, giving political actors disproportionate influence in shaping interpretations of events. The lack of verification not only destabilises journalistic authority but also alters the discursive quality of the public sphere, privileging immediacy over deliberation (Tandoc Jr, Lim and Ling, 2018)

Second, impartiality and independence are compromised by the political and commercial realities of Pakistani media. While journalists articulated a commitment to neutrality, they also described pressures from proprietors, advertisers, and political networks. This reflects what Michaelsen (2011) calls the 'dilemma of free media' in Pakistan, where wealthy elites and landowners exert significant influence over media agendas. On Twitter, these dynamics are amplified by platform logics: journalists who frame issues in polarised or emotionally charged ways attract greater visibility. This reinforces the framing theory argument that salience is not only constructed but strategically amplified, with platform affordances acting as additional frame multipliers. As a result, the digital public sphere in Pakistan is not simply an open space for deliberation, but a contested arena where power and visibility are unevenly distributed.

Finally, these challenges have profound implications for public trust. Young people described mainstream news channels as biased and unreliable, preferring social media as a source of

political information. This finding resonates with global evidence that trust in traditional journalism is in decline (Reuters Institute, 2025). Yet the paradox, as my study shows, is that social media platforms themselves lack verification and are prone to disinformation. This contradiction illustrates how the digital public sphere can appear more open and participatory, while in practice it risks amplifying polarisation and eroding the deliberative ideals associated with the public sphere model.

In conclusion, mainstream media in Pakistan plays a significant role in amplifying the salience of political party messages, particularly through the integration with social media platforms like Twitter. The interconnectedness of these media forms allows for a rapid dissemination of political narratives, facilitated by journalists who have assumed multifaceted roles that extend beyond traditional reporting. As opinion leaders and content creators, they shape public discourse while navigating the complexities of political affiliations and pressures from party followers. The findings highlight that while social media provides a space for diverse voices and underrepresented stories, it also poses challenges to journalistic integrity and ethics, with financial incentives often driving content creation. This shift towards market-driven journalism impacts the objectivity and neutrality expected of journalists, as they face backlash for their critiques of political entities. Ultimately, the relationship between mainstream media and political parties in Pakistan illustrates a transformation in the media landscape, where the boundaries between reporting and advocacy blur, and where the salience of political messages is heightened, influenced by both audience engagement strategies and the competitive nature of digital platforms. The complexities of these interactions underscore the evolving dynamics of journalism within Pakistan's socio-political context.

8.3.1 Platformed Journalism: Ethical Challenges and the Need for Regulation

The findings of this study indicate that the strategic co-option of Twitter by political actors, combined with its routine use as a source and amplification tool by journalists, has tangible

implications for journalistic practice and democratic communication. In the absence of robust regulatory frameworks, platform-based political communication in Pakistan operates with limited oversight, enabling the circulation of strategically framed, emotive, and occasionally misleading content with minimal accountability. This challenges core journalistic norms of verification, impartiality, and public responsibility (Ward, 2011; Carlson, 2020).

While digital platforms have increased the speed and visibility of political communication, they have also intensified pressures on journalists to prioritise immediacy, engagement, and platform logics over traditional gatekeeping functions (Vos and Russell, 2019). The findings therefore support growing scholarly concerns that platform journalism blurs professional boundaries and weakens established ethical standards when institutional safeguards are absent (Lewis, 2012).

Rather than advocating censorship, this study argues for the need for clearer professional guidelines governing journalists' use of social media, stronger enforcement of ethical codes in digital contexts, and improved digital literacy among journalists and political communicators. Such measures are increasingly recognised as necessary to counter the normalisation of partisan amplification and to protect public trust in journalism within hybrid media systems (Wardle and Derakhshan, 2017).

8.4 Transformation of the political public sphere in Pakistan

The third study research question explores how Twitter has transformed political communication in Pakistan. This section discusses the changing nature of political communication in the country, focusing on both structural and discursive shifts. It also critiques the applicability of Habermas's bourgeois public sphere, particularly the ideal of rational-critical debate, to the Pakistani context. Unlike Habermas's conception, presented in 1962, I argue that the Pakistani public sphere is shaped by unique structural challenges, such as digital

inequality and deep-rooted cultural complexities. These factors influence not only who participates in public discourse but also how discussions unfold, and narratives are constructed.

Based on the arguments made in response to the first two research questions, I argue that political parties strategically frame their messages on Twitter and amplify them through mainstream and other social media platforms. While the features of two-way communication can enhance democratic practices, they are also challenged by the powerful hashtag feature on Twitter. Political parties can leverage Twitter to expand their influence, creating a larger "bubble" that overshadows smaller, more local conversations. As noted by Papacharissi (2002), this dynamic often stifles genuine discussion. Instead, political parties foster an "echo chamber" effect, where certain viewpoints are repeatedly amplified and reinforced within online communities (Sunstein, 2001). In such environments, individuals are often shielded from diverse perspectives, which can diminish their motivation to critically examine their own beliefs. Additionally, these individuals may connect with fewer people in the digital public sphere than they anticipate, leading to what Papacharissi (2002) describes as a "false sense of empowerment" (p. 17).

Habermas's concept of the public sphere outlines a normative ideal in which rational-critical debate occurs among citizens, independent of state or corporate influence, allowing democratic will-formation (Habermas, 1989). However, the application of this framework to the context of Pakistan, particularly in the age of social media, reveals a transformed and more complex reality. Rather than a space for open deliberation among equals, the findings of this study demonstrate that Twitter operates as a strategically managed political arena, where political elites, journalists, and aligned digital actors frame discourse to suit partisan objectives.

In Pakistan's hybrid media system (Chadwick, 2013), Twitter does not serve as a democratic space of unfettered citizen participation. Instead, the platform functions as a digitally mediated

elite sphere accessible primarily to political actors, journalists, and urban, literate users. Connectivity within this sphere is often hierarchical and performative rather than horizontal or deliberative. Political parties employ Twitter as a tool of strategic communication, using framing techniques to shape discourse, legitimise their narratives, and attack opponents bypassing traditional media gatekeepers and, in some cases, manipulating media logics to trigger mainstream coverage.

This shift aligns with Papacharissi's (2010) concept of the "networked public sphere", where emotional expression, personal branding, and strategic signalling often replace rational-critical deliberation. In Pakistan, Twitter's architecture and affordances are used by political actors to construct "sphericules" (Gitlin, 1998), fragmented, issue-specific micro-publics that amplify party-aligned messaging but rarely promote genuine debate or ideological pluralism. Hashtag campaigns and viral content serve strategic goals, with issue publics shaped by algorithms and coordinated digital teams rather than spontaneous civic engagement. Moreover, the findings illustrate that while journalists also participate in the Twitter sphere, their contributions are often shaped by institutional bias, personal ideology, or commercial incentives, rather than professional objectivity. As such, the discursive space on Twitter reflects a convergence of media logic and political strategy, where visibility is earned not through deliberative merit but through viral traction and political alignment.

This interpretation departs from Habermas's normative vision but reflects a growing body of scholarship that rethinks the public sphere in digital and non-Western contexts (Dahlberg, 2007; Fuchs, 2014). In fragile democracies like Pakistan, the public sphere is less a forum for democratic consensus-building and more a battleground for symbolic dominance, where political narratives are framed, circulated, and contested through highly controlled and strategic use of digital tools.

Despite its potential to democratise political discourse, Twitter in Pakistan often reinforces existing power hierarchies, particularly patriarchal structures. The platform, while offering visibility to women politicians and journalists, simultaneously exposes them to disproportionate harassment, trolling, and gendered disinformation. Female political actors such as Maryam Nawaz or journalists like Asma Shirazi face targeted attacks that are often not based on their political stance alone, but on their gender, appearance, and personal lives. This reflects how the digital sphere, rather than offering an equal playing field, becomes a site where patriarchal norms are amplified under the guise of political debate. Studies by Li et al. (2023) and Siddiqui (2023) confirm that women in Pakistan's political and media landscape are subjected to coordinated online abuse campaigns, particularly on Twitter, which discourages participation and narrows the inclusiveness of the digital public sphere. Thus, while Twitter plays a strategic role in shaping political communication, it also reproduces exclusionary practices that mirror the patriarchal tendencies of offline political culture. My research findings concur with a study conducted by Posetti *et al.* (2022) with the help of UNESCO and the International Centre for Journalists (ICFJ) in multiple countries and societies, which revealed that social media was normalising patriarchal behaviours. My study findings suggest that Twitter is not divorced from the Pakistani political culture but rather it reflects what Pakistani political culture is. Challenges posed by social media harassment and abuse for women journalists and politicians multiply the gravity of the situation where politics is already dominated by men as indicated by Ahmad and Anwar (2018) who found that men are leading politics and are considered custodians of politics even by women politicians in Pakistan. It further adds to the challenges instead of facilitating democracy.

Further extending this pattern of communicative distortion, my findings show how Twitter is used not as a deliberative space for rational-critical debate, as Habermas (1989) envisioned, but as a platform for blame games and self-projection. Politicians deploy moralised, populist

frames that depict the military or rival political parties as corrupt elites responsible for national crises. These narratives, grounded in binaries of good versus evil, not only deflect responsibility but also construct the speaker as a virtuous saviour. This aligns with Moffitt (2016)'s concept of populist political style, in which constant crisis and personalisation dominate the communicative logic. The use of such frames mirrors patterns observed globally for example in Trump's rhetorical strategy on Twitter, where emotionally charged, accusatory posts outperformed other forms of content (Ott, 2017; Brady *et al.*, 2021). In Pakistan's hybrid media system, these digitally circulating narratives gain further amplification when picked up by partisan news outlets and echoed by aligned journalists, illustrating how political messaging on Twitter permeates beyond the platform into broader public consciousness. As Waisbord (2018) argues, such populist communication simplifies complex crises into a moral drama, sustaining engagement and reinforcing the leader's central role as the only possible solution.

According to the study's findings, politicians in Pakistan rarely post about social and economic problems. Instead, they are engaged in public discourse to strengthen their own convictions or support their leaders, while simultaneously criticising opposing viewpoints, hurling abuse, or promoting themselves (Shafiq, 2021). Social media abuse has a significant impact on Pakistani politics, as highlighted by (Kumari, Razaqat and Shabbir, 2025). Their research points to several key issues: the spread of false information, rising political divisions, an increase in cyberbullying, and the manipulation of public opinion by trolls and bots. These factors collectively hinder productive discussions about public issues. The dependence of mainstream media on social media platforms has compromised credibility which was there in the form of editorial policies of the organisations. The respondents were of the view that Twitter policy changes for verified accounts have helped fight disinformation to a certain degree but because of the recent policies where verified users need to pay for their accounts to remain verified has affected the number of Twitter users. Scholars like Khan *et al.* (2022) consider the platform

democratic because it has provided a space for young people to interact with their leaders directly but Zaheer (2018) found that social media platforms like Twitter are inciting violence among young people. Muzaffar, Chohdhry and Afzal (2019) also found that despite the online presence, young people in universities in Pakistan lack knowledge about political issues. Based on the type of content discussed about abusive language, personality cult, blaming institutions and individuals, gender abuse and utilisation of bots for manipulating of public opinion, the spread of disinformation raises questions about the role of platforms in fragile democracies like Pakistan.

In conclusion, the public sphere in Pakistan has increasingly transformed into a space characterised not by constructive discussions but rather by abuse, disinformation, and a blame game among various factions. The rise of digital platforms has intensified these issues, as the focus is not towards nuanced dialogue but rather sensationalism and conflict. This environment stifles meaningful discourse and ultimately undermines the integrity of democratic values. Digital platforms are a battleground for vitriol and misinformation.

8.6 Conclusion

In this discussion chapter I have critically examined how political parties and journalists in Pakistan use Twitter to shape, contest, and amplify political narratives within a hybrid media environment. Drawing on framing theory, the analysis showed that politicians consistently deploy diagnostic, prognostic, and moral frames to delegitimise rivals and promote themselves as uniquely capable of solving crises. These frames are rooted in Pakistan's political history yet gain renewed potency through the platform logic of Twitter, which privileges negative, affective, and emotionally resonant content.

I argue that journalists, operating within a platformed journalism context, increasingly adapt to social media's affordances by blending traditional reporting with influencer-style practices,

sometimes amplifying disinformation, emotionally charged images, or partisan frames for engagement. This dual role as both curators and producers highlights how journalists participate in frame-building rather than merely gatekeeping, contributing to the salience of party messages in the digital sphere. The findings suggest that the strategic use of Twitter by political actors and its routine amplification by journalists cannot be understood solely as an issue of individual practice, but as a structural challenge within Pakistan's evolving media ecosystem. While traditional broadcast media in Pakistan is subject to regulatory oversight through bodies such as PEMRA, equivalent mechanisms governing platform-based political communication remain weak or fragmented. This regulatory gap allows strategically framed, emotive, and polarising content to circulate rapidly across platforms and into mainstream media with limited accountability. The study therefore highlights the need to rethink regulatory and ethical frameworks so that they are responsive to the realities of hybrid media systems, where political communication flows fluidly between digital platforms and legacy media.

Furthermore, the discussion revealed how the digital sphere's structure - interactive, fast-paced, and algorithmically driven - differs from the traditional public sphere, producing a political discourse that is more polarised, personality-centred, and emotionally amplified. Within this structure, Pakistani political actors and journalists together transform the boundaries of political debate, embedding historically familiar narratives within new technological and commercial logics. Overall, this chapter contributes to the field by deepening understanding of how framing processes, platformed journalism, and hybrid media logics interact in a fragile democratic context.

Chapter 9: Conclusion and Recommendations

9.1 Introduction

This concluding chapter draws together the central arguments and findings of the thesis, reflecting on how the study has addressed its aim and research objectives. It highlights the theoretical and empirical insights generated through the investigation and considers their implications for the study of political communication, for journalistic practice in Pakistan, and for the prospects of democratic processes in fragile political contexts. By stepping back from the detailed analysis of earlier chapters, the conclusion provides a holistic perspective on the contribution this research makes to understandings of political communication in Pakistan.

The chapter is structured to first summarise the study, identifying the most significant findings and the ways in which they advance existing knowledge in the field of political communication, particularly at the intersection of journalism, social media, and democratic processes in specific political contexts. It then turns to the contributions of the research, both theoretical and empirical, before acknowledging its limitations and outlining areas for further inquiry. Finally, the chapter offers a critical reflection on what the study reveals about the evolving dynamics of political communication in fragile democracies like Pakistan, and how digital platforms both enable and constrain the development of a democratic public sphere.

9.2 Summary of the research

This study set out to explore how Twitter is strategically employed in shaping political communication within Pakistan's hybrid media system. Against the backdrop of a fragile democracy, entrenched elite dominance, and media polarisation, the research examined how political actors and journalists utilise digital platforms to construct and amplify political narratives. Guided by an interpretivist philosophy and combining qualitative interview data

with Twitter content, the study investigated how political discourse is developed, circulated, and reconfigured in this digital context.

To achieve this aim, the study was guided by three objectives:

1. To critically analyse Twitter usage by prominent political parties in Pakistan as a strategic campaigning tool.

This objective was addressed by showing how PTI, PMLN, and PPP integrated Twitter into their broader campaign strategies. PTI adopted a decentralised model that encouraged members of its social media teams at multiple levels to participate in content creation and trend generation, reflecting the party's strong grassroots digital mobilisation. They are more organised in content creation and dissemination. PPP, by contrast, relied more heavily on leader-centred messaging and waited for the main message to float from the senior-most leadership in Bilawal House, as compared to the PTI, where content can be generated by senior political leadership, second-tier leadership, main social media teams or grassroot-level social media teams, while PMLN social media teams are passive, they wait for the statements of their leaders get famous on media and then start amplifying it. Their approach is defensive. All three are found investing in social media teams, having different strategies based on the differences in their vote banks. All three consider Twitter as a significant platform for posting strategic party messages. Framing theory was central to analysing these strategies, revealing how diagnostic and prognostic frames were used to attribute blame to rivals and present leaders as solutions, while moral frames portrayed leaders as guardians of national or cultural values. These practices confirmed that Twitter is not a random or open platform for political expression, but a carefully managed space where parties strategically craft messages to capture attention, generate visibility, and influence wider media agendas. Secondly, these practices also need to be understood within the dynamics of the digital sphere. Political parties did not treat

Twitter as a neutral channel for communication but as a strategically constructed space where visibility, legitimacy, and influence were contested. Hashtags, coordinated posting, and selective framing were used to dominate the platform's trending lists and to ensure that party narratives circulated widely. In this way, the digital sphere functioned as both a site of dissemination and a mechanism of amplification, where constructed frames were embedded, repeated, and normalised across networks. It is also important to recognise that these strategies cannot be understood in isolation from Pakistan's complex political landscape. The digital presence of political parties varies considerably across provinces, reflecting historical legacies, uneven internet access, and different patterns of party support. For instance, PTI's strong digital footprint aligned with its popularity among younger, urban voters, whereas PPP's strategy reflected its concentration in Sindh and reliance on leader-centric narratives. PMLN's approach was shaped by its base in Punjab, where it used Twitter to reinforce its identity as a party of governance and stability. These variations underscore that party strategies in the digital sphere were contingent on their regional presence and political positioning, demonstrating that framing and dissemination practices were deeply embedded in the uneven socio-political fabric of Pakistan.

2. To critically analyse the role of journalists on Twitter in circulating and amplifying political party messages.

This objective was addressed by analysing the activities of journalists both in their individual capacities and as representatives of mainstream news organisations. The study found that individual journalists frequently used Twitter to express opinions, comment on events, or selectively amplify frames aligned with their own preferences, thereby blurring the boundaries between professional reporting and partisan communication. At the same time, journalists also carried the narratives of their respective media organisations onto the platform, reproducing institutional framings in a faster, more interactive environment. The analysis further showed

that Twitter functioned simultaneously as a consumer of news where journalists picked up party messages, trends, and hashtags and as a source of news, with Twitter activity feeding directly back into broadcast and print coverage. In this way, the platform created a recursive loop between digital and mainstream spheres, demonstrating how journalists at both the individual and institutional levels play a pivotal role in the dissemination and reframing of political messages. These patterns reveal that journalists do more than simply report; they actively participate in shaping and disseminating political narratives within the digital public sphere. By amplifying selective messages and aligning them with their own political leanings or institutional agendas, journalists reinforce particular frames and elevate them to wider visibility. In doing so, they contribute to shaping the agenda of public debate, not only within Twitter but also across mainstream platforms that continue to carry authority in Pakistan's hybrid media system. This dual role illustrates how the professional norms of journalism verification, impartiality, and editorial distance are increasingly blurred on social media, as journalists operate simultaneously as reporters, commentators, and amplifiers of partisan discourse.

3. To examine the ways in which Twitter restructures political discourse and contributes to the formation of a digitally mediated public sphere in Pakistan.

This objective was addressed by analysing how Twitter reshapes political communication in ways that are both enabling and constraining. On one hand, the platform allows political leaders to bypass traditional gatekeepers and engage with followers in real time, fostering a sense of accessibility and responsiveness. On the other hand, these opportunities are filtered through algorithmic amplification, digital literacy divides, and elite dominance, which limit the inclusivity of participation. Rather than encouraging deliberation, the evidence suggested that Twitter discourse in Pakistan is characterised by immediacy, polarisation, and emotional intensity. Political parties exploited trending hashtags to create visibility, while trolling, gender

abuse, and disinformation campaigns undermined meaningful democratic debate. These findings extend theoretical debates on the public sphere by demonstrating that Pakistan's digital sphere does not replicate Habermasian ideals of rational-critical discourse. Instead, it represents a fragmented and contested arena where frames are strategically deployed, populist rhetoric thrives, and democratic deliberation is overshadowed by elite control and platform logics.

In summary, the study successfully addressed its central aim and three research objectives. It provided an in-depth account of how political communication in Pakistan is shaped within a hybrid media system, showing that Twitter functions not only as a distribution channel for political messages but also as a site where political discourse is strategically reconstructed. By integrating framing theory with the concept of the digital public sphere, the research contributes original insights into political communication, journalism, and media practices in fragile democracies. It highlights both the opportunities and the risks of digital political communication, illustrating how platforms like Twitter simultaneously expand avenues for participation and amplify practices that erode journalistic norms, polarise debate, and weaken deliberative democracy.

9.4 Contribution to knowledge

9.4.1 Recontextualising framing theory in fragile democracies

This study contributes to framing theory by demonstrating that, in the context of Pakistan, political frames deployed on Twitter are not fundamentally new but are deeply embedded in longstanding political and cultural traditions. Narratives of patriarchy, religion, corruption, victimhood, and anti-establishment resistance have long shaped political discourse in the country, and the findings show that these same frames were strategically repurposed for dissemination on Twitter. While digital affordances such as speed, hashtags, and algorithmic

amplification alter the visibility and intensity of these frames, the cultural substance remains continuous with Pakistan’s political history. This highlights an important theoretical insight: rather than technology transforming political culture, digital platforms adapt to and amplify pre-existing cultural and political logics. In this sense, the study enriches framing theory by showing how frames persist across communication environments but acquire new salience and reach when embedded within the logics of digital platforms. In addition, the findings demonstrate how framing on Twitter in Pakistan often takes on a distinctly populist character. Political actors consistently used diagnostic frames to delegitimise opponents as corrupt or unpatriotic, while employing moral frames to present themselves as saviours of the nation. These frames, already embedded in Pakistan’s political culture, gained new intensity in the digital sphere through repetition, hashtag campaigns, and algorithmic amplification.

Figure 9.1 A visual presentation of the adaptation of existing cultural frames on digital platforms in Pakistan

The result was a communicative environment in which negative and adversarial content travelled faster and further than issue-based or policy-oriented messages. This dynamic reflects a broader global trend towards populist political communication (Waisbord, 2018), but the study shows how it is uniquely adapted in Pakistan to long-standing cultural scripts of patriarchy, religion, and resistance. By foregrounding the amplification of negativity and the

performance of populism on digital platforms, the research adds to theoretical debates on the consequences of framing in hybrid media systems.

9.4.2 Rethinking journalism in the platformed environment

This study adds to the growing body of research on platformed journalism by showing how its dynamics operate in the Pakistani media landscape. Previous scholarship has examined how journalists adapt their practices to the logics of digital platforms, but this research extends those debates into a fragile democratic setting marked by entrenched partisanship and structural weaknesses in the media system. The findings reveal how Pakistani journalists used Twitter not only to report but also to comment, debate, and selectively amplify political narratives, often aligning with their own political preferences or those of their organisations. Twitter functioned both as a consumer of news, drawing content from party tweets and online debates, and as a source of news, with journalists' posts feeding directly back into mainstream coverage. This recursive loop blurred traditional gatekeeping functions and contributed to the salience of party-driven frames.

What distinguishes the Pakistani case is the way these dynamics intersect with the conditions of a fragile democracy. Mainstream media bias, shaped by ownership patterns and political alignments, is reproduced on Twitter rather than neutralised. Economic precarity and job insecurity push journalists to prioritise visibility and personal branding over editorial verification. Weak institutional checks mean that partisan commentary and unverified information circulate unchecked, while the absence of clear professional or regulatory policies leaves little accountability for online practices. These factors combine to create a hybrid media environment in which the ethical boundaries of journalism are consistently blurred. By situating these concerns in Pakistan, the study contributes to existing debates on platformed

journalism by demonstrating how digital affordances exacerbate long-standing weaknesses in journalistic ethics, accountability, and independence in fragile democracies.

The study also contributes to the understanding of the need for further research into the evolving trust deficit on social media platforms. While this research demonstrates how disinformation and a lack of verification are evident in both mainstream and digital journalism in Pakistan, it also raises wider questions about how audiences perceive credibility across platforms. As trust in traditional institutions declines globally, it is crucial to determine whether social media can offer alternative sources of authority or whether it perpetuates and exacerbates the same weaknesses. In fragile democracies such as Pakistan, where institutional checks are limited and political polarisation is intense, further investigation into how citizens evaluate information credibility online would help extend debates on media trust and democratic resilience.

9.4.3 Hybrid media entanglements and the complexity of the Pakistani public sphere

The study also contributes to knowledge of hybrid media systems by showing how political communication in Pakistan is shaped by the entanglement of digital and traditional platforms. Twitter, though an elite and relatively small-scale platform in terms of direct users, exerts disproportionate influence because its trends and frames are routinely taken up by television channels, which remain the most widely consumed medium nationwide. In this way, strategic frames constructed on Twitter gain amplification through mainstream media, reaching audiences far beyond the platform itself. Conversely, television debates and headlines also migrate into Twitter, where they are reframed and debated by journalists, party activists, and supporters. This recursive flow highlights how political narratives in Pakistan circulate across platforms rather than within them, creating a layered communicative environment.

The findings also reveal how the digital divide shapes party strategies. PTI invested heavily in Twitter to connect with its urban, youth-oriented base and to generate visibility in mainstream media, while PPP and PMLN relied more on Twitter as a signalling device to journalists, since much of their rural vote base remains outside the platform. This indicates that Twitter's influence lies less in its reach to ordinary voters and more in its ability to set agendas that cascade into television, print, and offline political mobilisation.

The study further demonstrates that political parties pursue multipronged strategies for dissemination, using each platform according to its popularity, affordances, and audience reach. TikTok's visual, short-video format is increasingly deployed to target younger, rural, and lower-literacy users; Facebook remains important for older demographics and organised political groups; and Twitter is primarily used to capture media attention and amplify elite debates. Importantly, these strategies are interconnected: a message launched on Twitter may be repurposed for television talk shows, shared in Facebook groups, or circulated as video snippets on TikTok.

This highlights an important theoretical insight: in fragile democracies, it is not the content of frames that shifts radically across platforms, but the modes of their dissemination, visibility, and resonance. By linking framing theory to the dynamics of hybrid media, the study demonstrates how Pakistan's public sphere is fragmented yet interconnected, with political communication strategies adapting to both structural inequalities and platform affordances.

9.4.4 Reconceptualising the political sphere in fragile democracies

This study extends beyond contributing to debates on the public sphere, adapting and refining public sphere theory for the context of fragile democracies. Existing formulations, often grounded in Western liberal traditions, assume a relatively unified public and the potential for rational deliberation. In contrast, the findings of this research demonstrate that Pakistan's

political sphere is fragmented, adversarial, and strategically managed, requiring a reconceptualisation of how public communication operates in such contexts.

The research identifies two key dimensions of this fragmentation. Structurally, political communication in Pakistan varies across provinces, reflecting differences in literacy, language, socio-economic development, and political culture. These variations prevent the formation of a unified national public. Digitally, participation is further fractured by platform divides: Twitter functions as an elite, agenda-setting space; television continues to dominate mass reach; while Facebook, TikTok, and WhatsApp extend political frames into grassroots communities. This multi-layered structure demonstrates that the Pakistani political sphere is hybrid and uneven, rather than singular and inclusive.

At the same time, the sphere is marked by adversarial rather than deliberative communication. The research shows how political actors and journalists rely on framing, disinformation, trolling, and coordinated campaigns to amplify polarisation and suppress dialogue. Far from promoting democratic engagement, digital affordances in Pakistan intensify existing cultural and political logics of religion, patriarchy, and populist victimhood while reinforcing elite control and undermining prospects for rational deliberation.

By making these dynamics visible, this research adapts public sphere theory to account for the realities of fragile democracies. It provides a framework for understanding political communication in contexts where structural inequality, digital divides, and elite dominance prevent the formation of a unified public, and where digital platforms reproduce and amplify adversarial communication rather than transform it.

While the empirical focus of this study is Pakistan, the findings have relevance beyond this context. The processes identified particularly the strategic use of platforms, the amplification of frames by mainstream media, and the pressures shaping journalistic practice may also inform

understanding of political communication in established democracies currently facing challenges such as polarisation, platform dominance, and declining trust in journalism. In this sense, the study offers analytically transferable insights into the functioning of digitally mediated public spheres under strain.

9.4.5 Policy and Professional Implications

Based on the findings of this study, there is a clear need for the development of regulatory and professional mechanisms that address political communication across digital platforms. While this research does not advocate direct censorship of social media, it supports the introduction of clearer guidelines and accountability structures for political actors and journalists operating in platformed environments. Comparative examples from other media systems indicate that platform governance can coexist with freedom of expression when grounded in transparency, proportionality, and ethical standards. In the Pakistani context, regulatory approaches similar to those applied to broadcast media such as sanctions for deliberate misinformation, hate speech, or incitement could be adapted for digital platforms in collaboration with media regulators, journalistic bodies, and platform providers. Such measures would help protect journalistic credibility and reduce the unchecked amplification of strategically manipulative content.

9.5 Limitations and directions for future research

Like all research, this study has limitations that reflect both deliberate choices and practical constraints. Acknowledging these makes clear the boundaries of the claims advanced here and suggests fruitful directions for future scholarship.

9.5.1 Methodological scope

This study was based on a qualitative, interpretivist design, relying on a relatively small number of elite interviews. This approach was chosen because it enabled access to rich, nuanced

accounts from politicians, journalists, and social media managers who play a central role in shaping political communication. However, the focus on elite perspectives necessarily excluded the voices of other actors, such as regional organisers, activists, or ordinary citizens. While the interpretivist approach allowed for a deep exploration of meaning-making and framing, it cannot capture the full diversity of experiences or claim statistical generalisability. Future studies could complement this design with larger-scale surveys, regional case studies, or mixed-methods approaches that include citizen perspectives, thereby broadening our understanding of how political communication operates across different layers of society.

The interview sample included a smaller number of politicians compared to journalists and social media managers, reflecting both practical access constraints and the scope of the study, which prioritised insight into strategic communication processes rather than political representation per se. Social media managers were therefore included alongside politicians due to their central role in planning, framing, and disseminating political narratives on Twitter. In this respect, the study captures strategic decision-making not only through elected representatives but also through actors directly responsible for managing political communication on digital platforms. While a larger number of politicians may have offered additional perspectives, the combination of politicians, social media managers, and senior journalists provided sufficient analytical depth to address the research questions, within the acknowledged access- and scope-related limitations of the study.

9.5.2 Platform selection

Twitter was chosen as the primary platform of analysis because of its prominence as an elite space in Pakistan, where journalists and politicians interact most visibly. This decision was justified within the scope of the study but also introduced limitations. Facebook, TikTok, Instagram, and WhatsApp play crucial roles in the country's media ecology, particularly for

younger, rural, and less literate audiences. By focusing narrowly on Twitter, the research risks over-emphasising elite discourse and underestimating how grassroots publics engage with and reinterpret political frames. Future research could adopt a comparative, cross-platform perspective, asking whether frames travel differently across platforms, whether their emotional intensity changes, and how platform-specific affordances such as virality on TikTok or private circulation on WhatsApp reshape political communication.

9.5.3 Data completeness

While this study analysed selected Twitter content in conjunction with elite interviews, it did not collate the entire dataset of Twitter activity across the research period. This meant that framing patterns were examined through a purposive sample rather than systematically across all party, journalist, and media accounts. A more comprehensive dataset would have allowed for the mapping of frame frequency, intensity, and interaction over time, providing a clearer picture of how political narratives were sustained or challenged during key events. Computational methods such as social network analysis or large-scale content analysis could complement qualitative insights in future studies, bridging depth with scale to capture the full dynamics of framing on digital platforms.

9.5.4 Temporal constraints

The research was conducted within a specific political and technological period, which inevitably limits its claims. Since the data was collected, political dynamics in Pakistan have shifted, and platform policies such as verification rules and algorithmic curation have evolved rapidly. These changes may alter the strategies political actors and journalists adopt, as well as the nature of audience engagement. Future longitudinal research is therefore necessary to examine whether trends identified in this study including polarisation, moralised blame frames, and the elite-driven use of Twitter persist, decline, or take new forms. Such work would also

help identify whether current practices represent temporary strategies or entrenched transformations in political communication.

9.5.5 Focus on elite accounts

While this study examined the role of journalists and mainstream media actors on Twitter, the analysis could not systematically collate and assess the full Twitter activity of Pakistan's mainstream media organisations. This represents an important limitation, as the institutional feeds of major television channels and newspapers and the patterns of engagement around them are central to understanding how mainstream media interacts with digital platforms. Analysing such data could reveal the extent to which news organisations use Twitter to set agendas, recycle party frames, or amplify polarising content. It could also provide insights into how audiences engage with media-originated content compared to political or individual journalistic accounts. Future studies could therefore undertake a large-scale analysis of mainstream media feeds on Twitter, mapping patterns of posting, retweeting, and audience response to build a fuller picture of the hybrid entanglement between legacy and digital media in Pakistan.

9.5.6 Scope of mainstream media analysis

While this study examined the role of journalists and incorporated examples of mainstream media activity on Twitter, the analysis could not systematically track the full output and engagement of mainstream media organisations on the platform. Instead, it drew selectively on Twitter posts linked to the events under study and complemented these with interview insights from journalists. This necessarily provided only a partial view of how mainstream media outlets as institutions use Twitter for example, how they structure their feeds, how frequently they repost party content, or how audiences engage with their posts. A more comprehensive dataset of media organisation Twitter activity would have enabled deeper analysis of the institutional dynamics that shape the hybrid media system. Future research could therefore

build on this study by collating longitudinal data from mainstream media accounts to examine their framing practices, their interaction with political parties, and the extent to which their Twitter activity influences or reproduces polarisation in Pakistan's political sphere.

9.5.7 Gendered trolling and online harassment

While this study documented instances of trolling and abusive behaviour, particularly targeting women journalists and politicians, it did not conduct a systematic analysis of the scale, intensity, or linguistic characteristics of such online harassment. The data revealed the presence of gendered abuse, but this was treated as part of the broader dynamics of polarisation and adversarial communication rather than as a central analytical focus. A dedicated study of gendered trolling could examine how political parties and their followers deploy targeted hate speech, how language is weaponised against women in public life, and how such practices affect participation and representation in the political sphere. Future research could employ discourse analysis, computational methods, or mixed approaches to measure the extent of this phenomenon and to understand its implications for democratic communication, press freedom, and gender equality in fragile democracies.

9.5.8 Trust and reliability of digital platforms

A further limitation of this study is that it primarily examined how political actors and journalists construct and disseminate frames, rather than systematically assessing how audiences evaluate the credibility of these messages. Yet, the findings consistently highlight issues of trust: both interview participants and existing scholarship point to declining confidence in mainstream media, while the spread of disinformation, trolling, and partisan framing raises urgent questions about the reliability of digital platforms. The study therefore establishes the need for deeper research on how citizens interpret, verify, or resist political messages online, and how trust in journalism and political communication is negotiated in

fragile democracies. Future work could focus explicitly on measuring levels of trust in digital platforms, assessing the conditions under which users perceive political information as credible, and examining the consequences of these trust dynamics for democratic resilience.

Taken together, these limitations underline the contextual and interpretive nature of the study. At the same time, they open multiple pathways for further inquiry: cross-platform analysis, audience reception studies, computational mapping of frames, longitudinal tracking of political communication, and comparative work across other fragile democracies. In this way, the limitations themselves highlight the potential for building a richer, more globalised understanding of digital political communication in non-Western contexts.

9.6 Conclusion

This thesis has shown that Twitter is not a neutral arena for political communication in Pakistan but a strategically managed platform where political parties, journalists, and mainstream media actively construct and contest narratives. In doing so, it has demonstrated that the digital public sphere in Pakistan cannot be understood through Western models alone. Instead, it is shaped by uneven access, socio-economic divides, and deeply embedded political cultures.

The research set out to explore how Twitter is strategically employed in shaping political communication in a fragile democracy. It found that Twitter plays a dual role: as a site of strategic framing by political actors and as a source of news and frames for mainstream media. Journalists emerged as particularly significant, operating both as amplifiers of party narratives and as independent actors whose own biases, branding, and unverified content contributed to the salience of political messages. This dual role blurs the line between journalism and political communication, raising questions about professional ethics, verification, and public trust in an increasingly platformised media environment.

By combining framing theory with the concept of the digital public sphere, this study provides a contextually grounded account of how digital platforms reshape political communication beyond the Global North. It extends framing theory by showing the persistence of cultural frames such as patriarchy, religion, and populism in digital environments, while also contributing to debates on journalism by highlighting how platform logics have disrupted established editorial norms. In Pakistan, where mainstream media already faces criticism for bias and commercialisation, the entanglement of journalists with political actors on Twitter intensifies existing concerns over trust and credibility.

Ultimately, this thesis demonstrates that political communication on Twitter in Pakistan cannot be understood as either a simple extension of Western models of the public sphere or as a purely disruptive digital innovation. Instead, it represents a hybrid formation where historical frames, party strategies, journalistic practices, and platform logics converge. By situating framing processes within the dynamics of a digital public sphere, the study not only advances theory but also offers critical insights for journalism practice, policymaking, and the resilience of democratic communication in fragile democracies. While the study is necessarily limited in scope, particularly in its focus on Twitter, it opens important avenues for future research into other platforms such as TikTok, YouTube, and WhatsApp, as well as questions of media trust, journalistic ethics, and gendered online abuse

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levelling of allegations without any proof against Gen Faisal Naseer and officers of our Intelligence Agency cannot be allowed and will not be tolerated. Twitter.

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List of Appendixes

Appendix A: Copy of Information Sheet

Name of School: Business and Creative Industries

Name of Degree: PhD

Title of Project: Role of Twitter in Shaping Political Communication: Case Study of Pakistan

Ethics approval number: 16721

I would like to invite you to take part in a research study. Before you decide, I would like to explain you why the research is being done and what it involves. Please take time to read the following information carefully. Please feel free to ask questions if anything you read is not clear or would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you want to take part.

Thank you for reading this.

My Name is Naheed Akhtar I am a 2nd year PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland. As my PhD project I have chosen to research on Role of Twitter in Shaping Political Communication in Pakistan. The University of the West of Scotland School of Business and Creative Industries is supporting me to undertake this project.

What is the purpose of this investigation?

The research is being conducted for the fulfilment of my PhD study at University of West of Scotland. It aims to explore the evolution of political communication with the changing media technologies. As a big part of academia in the field of social sciences particularly political communication is adding to the knowledge of evolution of political communication with the changing patterns and priorities in political communication due to digitalization in developed, developing and autocratic regimes, this project focusses to investigate how Twitter as a technology has provided a platform for political parties to run their political campaigns and how it has challenged/complemented the mainstream media and journalists in Pakistan. It will explore how aware political parties in Pakistan are about the potential of Twitter as a strategic tool for their political campaigns. The discussion involves how contemporary reimagined concept of public sphere can be implied on the current study. It deliberates upon the argument about the concept of transforming public sphere which has been celebrated and discussed enormously in western settings and attempts to relate it in a fragile democracy like Pakistan in the south Asian region.

Research Objective

The study will address the following objectives:

- (1) To investigate Twitter usage by prominent political parties in Pakistan as a strategic campaigning tool.
- (2) To investigate role of party activists, media influencers and journalists to spread messages of political parties to target potential voters

Do you have to take part?

Participation in this study is voluntary. I will describe the study and go through the information sheet, which will be given to you. I will then ask you to sign a consent form to show you agree to take part. At any time, you are free to withdraw without giving a reason. This will not affect the standard of care you receive.

What will you do in the project?

You will be required to attend one interview session which will cover the topic of use of Twitter by political parties for political campaigning, how and what political parties post on Twitter and how beneficial it is. What are the differences, challenges of this new media as compared to the traditional offline political campaigns or the mainstream media political campaigns. The interview will take place in your organisational setting or online as per your availability. Each interview will last approximately 35-45 minutes. The interviews will be recorded on a mobile and handwritten notes will be taken. In the review of guidelines by the Social Research Association (2003) principles have been taken to ensure respect for privacy, confidentiality and protection of data, honesty and integrity of information and preventing harm and risk to yourself and other participants taking part. However, if at any time during the process you feel uncomfortable answering a question you can decline to answer it.

Why have you been invited to take part?

You have been chosen to take part because you have experience of political communication as has experienced evolution of political communication in Pakistan starting from only one media option to multiple private channels and now the social media. You have in-depth knowledge and understanding of political campaigns of main political parties in Pakistan. You are considered as an expert of this field of study.

What are the potential risks to you in taking part?

During the research you will be not exposed to any physical, psychological or legal risk or harm.

Interview questions have been structured in such a way so that your privacy will be protected and no pressure will be put on you to answer sensitive questions. All information pertaining to you as an individual and your organisation will be anonymised and kept confidential (if you require). The data you provide will not compromise your position in the organisation at any point in time.

What happens to the information in the project?

All information received will be stored securely in password protected system or password protected electronic files which is under my use only and the access will be provided to supervisor for academic guidance purpose. All references to individuals and organisations will be removed or given pseudonyms of data is to be included within the submitted study unless express permission has been given. All data will be destroyed after successful completion of PhD degree.

The University of the West of Scotland is registered with the Information Commissioner's Office who implements the Data Protection Act 1998. All personal data on participants will be processed in accordance with the provisions of the Data Protection Act 1998.

Thank you for reading this information – please ask any questions if you are unsure about what is written here.

What happens next?

If you are happy to be involved in this project, please sign the consent form to confirm this. If you do not wish to be involved, thank you very much for your time.

If desired, a feedback report can be sent once the investigation is complete.

This investigation was granted ethical approval by the University of the West of Scotland, School of Business and Creative Industries ethics committee.

If you have any questions/concerns, during or after the investigation, or wish to contact an independent person to whom any questions may be directed or from whom further information may be sought please contact:

School Ethics Committee

School of Business and Creative Industries

Paisley Campus

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley

PA1 2BE

Researcher Details

Address: [REDACTED]

E-mail: [REDACTED]

Telephone: [REDACTED]

Supervisor Details:

E-mail: [REDACTED]

Appendix B: Participant consent form

Title of Project: Role of Twitter in Shaping Political Communication: Case Study of Pakistan

Please initial box:

- 1 I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet dated for the above study with the relevant information and have had the opportunity to ask questions.
- 2 I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason.
- 3 I understand that my responses will be anonymised and that confidentiality will be ensured.
- 4 I agree to take part in the above study.

Your signature will certify that you have voluntarily decided to take part in this research study having read and understood the information in the sheet for participants. It will also certify that you have had adequate opportunity to discuss the study with the researcher and that all questions have been answered to your satisfaction.

Name of Participant:

Signature:

Date:

Name of researcher:

Signature:

Contact information:

Date:

1 copy for participant and 1 for researcher

Appendix C: Ethics approval letter

07/06/2023

Dear Naheed Akhtar,

Your application 21452: Role of Twitter in Shaping political communication: Case Study of Pakistan, submission 16721, has been approved by the Business and Creative Industries SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr John Quinn

Appendix D: Interview Schedule for journalists

- 1) To what extent has Twitter, as a social media platform, affected mainstream media operations in Pakistan in terms of political communication?
 - a. PROBE: Is it shifted to Twitter? Is it going parallel, is Twitter feeding news to mainstream media or otherwise?
- 2) What type of content do politicians and political parties share on Twitter in Pakistan?
- 3) What type of political content from political parties do you retweet, comment, or use as content for your news organization?
- 4) What role do you think journalists are playing in the political campaigning/communication of political parties?
- 5) How do you think political parties use Twitter for their political campaigning?
 - a. PROBE: Networking? Are they planning for that? Involving media teams?
- 6) In what way (s) do you think online campaigns on Twitter are beneficial to political parties' offline campaigns?
 - a. PROBE: What type of language/ images, audios, videos, politicians use for their messages?
- 7) What topics or subjects in Pakistani politics do mainstream parties use in common for their campaigns,
 - a. PROBE: How have they evolved with the passage of time and technology?
- 8) What element of strategic planning do you notice behind Twitter political campaigns of political party (PPP, PMLN, TLP, PTI)?
 - a. PROBE: Which strategies do political parties use on Twitter to
 - defend their position.

- project their party image
- project party leader
- project individual party members
- defame other parties
- snub journalists who criticize and question
- propaganda

Follow-up questions

- How did (PTI,PPP,PMLN) media SMTs utilized Twitter as a platform when former Prime Minister Imran Khan was ousted in April 2022?
- How did the party framed its messages to protest the decision against IK? How far do you think they were successful?
- How did the (PTI, PPP,PMLN) media SMTs, official Twitter accounts, party members utilized Twitter as a platform after the deteriorated law and order situation in Pakistan following the arrest of IK? What type of text, images and video messages were posted?

Appendix E: Copy of interview schedule for politicians and social media team leaders

- 9) To what extent Twitter as a social media platform has affected mainstream media operations in Pakistan in terms of political communication? Is it shifted to Twitter? is it going parallel, is Twitter feeding news to Mainstream media or otherwise?
- 10) What type of content you as a party representative/ SMT lead prefer to post/share on Twitter?
- 11) To what extent Twitter keeps you updated about activities of other political parties, government decisions and important updates?
- 12) Who decides the content to be posted? Does this come from the main party leadership, or you are independent to post anything?
- 13) Is there any specific timing for the tweets, number of tweets per day for you?
- 14) Who do you think your target audience is most of the times when you post? (national, international, journalists, mainstream media) ?
- 15) Mainstream media is polarized politically, how do your party counter propaganda news against your party by using Twitter? To what extent Twitter has helped to counter mainstream media monopoly?
- 16) How do you think political parties use Twitter for their political campaigning? Networking? Are they planning for that? Implying media teams?
- 17) How do you think online campaign on Twitter is benefitting to political parties' offline campaigns? How does your party connect to rural and far flung areas of Pakistan through Twitter campaigns?

18) How do you perform your duty as SMT leader/ information secretary (PPP, PMLN, PTI) utilize Twitter to

- defend party position.
- project your party image
- project party leader
- project individual party members
- defame other parties.
- snub journalists who criticize and question or miss report
- propaganda

Follow-up Questions:

- How did your party (PTI, PMLN, PPP) media SMTs utilize Twitter as a platform when former Prime Minister Imran Khan was ousted in April 2022? What type of photo, video, text messages, hashtags were used to highlight the issue.
- How did the (PTI, PPP, PMLN) media SMTs, party official Twitter accounts, and party members utilize Twitter as a platform after the deteriorated law and order situation in Pakistan following the arrest of IK? What type of text, images and video messages were posted?

Appendix F: copy of the codebook downloaded from NVivo

PhD project Phase 1

Codes

Name	Description	Files	References
Interdependance of Twitter and mainstream media		15	65
Adoption of Twitter by mainstream media		5	9
centrality of Twitter in News communication		11	30
mainstream media is powerful, twitter has not changed everything		1	1
Twitter Primary source of News		4	12
Theme - Political content on Twitter, public sphere and activism		15	120
digital sphere		10	31
flow of Twitter narrative to offline public		4	6
impact of Twitter campaign on Election dynamics		6	10
Impact of Twitter campaign on election dynamics		3	3
Impact of Twitter narratives on Public activism		6	8
impact of Twitter on political discourse		10	31

Name	Description	Files	References
disinformation		6	17
negative impact of Twitter narrative on political discourse		1	1
negative impact of Twitter on social fabric		5	7
Twitter use for street activism		2	2
types of political content on Twitter		11	32
differentiation between party and individual politician responses		1	1
portrayal of leader at national and global stage		1	1
Public sentiment expression		7	13
Theme - Presence of those who matter		14	80
expatriate running PTI campaigns from abroad		8	10
Impact of celebrities		2	2
level of social media knowledge in the political parties		5	21
comparison between west and pakistan on twitter		6	9
Presence of all political powers on Twitter		8	10

Name	Description	Files	References
Role of journalists in shaping political communication		7	14
Digital media journalists are damaging journalistic ethics		3	4
The positive impact of Twitter for journalists		4	5
Social media is a challenge to journalists		4	5
urban elites are influenced by Twitter narratives		10	12
youth, the main power of Twitter narrative flow		7	11
Theme - strategic use of Twitter by political powers		15	139
Effective strategic use of Twitter by PTI		6	11
framing of messages on Twitter		11	28
Narrative building mechanism in political parties		8	33
Use of state money to run party campaigns		3	7
dedicated social media teams		6	9
financing of media teams		1	3

Appendix G: Screen Shot from NVivo Analysis (1)

The screenshot displays the NVivo interface with a list of codes. The table below represents the data shown in the 'Codes' pane.

Name	Files	References	Created on	Created by	Modified on	Modified by
Adoption of Twitter by mainstream media	5	9	29/08/2024 1	NHD	20/03/2025 1	NHD
centrality of Twitter in News communication	11	30	29/08/2024 1	NHD	20/09/2024 1	NHD
mainstream media is powerful, twitter has not cha	1	1	14/09/2024 1	NHD	14/09/2024 1	NHD
role of journalists in shapping political communica	7	14	29/05/2025 1	NHD	20/03/2025 1	NHD
digital media journalists damaging journalistic	4	5	29/05/2025 1	NHD	08/03/2025 1	NHD
positive impact of Twitter for journalists	4	5	29/05/2025 1	NHD	15/09/2024 1	NHD
social media a challenge to journalists	4	5	29/05/2025 1	NHD	08/03/2025 1	NHD
Twitter Primary source of News	4	12	29/08/2024 1	NHD	15/09/2024 1	NHD
Theme - Political content on Twitter, public sphere an	15	87	23/09/2024 1	NHD	23/09/2024 1	NHD
impact of Twitter campaign on Election dynamics	6	10	29/08/2024 1	NHD	20/03/2025 1	NHD
Impact of Twitter narratives on Public activism	6	8	31/08/2024 1	NHD	19/09/2024 1	NHD
impact of Twitter on political discourse	10	35	31/08/2024 1	NHD	20/03/2025 1	NHD
Twitter use for street activism	2	2	29/08/2024 1	NHD	19/09/2024 1	NHD
types of political content on Twitter	11	32	29/08/2024 1	NHD	20/09/2024 1	NHD
Theme - Presence of those who matter	14	80	23/09/2024 1	NHD	23/09/2024 1	NHD
Theme - strategic use of Twitter by political powers	15	179	31/08/2024 1	NHD	20/03/2025 1	NHD

Appendix H: Screenshot from NVivo (2)

The screenshot displays the NVivo interface with a list of cases. The table below represents the data shown in the 'Cases' pane.

Name	Codes	References	Modified on	Modified by	Classification
P1	13	27	23/09/2024 11:51	NHD	
P2	16	34	23/09/2024 11:51	NHD	
P3	17	39	23/09/2024 11:51	NHD	
P4	14	31	23/09/2024 11:51	NHD	

Appendix I: Twitter of political parties for the events 10th April 2022, 9 May 2023 (left) Twitter data for November 2024 (right).

The screenshot shows an Excel spreadsheet with two main sections. On the left, there is a list of files with columns for 'Name' and 'Type'. The files listed include names like 'HaleemAdil2023-April23-May9', 'ImranKhan-2022-April10-April26', etc. On the right, the 'Mention Data Export' table is displayed, containing the following data:

Query Id	Query Nar Date	Title	Snippet	Full Text	Url	Domain	Se
1	2E+09	UmarChee 2024-12-0	وینڈی کل ایک وینڈی کل ایک		http://twi	twitter.co	ne
2	2E+09	UmarChee 2024-12-0 RT	@Razz: RT @Razz:		http://twi	twitter.co	ne
3	2E+09	UmarChee 2024-12-0 RT	@Khur RT @Khur RT @Khur		http://twi	twitter.co	ne
4	2E+09	UmarChee 2024-12-0 RT	@soule RT @soule RT @soule		http://twi	twitter.co	ne
5	2E+09	UmarChee 2024-12-0 RT	@iqrar RT @iqrar RT @iqrar		http://twi	twitter.co	ne
6	2E+09	UmarChee 2024-12-0 RT	@Klasr RT @Klasr RT @Klasr		http://twi	twitter.co	ne
7	2E+09	UmarChee 2024-12-0 RT	@Habi RT @Habi RT @Habi		http://twi	twitter.co	ne
8	2E+09	UmarChee 2024-12-0 RT	@Sheh RT @Sheh RT @Sheh		http://twi	twitter.co	ne
9	2E+09	UmarChee 2024-12-0	@SyedMu @SyedMu @SyedMu		http://twi	twitter.co	ne
10	2E+09	UmarChee 2024-12-0 RT	@Syed RT @Syed RT @Syed		http://twi	twitter.co	ne
11	2E+09	UmarChee 2024-12-0	صرف پاکستان صرف پاکستان		http://twi	twitter.co	ne
12	2E+09	UmarChee 2024-12-0	صرف پاکستان صرف پاکستان		http://twi	twitter.co	ne

Appendix J: Twitter data of selected journalists, November 2024

The screenshot shows an Excel spreadsheet with a table containing the following data:

Region	Co Region	City Code	Account T	Assignmer	Author	Avatar	Category	Checked	Circulator	City	Display UF	Expanded	Facebook	Facebook	Facebook	Facebook	Facebook	Facebook	Fu
PAK	Punjab	Punjab	PAK.Punjab	individual	TalatHuss	https://au		false		Rawalpinc	https://x.c		0	0	0	0	0	0	Ta
PAK	Punjab	Punjab	PAK.Punjab	individual	KlasraRau	https://au		false		Rawalpinc	https://x.c		0	0	0	0	0	0	Kla
PAK	Punjab	Punjab	PAK.Punjab	individual	KlasraRau	https://au		false		Rawalpinc	https://x.c		0	0	0	0	0	0	Kla
PAK	Punjab	Punjab	PAK.Punjab	individual	asmashira	https://au		false		Rawalpinc	https://x.c		0	0	0	0	0	0	as
PAK	Punjab	Punjab	PAK.Punjab	individual	TalatHuss	https://au		false		Rawalpinc	https://x.c		0	0	0	0	0	0	Ta
PAK	Punjab	Punjab	PAK.Punjab	individual	KlasraRau	https://au		false		Rawalpinc	https://x.c		0	0	0	0	0	0	Kla
PAK	Punjab	Punjab	PAK.Punjab	individual	asmashira	https://au		false		Rawalpinc	https://x.c		0	0	0	0	0	0	as
PAK	Punjab	Punjab	PAK.Punjab	individual	asmashira	https://au		false		Rawalpinc	https://x.c		0	0	0	0	0	0	as
PAK	Punjab	Punjab	PAK.Punjab	individual	asmashira	https://au		false		Rawalpinc	https://x.c		0	0	0	0	0	0	as
PAK	Punjab	Punjab	PAK.Punjab	individual	asmashira	https://au		false		Rawalpinc	https://x.c		0	0	0	0	0	0	as
PAK	Punjab	Punjab	PAK.Punjab	individual	asmashira	https://au		false		Rawalpinc	https://x.c		0	0	0	0	0	0	as
PAK	Punjab	Punjab	PAK.Punjab	individual	asmashira	https://au		false		Rawalpinc	https://x.c		0	0	0	0	0	0	as
PAK	Punjab	Punjab	PAK.Punjab	individual	asmashira	https://au		false		Rawalpinc	https://x.c		0	0	0	0	0	0	as
PAK	Punjab	Punjab	PAK.Punjab	individual	asmashira	https://au		false		Rawalpinc	https://x.c		0	0	0	0	0	0	as
PAK	Punjab	Punjab	PAK.Punjab	individual	asmashira	https://au		false		Rawalpinc	https://x.c		0	0	0	0	0	0	as
PAK	Punjab	Punjab	PAK.Punjab	individual	asmashira	https://au		false		Rawalpinc	https://x.c		0	0	0	0	0	0	as
PAK	Punjab	Punjab	PAK.Punjab	individual	asmashira	https://au		false		Rawalpinc	https://x.c		0	0	0	0	0	0	as

